

**LARGE-SCALE REAL-TIME 5G
MULTI-TENANT NETWORK
TOPOLOGY DISCOVERY AND
HOLOGRAPHIC MONITORING**

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This research based on publications has been funded by 2 different research projects where the candidate has been working actively delivering tasks like designs, implementations, deployments over 5G mobile edge computing infrastructures:

- **Project 1:**

Project Title:	SLICENET: END-TO-END COGNITIVE NETWORK SLICING AND SLICE MANAGEMENT FRAMEWORK IN VIRTUALISED MULTI-DOMAIN, MULTI-TENANT 5G NETWORKS
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This research base on publications is an aggregation of international journals, international conferences and intellectual property rights where the candidate is the main contributor. Thus, the candidate declare that he has made a major contribution to all of the work that has been produced. The following list shows the accepted and published publications in **international journals** and **conferences** that the candidate has been made the main contribution in the research. A clear linkage among the plot line of these outputs is defined in Table 5.1:

- **Output 1 (Journal):**

Authors:	Ignacio Sanchez-Navarro , Ana Serrano Mamolar, Qi Wang, Jose M. Alcaraz Calero
Title:	5GTopoNet: Real-time topology discovery and management on 5G multi-tenant networks [1]
Journal:	Future Generation Computer Systems, Elsevier Imp. Factor: 7.187 (2020)
Volume:	114
Pages:	435-447
Year:	January 2021
DOI:	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.future.2020.08.025

- **Output 2 (Journal):**

Authors:	Ignacio Sanchez-Navarro , Jorge Bernal Bernabe, Jose M. Alcaraz-Calero, Qi Wang
Title:	Advanced spatial network metrics for cognitive management of 5G networks [2]
Journal:	Soft Computing, Springer Imp. Factor: 3.643 (2020)
Volume:	25
Pages:	215-232
Year:	January 2021
DOI:	https://doi.org/10.1007/s00500-020-05132-y

- **Output 3 (Conference):**

Authors:	Ignacio Sanchez-Navarro , Pablo Salva-Garcia, Qi Wang, Jose M. Alcaraz Calero
Title:	New Immersive Interface for Zero-Touch Management in 5G Networks [3]
Conference:	2020 IEEE 3rd 5G World Forum (5GWF)
Pages:	6
Year:	2020
DOI:	https://doi.org/10.1109/5GWF49715.2020.9221116

- **Output 4 (Conference):**

Authors:	Ignacio Sanchez-Navarro , Jose M. Alcaraz Calero, Qi Wang
Title:	Topology Awareness for Smart 5G eMBB Network Slicing VNF Placement [4]
Conference:	2020 IEEE 21st International Symposium on "A World of Wireless, Mobile and Multimedia Networks" (WoWMoM)
Pages:	6
Year:	2020
DOI:	https://doi.org/10.1109/WoWMoM49955.2020.00076

- **Output 5 (Software):**

Author:	Ignacio Sanchez-Navarro
Title:	Layout Monitoring Agent (LMA)
Description:	LMA software implements a monitoring tool that receives the information discovered about a 5G multi-tenant network topology and creates a logical spatial representation that integrates all physical and virtual components of the network in a 3D spatial graph layout. This layout is reported as individual metrics for every component of the topology. The value of the metric is a triplet of float numbers that represent the 3 coordinates in the space.
Url:	https://gitavcn.uws.ac.uk/isanchez/lma.git

- **Output 6 (Software):**

Author:	Ignacio Sanchez-Navarro
Title:	5G Topology GUI
Description:	This software provides a Graphical User Interface (GUI) that allows the user to visualize a complete 5G multi-tenant network topology, in addition to monitoring and management. The software is interconnected with other software elements that provide real-time topology discovery and metrics that allow real-time visualization, monitoring and management capabilities. The GUI software is a multi-platform software ready to run in PC, HoloLens 1 and HoloLens 2.
Url:	https://gitavcn.uws.ac.uk/isanchez/TopologyGUI.git

- **Output 7 (Software):**

Author:	Ignacio Sanchez-Navarro
Title:	Topology Monitoring Agent (TMA)
Description:	TMA software provides a monitoring component that stores the topological information of a large-scale 5G multi-tenant network in a graph database. TMA also aggregates real-time performance metrics, such as bandwidth or latency, to this topological information. Using the graph database, TMA is able to produce topology awareness spatial metrics such as centrality based metrics.
Url:	https://gitavcn.uws.ac.uk/isanchez/tma.git

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Declaration

I hereby declare that except where specific references are made to the work of others, the contents of this dissertation are original and have not been submitted in whole or in part for consideration for any other degree or qualification in this, or any other University. This dissertation is my own work and contains nothing which is the outcome of work done in collaboration with others, except as specified in the text and acknowledgements. This dissertation contains more than 10,000 and less than 25,000 words excluding appendices, bibliography, footnotes.

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Glossary of Terms

5G Fifth-Generation.

5G-TA 5G-Topology Agent.

5GCC 5G Closeness Centrality.

5GMA 5G Monitoring Agent.

AMF Access and Mobility Function.

AMQP Advanced Message Queuing Protocol.

API Application Program Interface.

AR Augmented Reality.

AUSF Authentication Server Function.

C-RAN Cloud-based Radio Access Networks.

CAPEX Capital Expenditures.

CDN Content Distribution Networks.

CDP Cisco Discovery Protocol.

CU Centralized Unit.

DHCP Dynamic Host Configuration Protocol.

DNS Domain Name System.

DU Distributed Unit.

eMBB Enhanced Mobile Broadband.

EPC Evolved Packet Core.

FMA Flow Monitoring Agent.

FPS Frames Per Second.

GNN Graph Neural Networks.

GRE Generic Routing Encapsulation.

GUI Graphical User Interface.

ICMP Internet Control Message Protocol.

IMSI International Mobile Subscriber Identity.

IoT Internet of Things.

IP Internet Protocol.

ISC Internet Service Consumer.

ISP Internet Service Provider.

JSON JavaScript Object Notation.

KPI Key Performance Indicator.

LLDP Link-Layer Discovery Protocol.

LMA Layout Monitoring Agent.

LTE-M Long-Term Evolution for Machines.

MANO Management and Orchestration.

MEC Multi-Access Edge Computing.

MIMO Multiple-input Multiple-output.

MME Mobility Management Entity.

mMTC Massive Machine Type Communications.

MTTA Multi-Tenant Topology Agent.

NB-IoT Narrowband-IoT.

ODL OpenDaylight.

OPEX Operational Expenditures.

OSI Open Systems Interconnection.

PCF Policy Control Function.

PGW Packet Data Network Gateway.

PLMN Public Land Mobile Network.

PM Physical Machine.

PMA Process Monitoring Agent.

PoP Points of Presence.

PTA Physical Topology Agent.

QoS Quality of Service.

RAN Radio Access Network.

RIA Resource Inventory Agent.

RMA Resource Monitoring Agent.

RRH Remote Radio Head.

RSCP Received Signal Code Power.

RSSI Received Signal Strength Indicator.

RSU Road Side Unit.

SDN Software-Defined Networking.

SDR Software-Defined Radio.

SGW Serving Gateway.

SLA Service-Level Agreement.

SMF Session Management Function.

SNMP Simple Network Management Protocol.

SSH Secure SHell.

TEDP Tree Exploration Discovery Protocol.

TIM Topology Inventory Manager.

TMA Topology Monitoring Agent.

UDM User Data Management.

UE User Equipment.

UPF User Plane Function.

URLLC Ultra-Reliable and Low-Latency Communications.

USRP Universal Software Radio Peripheral.

VIM Virtual Infrastructure Manager.

VLAN Virtual Local Area Network.

VM Virtual Machine.

VNF Virtual Network Function.

VNO Virtual Network Operator.

VR Virtual Reality.

VXLAN Virtual Extensible Local Area Network.

WMI Windows Management Instrumentation.

Abstract

The new generation of mobile networks including Fifth-Generation (5G) and beyond are empowered by virtualisation and softwarisation to reduce both capital and operating expenditures, whilst benefiting from network programmability and flexibility for various use cases. Meanwhile, virtualisation and softwarisation introduce unprecedented complexities to network infrastructure topologies, and thus impose substantial challenges to network topology management.

This research investigates innovative approaches to help reduce the new operational costs that arise with the complexity associated to the introduction of these complex topologies. In addition, it investigates more efficient ways to understand the network, providing a spatial layout of the multi-tenant 5G network topologies. To achieve a complete management in real time for both, virtual and physical networks, this research explores ways to improve the behaviour of the different components of the infrastructure by utilising spatial metrics.

The primary innovation beyond the state of the art technology is the novel architecture to support the discovery and rendering of software data paths, containers and virtual machines, with support for geographically distributed edges. This architecture is composed of a series of components capable of discovering information in real-time about the network topology, and using it to carry out monitoring and management tasks. Among them, Layout Monitoring Agent (LMA), Topology Monitoring Agent (TMA) and Topology Graphical User Interface (GUI) are the direct results of this research work. LMA provides layout structures on the graph that forms the network topology, so that the topology GUI can place each element of the network in a logically ordered way. Topology GUI is the rendering application that allows network topology monitoring in real time. It is implemented for both Windows-based

computers and holographic headsets (HoloLens 1st Gen and HoloLens 2nd Gen). TMA provides spatial metrics to take allocation decisions on where to place new components through the virtual and physical networks. This calculation of such metrics is so complex that until now, it has been completely impractical to calculate them in acceptable time frames; however, a significant improvement in such calculations has been achieved to make them usable for multi-tenant 5G topologies. All these components have achieved another important innovation, which is the flexibility to support the differentiation of business roles by means of a novel method to perform an alignment of data models, associated with each of the infrastructures, and owned by each of them of such different roles.

LMA, TMA and topology GUI have been designed, implemented and empirically validated, and experiment results have demonstrated promising scalability. LMA is able to generate a topology layout structure for a network with 37,000 devices in less than six minutes, and subsequently to perform updates in real-time. Topology GUI is able to render the same topology in approximately 100 minutes, and also allows real-time navigation and updates after the initial rendering. Finally, TMA is able to calculate the metrics for a network topology with more than one million devices in approximately two minutes, and such performance would be otherwise completely impracticable (in hundreds of years) without TMA.

Part I

Summary

Chapter 1

Introduction

The mobile communication networks is continuously evolving to satisfy the requirements imposed by mobile users. Fifth-Generation (5G) and beyond mobile networks have to be better prepared to deliver higher data rates [5] and lower latency [6], among other Key performance indicators (KPIs), than previous network generations for an unprecedented number of connected devices, which is growing by the billions [7] [8].

On the move to 5G mobile networks, the International Telecommunication Union (ITU) [9] has published three communication scenarios that 5G networks should support to provide the key minimum technical performance requirements: Enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB), Ultra-Reliable and Low-Latency Communications (URLLC) and Massive Machine Type Communications (mMTC). These three use cases encompass different scenarios associated to current networks such as Virtual Reality (VR)/Augmented Reality (AR) applications, 360-degree video streaming, self-driving cars, massive Internet of Things (IoT) connections, and more.

The reduction of both Capital Expenditures (CAPEX) and Operational Expenditures (OPEX) are some of the main motivations pursued by telecommunications companies. It is incredibly important due to the exponential growth of 5G mobile subscribers. In addition, it is necessary to find a new way to carry out efficient changes in the infrastructure, due to the size that 5G networks will reach.

To achieve the full implementation of 5G mobile networks, it is necessary to increase the capacity per square kilometre as well as the bandwidth and minimise the latency. However, there is a physical limit in the current physical infrastructures to these benefits, in addition to the large amount of space needed for the deployment of a conventional telecommunication base station. Operating at higher frequencies, 5G mobile network infrastructures are based on the deployment of small cells that, despite having a smaller radius of reach, can offer higher bandwidth and lower latency. Due to their reduced size, a larger number of small cells can be deployed.

These small cells make use of virtualisation and containerisation ¹ [10] technologies, moving from centralised Radio Access Network (RAN) to software-based cloud RAN in order to achieve space reduction. This allows the infrastructure to be managed from anywhere, leading to a significant reduction in OPEX. In addition, this enables Internet Service Provider (ISP) owners to dynamically and efficiently reuse this scarce and expensive resource, leading to the concepts of overlay networks and multi-tenancy.

Overlay network refers to logical networks created on top of physical networks. These are networks based on virtualised and containerised network components that run on top of the physical infrastructure components of the network. These components emulate physical components, but simultaneously allow a more optimal distribution of physical resources, so that it is possible to make better usage of resources. Overlay networks also allow isolating the network resources between different virtualised components, although they run on the same physical machine. Multi-tenancy means that two or more Virtual Network Operator (VNO) can share the same physical resources through virtualised components in an isolated way.

On the other hand, virtualisation and containerisation impose the usage of software data paths to allow the connectivity between virtual and physical network interfaces. These software data paths impose significant challenges in terms of understanding the network

¹Containerisation is the packaging of software code with just the operating system (OS) libraries and dependencies required to run the code to create a single lightweight executable—a container—that runs consistently on any infrastructure (see www.ibm.com/cloud/learn/containerization)

topologies. These network topologies are deployed in the novel network architectures for data centres, telecommunication providers, infrastructure providers, and other key stakeholders.

This challenge is exacerbated by the support of multi-tenancy capabilities, highly demanded in industry as it has proved to reduce significantly CAPEX and OPEX [11]. Multi-tenancy imposes the usage of overlay networks to perform resource and network isolation for each of the tenant, using the same physical infrastructure. Such isolation requires the creation of new logical networks and virtual machines per each of these tenants. This makes the network topology more complex, and hence harder to perform troubleshooting of networking issues.

The complexity of understanding the network topology is increased significantly when there is also a clear need to perform a separation of business roles associated with the multi-tenant infrastructure. The separation of business roles imposes the definition of the topological boundaries between the ISP physical network and Internet Service Consumer (ISC) virtual tenant networks, which in turn has significant implications in terms of technical and legal responsibility, since they can be used to determine the physical and virtual scopes of the administrative domains.

The complexity of the network topologies is even larger when the infrastructure needs to deal with the mobility of user equipment between different access points. This is associated to 5G networks where user mobility, multi-tenant isolation and virtualisation are key elements of the 5G architecture.

It is clearly a problem for the monitoring of the 5G networks, to deal with complex topologies due to virtualisation, multi-tenancy and other novel concepts. This is primarily due to the fact that all those concepts do not physically exist in real life, and they are just merely virtual representations. Consequently, the troubleshooting of these networks is a clear challenge as well as understanding how to monitor these new resources that are not physical ones.

The understanding of such complexity in network topologies is a critical aspect for the success of the adoption of these technologies in operational environments. In these operational environments, the services must be delivered to thousands of users, where problems can

come from any of the physical and virtual network interfaces. Current software prototypes and architectures in charge of the understanding of network topologies are insufficient to fulfill all the challenges previously mentioned.

Moreover, this complexity makes it very difficult even for network administrators to perform a quick reaction over the different elements of the network. This is critical, for example, when we need to react against a cyber-attack, or quickly need to enforce a policy in the system, etc.

This research work studies these multi-tenant 5G network topologies, formed by both physical and virtual machines and networks where the same physical infrastructure is shared by different VNO (multi-tenancy), and there is user mobility across the access points. The main aim is to provide novel solutions that help network administrators and users, in general, to understand the network and the events that are happening in these novel networks in real time. Moreover, this research work presents the first holographic GUI for network topology visualisation and monitoring that integrates detailed digital representations of the software datapath that exists inside of complex devices in the network. In addition, all the components of the network are provided with real-time metrics about their available resources (e.g., CPU usage, memory usage, etc.), and information gathered with sensors (e.g., IoT sensors). Finally, this tool is able to show events such as a dropped link or if a device is under attack. These events are attached to the specific components in the topology, and it also notifies if the event is important, and in some cases, how it has been self-mitigated.

The creation of this tool brings with it some challenges such as the modeling of the components that compose the network topology, or how to create a topology layout that helps understand the network.

During this study, new ways of exploiting the designed spatial representation of the network topology have also been explored. Therefore, a new spatial metric is proposed, to use the knowledge of the topology to help conduct network management. This metric, based on the minimum paths between the vertices of a graph, has been custom designed for multi-tenant 5G network topologies, such that it has been possible to improve the results obtained using the traditional Dijkstra's algorithm, by six orders of magnitude. This metric

has been implemented in a new tool that is capable of providing real-time results for large-scale network topologies. In addition, this novel spatial metric is proposed for the Virtual Network Function (VNF) placement use case, where it helps select the best host to move or create a VNF.

1.1 Aim And Objectives

1.1.1 Aim

The primary aim of this research work is to provide new holographic network management solutions to allow network administrators to have a real-time spatial representation of their network topologies, and thus to handle the complexity of the multi-tenant 5G network infrastructure. Furthermore, these solutions will enable network administrators to monitor the state and performance of the network, including all the different resources that compose the multi-tenant 5G network infrastructure. These solutions will be flexible enough to be suitable for all the different business roles that are making use of the network infrastructure, for both network monitoring and making informed network management decisions.

1.1.2 Objectives

To achieve this aim, several measurable objectives need to be addressed:

- **Objective 1:** To design, develop and empirically evaluate a novel algorithm able to effectively lay out all the different components discovered in a multi-tenant 5G architecture, in order to allow network administrators to deal with the complexity in the understanding of this type of infrastructures. The algorithm will generate 3D spatial coordinates of all the different components available in the infrastructure to achieve a logically ordered representation.
- **Objective 2:** To design, implement and empirically evaluate a novel visualisation tool to render the topology of a multi-tenant 5G infrastructure using the layout achieved

in Objective 1. The tool will allow real-time rendering for effective understanding of physical and virtual infrastructures, supporting both multi-tenancy and mobile user mobility in 5G networks. It will address as well as support different business roles: infrastructure service provider and infrastructure service consumer.

- **Objective 3:** To design, implement and empirically evaluate a real-time monitoring and analytic tool that is able to gather performance metrics of the components of the infrastructure, and to display alerts gathered from analytical tools. The tool will provide context awareness information over the 3D topology achieved in Objective 2.
- **Objective 4:** To design, implement and empirically evaluate an immersive holographic visualisation tool that is able to integrate the outcomes of Objectives 1, 2 and 3, providing a full immersive experience to allow network administrators to completely understand the network administration problems.
- **Objective 5:** To propose a new algorithm able to calculate novel 5G tailored spatial metrics over the structure of the multi-tenant 5G network topology with the purpose of allowing the taking of optimised decisions, based on the structure of the network.
- **Objective 6:** To design, implement and empirically evaluate a new monitoring probe able to provide the spatial metrics achieved in Objective 5, per each component of the dynamically changing network topology associated to this kind of infrastructure.
- **Objective 7:** To apply the metrics achieved in Objectives 5 and 6 to a concrete use case, with the aim to develop informed network management decisions. The use case is focussed on making optimal decisions about the best location to place the Virtual network function (VNF) into the multi-tenant 5G network.

1.2 Outline

This thesis is organised into two parts. The first part consists of a summary of this research work for the elaboration of the four publications that compose it. After this introductory

chapter, Chapter 2 summarises the seven main innovations achieved in this research work. Chapter 3 provides an overview of the concepts necessary to understand the work carried out. First, the multi-tenant 5G network infrastructure that has been used during this work is presented in detail. Then, a global view of the architecture of the framework is shown, which includes the components that have been used, as well as the new components that have been created in this research work. Subsequently, an introduction to spatial metrics is provided in order to help the reader to better understand how it works. Next, in Chapter 4, a summary of the literature review on the related works is provided. First, existing work related to the visualisation and monitoring of network topologies are reviewed. Second, work related to spatial metrics in networks are studied. Chapter 5 describes the project management followed during this research work, and the order and relationship of the different stages involved. Then, Chapter 6 describes the design and implementation details of the work carried out. In Chapter 7, a summary of the most important results obtained during this thesis are provided. This chapter also analyses both the strengths and shortcomings of the proposed solutions under the Critical Analysis section. Finally, Chapter 8 presents the conclusions and research directions for future work.

The second part consists of the inclusion of the outputs already published on this research work.

First, Journal 1 [1], entitled "*5GTopoNet: Real-Time Topology Discovery and Management on 5G Multi-Tenant Networks*" presents a novel framework application for discovery, monitoring and visualisation of multi-tenant 5G network topologies. This publication provides results of the research carried out to achieve a new way of understanding the network topology. Furthermore, it presents innovations for the detailed discovery of the topology, the generation of a 3D layout, and the rendering of the detailed datapath.

Then, Journal 2 [2] entitled "*Advanced Spatial Network Metrics for Cognitive Management of 5G Networks*" provides the novel spatial metric algorithm for identification of key nodes of the network topology and its implementation in the component Topology Monitoring Agent (TMA). This research presents a cognitive 5G network management framework

and different usage cases where the metric can be applied. It provides empirical results that demonstrate the scalability of the implementation for large-scale multi-tenant 5G networks.

Following this, Conference 1 [3] "*New Immersive Interface for Zero-Touch Management in 5G Networks*" provides a holographic version of the topology GUI presented in Journal 1, which extends the functionality adding new monitoring and analytic features. This publication presents a new way of monitoring for a zero-touch management system where the operator can take advantage of the immersive experience to explore the topology, and visualise monitoring information in the place where it is actually happening.

Finally, Conference 2 [4] "*Topology Awareness for Smart 5G eMBB Network Slicing VNF Placement*" proposes the usage of the novel spatial metric presented in Journal 2 as a novel strategy for VNF placement. This publication presents the advantage of considering the topological information of the network to perform management tasks, such as the placement of a new VNF. Moreover, it presents the eMBB media stadium use case as an example to understand how the spatial metrics work, and provides empirical results that support the usage of these metrics.

Chapter 2

Achievements

This chapter summarises the seven primary innovations achieved in this work. The purpose is to consolidate these achievements and contrast them against the existing state of the art ones.

The first achievement is related to the components that discover the topology. In particular, Resource Inventory Agent (RIA) inventories in detail, both the hardware and different physical, logical and virtual network interfaces. Physical interfaces involve all the existing physical hardware-based network interfaces in the machine. Logical interfaces correspond to those that are part of the software datapath inside the physical machine (PM) or virtual machine (VM), while the virtual interfaces correspond to the interfaces of the containers, and VMs are connected to the PM. There is a concrete example in the connection from the PM to the VM, where information is needed about the name of the network interface assigned inside the VM. Here a common point of information must be created that the RIA inside the VM and the RIA inside the host PM will have available to create the complete datapath. The creation of this connection is a very important innovation, which now makes possible the use of the predictable network interface names provided since systemd v197 version. This level of detail of real-time datapath inventory has never been achieved before, using a single component. State of the art tech, such as Skydive [12], achieves a detailed level of the topology. However, Skydive [12] is unable to show the level of detail of connection types and establish the datapath with non-physical components of the topology, such as the software

switches that play a fundamental role in 5G networks, or the virtualised and containerised components.

The second achievement is related to the problem of business role separation between the Internet Service Provider (ISP) and the Internet Service Consumer (ISC). This is also known as multi-tenancy allowing of different ISCs (or tenants) to share the same physical infrastructure provided by an ISP. The boundaries in terms of privacy and security regarding which information should be exposed to one or the other is a very important topic, since it has not been addressed in the past. In finding that gap, a solution was achieved in terms of the discovery of the topology. To solve this, RIA can report the information strictly necessary to not overpass the boundary, and only inventory the information of the business role. Thus, as an infrastructure provider, it will know about the existence of a VM, but it won't access information about what is happening inside the tenant VM. This is a significant innovation not achieved in the state of the art techs. For instance, Skydive [12] doesn't give information about these boundaries, and it doesn't provide a view from the perspective of the tenant. It only supports a view of the topology from the perspective of a cloud administrator that has access to everything.

The third achievement is the new algorithm to create a meaningful layout of a multi-tenant 5G network. With this algorithm, a way of positioning the different devices and connections of a multi-tenant 5G network topology in the space could be achieved. This algorithm provides an optimisation of the space to scale-up and layout larger topologies. It allows a logical order in the space for the different devices and connections, avoiding collisions between them and helping the user to better visualise when using this layout to render it. This algorithm is implemented in a separate component that provides the layout structure as metrics in real-time. The existing state of the art technology generates the layout of the topology by using existing 2D graph layout algorithms, or by creating the layout manually. However, they have to use filtering techniques to avoid collisions, and let the human understand the layout.

The fourth achievement consists of a new tool to render an understandable representation of multi-tenant 5G networks. Using the topological information gathered from the topology

discovery components, together with the generated 3D layout of the network topology, a new tool able to produce a meaningful visual representation of a multi-tenant 5G network was achieved, that allows humans to understand what is happening in the network and perform optimised network topology monitoring in real-time. The main innovation of this tool is the capability to show the complete datapath, including the software datapath that the human eye was not able to see. The current solutions that provide network visualisation do not achieve this level of detail of the datapath, and neither the organised layout that allows a meaningful visualisation of the topology. Skydive [12] which is one of the most advanced tools, still provides a limited 2D layout and level of detail.

The fifth achievement is the new holographic tool for multi-tenant 5G networks visualisation with aggregated metrics and alerts. This tool is the next step of the previous achievement that extends the implementation to be executed on a holographic headset. Furthermore, this extension achieves the aggregation of metrics and alerts attached to the element of the network topology, where they are happening. All of this together allows for an improved experience to perform network monitoring, where the user can explore the topology and see information in real-time about what is happening in a specific device or network interface. The implementation of this tool for holographic headsets has opened the door to much more advanced capabilities that cannot be achieved with the current state of the art tools. Augmented Reality (AR) is a powerful tool that can enhance and make easier the understanding of autonomous management.

The primary purpose of these visualisation tools is to reduce the complexity, time and effort required for network operators to understand the network, and see what is happening. This complexity can impact different aspects such as network security, troubleshooting or finding topology configurations that miss the potential that could be achieved, if the topology was well configured. Some parameters that quantify the complexity of a network can be the size of the network, and the number of different types of devices that compose the network. Moreover, now, with virtualisation or concepts such as multi-tenancy, the datapath can be difficult to understand. The current state of the art tool does not provide network topology management solutions that reduce the complexity in these terms. The visualisation tools

achieved in this work manage to hide the complexity by using a meaningful layout of the topology, and allowing the network operator to explore the network and analyse the detailed software datapath. This includes not-physical interfaces that add more complexity to the datapath, allows to understand better the network, and speeds up the time required to perform management actions, which directly impacts the performance of the network.

The sixth achievement is the new 5G spatial metric algorithm, tailored for multi-tenant 5G networks. This algorithm is based on the closeness centrality metric used in graphs. This metric can be applied to mobile network topologies to identify key nodes in the network. A tailored version for multi-tenant 5G network topologies has been created, by applying three different optimisations. As a result, a reduction of six orders of magnitude was achieved with respect to the original algorithm, making feasible the use of this algorithm in real-time. The usage of this metric for network management purposes has not been addressed yet, where state of the art focus on other metrics such as end-to-end latency, last-mile latency, latency-under-load, mean latency, end-to-end packet loss or jitter, upstream-downstream throughput-goodput, network availability, etc., as indicated in Bajpai and Schönwälder [13] and Goel et al. [14].

The seventh achievement is the new tool to calculate the spatial metric, achieved previously in real-time. This means the tool will be able to receive the discovered topology in real-time, and calculate this metric for all the required devices of the multi-tenant 5G network. This tool achieves this by implementing the optimisations designed for the tailored 5G closeness centrality. Considering the existing tools that try to use topological information to perform network management, this new one goes one step further by trying to innovate a spatial metric that aggregates the spatial status of the network topology, and identify key nodes in the topology. Furthermore, it has achieved promising scalability results that allow its usage in large-scale multi-tenant 5G networks.

Chapter 3

Overview of System Concepts

This chapter presents an overview of the system concepts to provide the reader with context of the research work that has been carried out. First, the use of the multi-tenant 5G infrastructure is presented. Then, an overview of the framework architecture is introduced, where all the software components necessary to achieve the objectives are depicted. Following that, some concepts about spatial metrics in the context of network topologies are introduced.

3.1 Multi-tenant 5G network infrastructure

Figure 3.1 illustrates an overview of the multi-tenant 5G infrastructure used during this research work. Vertically, the infrastructure consists of two levels, the virtual infrastructure plane on the top where all the virtualised devices in the infrastructure are placed, and the physical infrastructure plane at the bottom, where all the physical devices of the infrastructure are located.

Horizontally, the infrastructure can be divided into five segments. The mobile users segment represents the final devices that are deployed in the enterprise premises and connected to the physical 5G network. Such devices can be both User Equipment (UE) and Internet of Things (IoT), supported by corresponding protocols (Long-Term Evolution for Machines (LTE-M), Narrowband-IoT (NB-IoT), etc.). The vast majority of connected devices belong to this network segment. A Key Performance Indicator (KPI) associated to 5G infrastructures

Fig. 3.1 Managed multi-tenant 5G infrastructure

indicates the ability to deal with up to one million devices per km^2 [15]. It is obvious that it is impossible for a human to digest the simultaneous information coming from such a huge number of devices. However, one of the purposes pursued in this research work is to investigate the usage of the Graphical User Interface (GUI) to increase the number of simultaneous information that can be shown in the topology visualisation.

The IoT and UE devices are connected to the network via the access network, using the radio base stations available in the last mile network segment. Then, the edge segment is composed by different network Points of Presence (PoP) that allow distributed computing infrastructures to bring the computational processing closer to the end user to satisfy ultra-reliable low-latency 5G networks requirement. All these distributed PoPs are connected through the blackhaul network to the components in the Core network segment. While the edge PoPs have limited computational capacity, the core is usually located in a centralised data centre, provided with a powerful infrastructure composed of a considerable number of servers. The core segment is connected to the backbone from where these servers can access to the Internet and other administrative domains.

In a distributed cloud-RAN, two functional elements, Distributed Unit (DU) and Centralized Unit (CU), are deployed. DUs are placed in the last mile segment and connected to a pool of CUs deployed in the edge segment. Moreover, these CUs provide an extended support for 5G IoT technologies such as LTE-M and NB-IoT. Figure 3.1 shows where these CUs are located in the virtual infrastructure plane of the edge segment, where other different virtualised services are collocated in different VMs and containers. The virtual infrastructure plane of the core network segment deploys the architectural elements of the 5G network

with various roles and functional responsibilities, as detailed in [16]. Briefly, the main concerned architectural components are the following: Access and Mobility Function (AMF) for UE-based authentication, authorisation and mobility management, Session Management Function (SMF) for session management, and IP address allocation, Policy Control Function (PCF) for policy control in order to support Quality of Service (QoS), Authentication Server Function (AUSF) storing data for authentication of UE, User Plane Function (UPF) for Internet data plane access, and User Data Management (UDM) that stores subscription data of UE.

Figure 3.2 shows the physical infrastructure deployed in the premises of the Beyond 5G Hub group. This infrastructure has been used to carry out the experiments of this research work. These pictures are shown in order to help the reader understand the scope of this research work and the empirical experiments carried out. The concrete testbed for each experiment is described in Chapter 7.

Fig. 3.2 Multi-tenant 5G infrastructure deployed in the premises of the Beyond 5G Hub group.

3.2 Reference framework architecture

Figure 3.3 depicts an overview of the elements that compose the framework used as a basis to achieve the challenges proposed in this work. Placed at the bottom of the figure are the components that provide information about the elements of the network topology. Notice that the discovery components are coloured in blue to remark that I have actively participated in their development. In the centre of the figure are located the channels through which the topological information is exchanged. Finally, in the upper part of the figure are located the components that have been produced as a result of this work (shown in green colour). All the components are briefly explained below, to provide the reader with a better understanding of the complete framework.

Fig. 3.3 Framework architecture design

At the bottom left corner of Figure 3.3 are depicted the components that provide topology discovery information. This information will be used by Layout Monitoring Agent (LMA), Topology Monitoring Agent (TMA) and both GUIs.

- **5G Monitoring Agent (5GMA)** helps discover information about the UE and their mobility across different cells of the radio access networks. This component needs to be deployed in every tenant network that requires it.

- **Resource Inventory Agent (RIA)** helps discover the topological information for all the physical and virtual devices, ports and connections between ports, and devices allocated in the physical machine. RIA is deployed inside each Physical Machine (PM) of the multi-tenant Fifth-Generation (5G) networks, if the deployment use case requires Internet Service Provider (ISP) topological information, and it is also deployed inside each Virtual Machine (VM) if the deployment use case requires Internet Service Consumer (ISC) topological information.
- **Topology Inventory Manager (TIM)** provides topological information about parts of the network where 5GMA and RIA cannot be deployed, and thus access to such information locally, such as closed hardware appliances (e.g., managed switches and routers) and centralised information stored in the management software (e.g. OpenStack).

To know more about these three components, refer to Section 9.5.

The monitoring and analytic visualisation system integrated in both GUIs requires information about topology alerts and topology sensing. The components that provide the information in real-time about alerts and actions are *Anomaly Based Analytics Module* and *Decision Making Module*.

- **Anomaly Based Analytics Module** provides information about the different alerts that are happening in the network. These alerts are automatically detected by this module but not mitigated, and thus require of human intervention.
- **Decision Making Module** provides information about the automatically mitigated alerts, and also those alerts that require user confirmation to be mitigated.

To read more about these components and some examples of alerts, refer to Section 11.5. On the topology sensing side, the architecture employs three components that provide performance metrics about resources, flows and operating system processes (services).

- The **Resource Monitoring Agent (RMA)** reports metrics about the physical device and where it is installed (e.g., CPU usage, memory size, etc.), the VMs allocated

in such PMs (e.g., memory I/O, disk I/O, memory used, etc.), and both physical and virtual network interfaces, such as bandwidth consumed, bandwidth capacity or bandwidth negotiated.

- The **Process Monitoring Agent (PMA)** reports metrics about each of the services/processes that are running in each PM of the 5G infrastructure. These metrics include process I/O, memory I/O, disk I/O, context switches, sleep time, idle time, and so on.
- The **IoT Sensing** component is the real-time sensing information collected from every IoT device available in the network. This encompasses all the real-world environmental information taken from LTE-M and NB-IoT sensors such as temperature, humidity, pressure, etc.

On the top of the figure, are depicted the architectural components developed in this research work for management purposes.

- **TMA** is a monitoring component that receives information about the discovered topology and generated tailored spatial metrics for multi-tenant 5G networks. These spatial metrics are generated using the network topology updated in real-time. TMA has been optimised to generate very complex metrics that usually take too long to be considered as real-time spatial metrics within reasonable times, that provide updated information about the devices of the topology. These spatial metrics can be used to identify the level of importance of a given node with respect to its location in the network.
- **LMA** is the component that generates the spatial positioning of the topology reported by the different topology agents. LMA receives all the information about topologies being reported, and runs customised algorithms to determine the best spatial allocation of all these components, with the primary intention to provide useful and effective rendering of large-scale information for the network administrators. As a result of the layout algorithms, it publishes metrics indicating the spatial locations, which are later on used by other components to render the devices, ports and connection in the best possible locations for human understanding.

- **PC GUI** is an interface that allows users to visualise multi-tenant 5G network topologies discovered by the topology discovery components (5GMA, RIA and TIM). These topologies are displayed using the layout structure generated in LMA. The user can interact with the different devices that compose the topology, and click on them to visualise the physical and logical network interfaces and the software datapaths inside of the device. Moreover, monitoring metrics are displayed on top of the detailed view of the devices to allow monitoring capabilities. These metrics are received from the monitoring components, previously mentioned. In addition, the user can visualise information about alerts and actions attached to every device and network interface received from the anomaly based analytics module and the decision making module.

Furthermore, this component is prepared to provide business roles separation, allowing two different configurations. In one configuration, the user of this graphical component is the ISP, which implies that it can see every device, port and connection available in the topology. This includes software components such as software switches. In the other configuration, the user is the ISC, and only the topology associated to that particular ISC is shown.

- **Holographic GUI** is an Augmented Reality (AR) interface that integrates the same features as the PC GUI, but allows the user to live an immersive experience with an AR headset, and interact using hand gestures. This allows network operators and users in general to explore the topology and visualise metrics and alerts, and perform network troubleshooting with other tools at the same time. This holographic GUI opens new future options, such as digital-twinning, to perform advanced network management.

The design and implementation details of these components, which are the main result of this thesis, will be described in Chapter 6.

3.3 Spatial metrics

Spatial metrics in the context of multi-tenant 5G networks refer to metrics that give information about the different components of the network, which have been calculated using the knowledge about the spatial structure of the network topology. These metrics exploit the relative locations of devices connected to the network to identify key nodes.

For this purpose, a representation of the topology in the form of a graph is used, and graph theory algorithms are applied. Among them, there are algorithms that provide information about the centrality of each node. Degree centrality measures the number of edges associated with each node. This metric is one of the simplest metrics in terms of complexity due to the structural representation of the graph. Its use may be interesting to detect devices that can be critical when it comes to a failure in their operation. Betweenness centrality is another example of a centrality metric that measures the number of times a node is on the shortest path between each pair of nodes belonging to the graph. This requires the calculation of the shortest path between each pair of nodes available in the graph. It makes more challenging to apply optimisations to the calculation of this metric, in order to reduce the number of shortest paths.

There are other metrics, such as Eigenvector centrality, PageRank centrality, and Closeness centrality. Eigenvector centrality and PageRank centrality are metrics much more complex to calculate. They extend the idea of Degree centrality considering neighbouring nodes. However, they require the inclusion of relative scores for each node that represents different levels of importance. The difficulty here is calculating those scores and evaluating if they are meaningful to each network scenario. Closeness centrality measures the distance from a node to all the nodes that can be reached in the graph; this metric can identify the importance of the nodes in the network, which can be used to determine the effort required for the node to reach the others. The interpretation of this metric is directly applicable in various usage cases such as cache allocation for 5G Ultra-Reliable and Low-Latency Communications (URLLC), computation offloading in Massive Machine Type Communications (mMTC), node over-provisioning, or optimal location of load balancers. Thus, this

applicability and interpretability of the Closeness centrality has been one of the main reasons why it has been chosen as a candidate to start the exploration of spatial metrics.

The applications of these metrics are interesting in the context of multi-tenant 5G networks. However, algorithms that require the calculation of shorter paths between nodes do not scale very well, as graphs grow in size. To solve this, the research proposes a tailored 5G Closeness centrality metric for multi-tenant 5G network topologies.

Chapter 4

Literature Review

This chapter presents an overview of the most relevant related work about the topics that have been investigated in this thesis. First, the state of the art work related to the visualisation and monitoring of 5G network topologies is discussed. Then, the state of the art work is reviewed in relation to the usage of the network topology to provide metrics based on topology awareness, and to perform optimal Virtual Network Function (VNF) placement strategies. The objective of this chapter is to make a summary of the most relevant works that have already been included in the related work sections of the published articles in this thesis, as well as new research works that have emerged after the articles were published.

4.1 5G Network Topology Visualisation and Monitoring

Network topology visualisation refers to the visual support of network topologies to help monitor and manage the network. Therefore, it is normal that this concept does not exist without the concept of network topology monitoring. However, the opposite does not happen, since there are various tools that allow network monitoring and management without having a global or partial view of the network topology.

Behringer [17] provided a classification of network complexity and some parameters that can help identify the complexity of a network. Behringer stated that most networks tend to grow, and as they increase in size, fewer and fewer network operators are able to understand

the whole network, and therefore they focus on smaller parts of the network. This leads to the observation that the complexity of a network is inversely proportional to the number of people who are able to understand the whole network. However, Behringer recognised that for a network to be robust, a certain amount of complexity is necessary. It is therefore better to transfer the complexity to the tools used for network management, and thus reduce the complexity for the network operator. Finally, Behringer noted that the more complex the network, the more likely it is that security rules will fail.

When building the visualisation of the topology, the arrangement of the devices that compose the network is one of the most important parts to take into account. At the end, a network of connected devices can be represented as a graph structure where the devices are nodes and the connections are edges of the graph. Nobre et al. [18] presented a study to help address this problem by taking into account layouts, view operations, layout operations, and data operations.

The following works focus on the study of the arrangement of nodes, and how to visualise network topologies. However, not all of them work on the arrangement of communication networks. Karatzas et al. [19] presented an interactive 3D visualisation tool for heterogeneous biomedical information, presented as multilayered networks in a single view. Gilroy et al. [20] provided a tool for large-scale graph based topologies of general purpose defined in specific formats (CSV, tab, and XML). Broască et al. [21] presented a hybrid solution between 2D and 3D for the generation of graph layouts, trying to solve the existing problems of 3D representation. Koutrouli et al. [22] presented the network analysis profiler, a web tool that provides 2D and 3D network topology of protein-protein interactions to visually compare different graphs simultaneously.

Total network inventory [23] and AixBOMS [24] are traditional systems for network inventory and management. They provide static mapping of the topology that can be updated manually to visualise the topology and allow network management of the physical infrastructure. These systems rely on Open Systems Interconnection (OSI) layer-3 discovery mechanisms, and therefore they do not show any device along the path, but just connectivity between devices.

nuGENTM3D visualisation for IoT networks [25] presents a management system for physical networks. It provides cloud-based and on-premise versions of a tool for visualisation of the complete network in real-time. However, it don't provide discovery of overlay networks, and therefore don't provide network management for multi-tenant networks.

Zhou and Ma [26] proposed an algorithm to discover the physical topology at layer-2 and layer-3 switches. Wang et al. [27] proposed an algorithm based on SNMP, also focussed on layer-2 and layer-3. Both works identify the differences between manufacturers and supporting SNMP, which directly impact the heterogeneity left for future work.

Rojas et al. [28] presented an alternative protocol to Link-Layer Discovery Protocol (LLDP) that calculates the shortest paths while simultaneously discovering the topology. Their protocol provides support for overlay networks too and also present some features that Software-Defined Networking (SDN) platforms should provide to allow efficient topology discovery. NMSaaS [29] also provides discovery of network topologies, using different layer-2 and layer-3 discovery protocols to build dynamic maps based on the connections. Network topology mapper [30] is a software that inventories network topologies using layer-2 and layer-3 discovery protocols as well as NMSaaS, but it also achieves support for switch ports, VLANs and subnets. Toufga et al. [31] presented a topology discovery service for SDN-based hybrid vehicular networks. They proposed a set of directions to follow to overcome the limits of efficient topology discovery on software defined vehicular networks.

Constantinescu et al. [32] proposed VizNet, a dynamic visualisation tool for networks and Internet of Things (IoT). This tool provides a 3D visualisation of the network, and a notification system using Facebook messenger and Telegram to provide alerts about the network. They provide a network topology discovery that uses different layer-3 protocols to discover the physical and wireless networks. However, they do not provide discovery of the software datapath, and neither the discovery of virtual networks. The visualisation tool was implemented using WebGL that works on web browsers. However, the provided topology layout does not follow an organised network structure that can help reduce the complexity of the topology.

Hofstede and Fioreze [33] presented a network monitoring tool prototype using Google Maps API, focussing on the lack of tools providing geographical information about networks. They provide geographical visualisation of the physical network with markers that represent hosts and lines that represent flows. Chen et al. [34] provided a solution for visualisation of large-scale network topologies, providing information about internal configuration of routers and port level QoS metrics. This visualisation tool allows interactive exploration in 2D zooming to the different parts of the topology. However, both of them are focussed on the physical network (without including the Radio Access Network (RAN) segment), and therefore they don't cover topologies of VMs. In addition, they do not exploit the use of 3D to scale-up the rendering to larger network sizes and minimise connection crossings.

There are some state of the art tools of special relevance that provide discovery and monitoring of network topologies in the most heterogeneous way possible. OpenDaylight (ODL) [35] stands out being a modular open platform for software-defined networking (SDN) that allows customising and automating centralised network device control, monitoring and discovery. ODL is aware of the multi-tenant overlay virtual networks for which it provides multi-tenant isolation control in cloud computing stacks, such as OpenStack. Moreover, Skydive [12] and MidoNet [36] are open-source network topology monitoring tools that discover physical and virtual networks in real-time. Both provide support for multi-tenant overlay networks, with both VMs and containers. However, none of these three tools are capable of providing support for the RAN segment. For this reason, they lack support for the discovery of users, as well as the tracking of these through the antennas. Furthermore, they are not capable of maintaining a real-time tracking system on the migration of VMs. They are not capable of establishing an alignment of the information exposed to different business roles. This makes it impossible to show different perspectives for the ISP and each of the ISCs. In addition, the ISC and ISP roles can belong to the same organisation in some cases, making the differentiation of business roles even more complex. The solutions they provide for the topology visualisation do not work well for large scale topologies, since they provide both the physical and the visual layer in 2D.

Zabbix [37] is an enterprise-level software for real-time network monitoring. This software is defined as large-scale monitoring software, being able to collect millions of metrics from tens of thousands of servers, VMs and network devices. However, it is not compatible with multi-tenant architectures, and it does not provide user mobility monitoring as well. Furthermore, the interface for end user monitoring does not provide any option to display a map of the network topology.

Nagios [38] provides a set of components for network monitoring and analysis. Among them, Nagios XI provides application, service, and network monitoring. Nagios XI supports multi-tenant capabilities in addition to providing business role separation in the interface, so that users can access different information, depending on their role. Icinga [39] is an open source multi-module tool that provides infrastructure monitoring. It provides support for cloud monitoring, but it does not define boundaries between tenants and the ISP. Both, Nagios and Icinga provide a user interface. However, they do not provide a real-time topology visualisation. Neither of them support RAN monitoring, so it is not possible to monitor UEs. Their user interfaces are not easy to visualise when the topology grows to a large scale. The representation of the topology in 3D, or improved exploration features could help perform network troubleshooting.

In summary, it is difficult to find research work focused on solutions for monitoring and visualisation of network topologies. Most of the state of the art work is found in solutions that, in the greatest number of cases, require the purchase of proprietary software. In this section, some open source software solutions that are usually used in the field of research are named, such as OpenDayLight [35]. However, none of these solutions provide a network topology visualisation system so that the user can easily understand the topology. They typically provide solutions focussed on troubleshooting of the physical infrastructure or the virtual infrastructure separately and they don not provide a real-time alignment between physical networks, virtual networks and device ports, as well as software-based data paths. They also do not provide an integration of RAN devices with the rest of the infrastructure, so user mobility is not integrated in the monitoring loop. Thus, they are not ready to fulfill the requirements imposed by the multi-tenant 5G networks, where the main aspects are

virtualisation and containerisation. Moreover, none of the solutions provide context aware metrics attached to the devices in the space nor allow an immersive exploration in a graphical environment, which can help to identify problems easily. All these reasons are a clear motivation for this research work.

4.2 Topology Awareness for Spatial Metrics and VNF Placement

The use of metrics based on the centrality of the nodes of a graph is quite commonly applied to social networks nowadays (Okamoto et al. [40]). These metrics are often used to measure the influence of key users who can spread information more efficiently, across a network (Newman [41]). In general, centrality metrics can be used in many scenarios, as long as a graph can be used to represent the data. For example, Lin et al. [42] used centrality metrics to study the form that bitcoin lightning networks are taking. Tizghadam and Leon-Garcia [43] proposed an architecture to help with the design of control algorithms in communication networks, using the Betweenness centrality and Resistance distance metrics. They modeled the network as a weighted graph and discussed the usage of directed and undirected graphs to represent the network.

Leaving aside the possible use cases that exist or could arise in the future, there are different types of centrality metrics, and not all of them are indicated for all use cases. Borgatti [44] matched different centrality measures with specific types of network flows to see which one is more appropriate for each type of flow. It highlights the importance of the assumptions made when generalising the path followed by the flows. In the case of the Closeness centrality [45] and Betweenness centrality [46] metrics, it is assumed that the flows usually use the shortest path.

Centrality measures can be applied in numerous cases, however their calculation continues to be a challenging scalability problem in the state of the art. This is because metrics such as Betweenness or Closeness require the calculation of the shortest paths between nodes, in the graph. Currently, the task of calculating the shortest paths can be achieved in $O(m + n \log n)$,

using Dijkstra's algorithm. However, this poses a great challenge in terms of computational complexity when applied to large-scale networks, as reported by Chen et al. [47].

Dolev et al. [48] presented a Routing betweenness centrality metric for communication networks. They used network flows generated by arbitrary loop-free routing strategies, where routing decisions only depend on the packet target and considers the source-target of the packet.

Some authors have studied centrality metrics in the past to propose possible solutions to overcome the scalability challenge. However, most of them used simulated scenarios with small graphs between 20 and 200 nodes, such as Kchiche and Kamoun [49] who used the centrality index to calculate the best placement of access points for vehicular networks, or Wang et al. [50] who used this index for deploying Road Side Unit (RSU). Zhao et al. [51] studied the optimal location of cloudlets in IoT access points (Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC) nodes) to minimise access delay in large-scale IoT networks. However, their solution can only be tested in scenarios with 1000 IoT devices. Kourtellis et al. [52] proposed optimisations using MapReduce to increase scalability in the Betweenness centrality calculation. His best results showed calculation of the metric for a 100k node graph in 10^5 seconds. However, this graph still cannot represent a 5G network.

Baštuĝ et al. [53, 54] analyzed the topology of the network to perform effectively a proactive caching in 5G small cells networks. However, they do not deal with large-scale topologies, and do not consider optimal centrality indexes to maintain up-to-date metrics in the evolving 5G networks.

Tulu et al. [55] provided spatial metrics to identify key nodes in the network topology to serve as content-centric mobile 5g networks. However, they focus on small networks of around 90 nodes to carry out their experiments.

Network metrics aggregation and composition are still not being broadly adopted in currently available monitoring tools, even less in the inter-domain and complex communications networks. Dourado et al. [56] provided a software implementation that allows metric composition considering intra-domain performance measurements in communications networks. They analyse metrics for quantifying end-to-end minimum-mean delay in spatial composition,

but they do not consider spatial centrality metrics. Indeed, Bajpai and Schönwälder [13] and Goel et al. [14] indicated in their state of the art survey, there is not any implemented model or monitoring tool for computing aggregated spatial metrics for 5G networks, and they focus only on network metrics such as end-to-end latency, last-mile latency, latency-under-load, mean latency, end-to-end packet loss or jitter, upstream-downstream throughput-goodput, network availability, etc.

Similarly, Sheu and Chen's [57] work has led to a routing algorithm for SDN, evaluated at small-scale, that considers Centrality in the weight functions to prevent the bottleneck in the multicast routing, and choose the nodes or links that can balance the loads across the network.

A topic of interest for the use of centrality metrics is the placement of different elements on the network. Li et al. [58] mentioned the possible use of the shortest path in the Betweenness centrality as a potential metric for their CaaS system for 5G networks. These metrics can be of special relevance in the case of optimal VNF placement (Camppanera et al. [59]), which is also a hot topic as it is known to be a NP-hard problem (Pham et al. [60] and Zhang et al. [61]).

There are some research work that make use of metrics about the network in real time. Musumeci et al. [62] proposed an optimised algorithm for Distributed Unit (DU) placement in 5G for Cloud-based Radio Access Networks (C-RAN). They considered different metrics such as traffic metrics, link bandwidth or latency, but they did not consider centrality metrics. Oechsner and Ripke [63] used delay and availability metrics to take optimum decisions for optimal VNF placement. Alahmad and Agarwal [64] used real-time metrics to evaluate both availability and reliability and make optimal VNF placements. Jabbarifar et al. [65] proposed a solution for monitoring functions placement by selecting the optimal nodes and making use of heuristics. Pei et al. [66] made use of the topological information of geo-distributed datacenter to optimise the allocation of VNFs and the service function chain associated to such VNFs, and improve that location by reducing the number of redundant VNF instances by allowing them to take combined workloads. However, there are no research work that

have directly considered the use of spatial metrics nor topological spatial information to solve the problem of VNF placement.

Spatial metrics based on the centrality of the nodes of a graph have been used in diverse cases. However, these metrics have not been studied in-depth to carry out monitoring and management of communication networks. Some works have used information about the topology and the arrangement of the different nodes to carry out network management. However, these works fail to scale and be applied to large network topologies. Other works try to solve the problem of VNF placement and the deployment of other elements throughout the network. However, they either fail to address this problem successfully, or they have trouble achieving scalability. These reasons represent a clear motivation to carry out the study of these centrality metrics applied to the multi-tenant 5G mobile networks, composed by physical and virtual elements.

Chapter 5

Project Management

This chapter details the strategy followed during the development of the PhD. The logical step-by-step order is explained together with a graphical visualisation to allow the appreciation of the work developed from a global point of view. A mapping between outputs and objectives is also provided so that the reader can understand the relationship between them.

5.1 Overall

The execution of this research work follows an iterative model. First of all, the project requirements are defined. After that, the iterative model starts with the base application and continues adding extensions and functionalities on each iteration. At the end of each iteration, the application is validated and tested.

This project is distributed in three lines of work. The first line is focused on the visualisation of network topologies. The second line targets the extension that adds capabilities for network monitoring. The third line is focused on the awareness of these network topologies to generate spatial metrics, to help to carry out network management decisions. All three lines are based on the utilisation of the topological information of the multi-tenant Fifth-Generation (5G) network topologies.

Figure 5.1 provides an overview of the association between the objectives and the outcomes of this research work. Moreover, it shows the distribution of these outcomes in the

Fig. 5.1 Logical order followed

three lines of work previously mentioned. Figure 5.1 also shows all the work distributed in four work packages, and the relationship with the published articles.

5.2 Work package organization

	Step 1	Step 2	Step 3	Step 4	Step 5	Step 6	Step 7	Step 8	Step 9	Step 10	Step 11
WP 1											
WP 2											
WP 3											
WP 4											

Table 5.1 Mapping between Work Packages and steps

Table 5.1 summarises the timeline of the steps involved in the strategy followed to achieve the completion of the *Work Packages*, shown in Figure 5.1. The explanation of each of the steps is provided as follows:

- **Work Package 1**

- **Step 1:** A deep investigation of the state of the art process of multi-tenant 5G network topologies has been carried out, concluding that network topologies have

so many new challenges to explore, specially when the expansion of softwarised and virtualised networks involves enlarging the size of such topologies. The visualisation of a complete multi-tenant 5G network topology is a real challenge. Most of the existing visualisation applications are based on physical network topologies. For this reason, they usually show the network topology in a two-dimensional graph. However, due to the emergence of overlay networks and the increase in number of User Equipment (UE), the visualisation of these new topologies is more understandable by users when making use of a third dimension. This new dimension faces a new challenge, which is the layout algorithm needed to render a tailored three-dimensional graph. Layout Monitoring Agent (LMA) has been designed and implemented in this step to overcome this new challenge.

- **Step 2:** After obtaining a software capable of providing a 3D layout of a network topology, it has been necessary to face the design of a visualisation tool that can provide a novel way to visualise the logical representation of a multi-tenant 5G network topology. This visualisation tool has to show all the physical and virtual devices logically interconnected, to allow the users to understand the topology and identify and explore every part of it. The challenge here is the number of devices, specially virtualised devices and UE. Thus, in this step, a topology Graphical User Interface (GUI) has been designed and implemented to provide a 3D logical visualisation of a multi-tenant 5G network topology.
- **Step 3:** The performance of both LMA and the topology GUI have been empirically evaluated, and the results obtained have been published in *Journal 1* (see Chapter 9) entitled “*5GTopoNet: Real-time topology discovery and management on 5G multi-tenant networks*” [1], which is the first journal published during this research work.

- **Work Package 2**

- **Step 4:** Once the topology GUI has been able to display a complete multi-tenant 5G network topology in real-time, the possibility of showing contextual

monitoring and analytic information located in each of the devices in the topology opens up with a novel approach to perform network troubleshooting. Thus, topology GUI has been extended in this step to receive this information in real-time, and to show it in the relevant context of the device in the topology. VMs and UE as well as all the traditional physical devices are provided now with such contextual information. New 3D views and renderings have been investigated to show a detailed version of every type of device. Furthermore, this view presents a novel approach to visualise the information about the device, such as physical and virtual interfaces, as well as a detailed view of the monitoring and analytic information.

- **Step 5:** Topology GUI is now able to provide a complete view of the topology that includes monitoring and analytic information specific to each device. However, the depth provided by 3D visualisation cannot be exploited enough on a 2D monitor. This leads to the novelty of bringing the application to an Augmented Reality (AR) headset, providing all the previous capabilities in a portable device that can create a realistic 3D digital world to allow an immersive exploration of the topology. Moreover, the limitations of this device are studied in depth to adapt the inputs and the scalability.
- **Step 6:** This novel holographic GUI is validated and empirically evaluated together with the results of the new monitoring and analytic information added. These results are presented in *Conference 1* (see Chapter 11) that corresponds to the first conference paper published, entitled “*New Immersive Interface for Zero-Touch Management in 5G Networks*” [3].

- **Work Package 3**

- **Step 7:** Spatial metrics are a useful tool to extract information with a global view of the entire network topology. This is a field that has not been previously studied in-depth, due to the limitations in their heavy computational requirements to be calculated. The different spatial metrics that can be used in the case of mobile

networks have been studied in this step, and the complexity of their calculations has been studied in-depth. It has been possible to create a tailored spatial metric algorithm for multi-tenant 5G networks. This novel spatial metric algorithm has been improved to achieve a feasible execution time for a large-scale multi-tenant 5G network by reducing significantly the computational complexity, to six orders of magnitude.

- **Step 8:** Topology Monitoring Agent (TMA) component has been designed and developed to implement this novel spatial metric algorithm. It is able to create a graph structure that represents the network topology and keeps it updated in real-time. TMA has been optimised to achieve the calculation of the metric for a large-scale network topology within feasible time.
- **Step 9:** TMA performance has been empirically evaluated, and the results obtained are presented in *Journal 2* (see Chapter 10, which is the second journal published during this research work, entitled “*Advanced spatial network metrics for cognitive management of 5G networks*” [2]).

- **Work Package 4**

- **Step 10:** A novel solution to provide Virtual Network Function (VNF) placement has been investigated in this step, using TMA as the engine to calculate spatial metrics. This solution is focussed on a concrete use case *Enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB) Media Stadium*. It proposes the insertion of bandwidth as weight in the topology graph, combined with available resource information of the candidate’s physical nodes to provide an accurate decision system to place a new VNF in a physical node.
- **Step 11:** This novel VNF placement strategy, and the results of an empirical evaluation of the performance of TMA, adapted to the use case, are presented in *Conference 2* (see Chapter 12, which is the second conference paper published entitled “*Topology Awareness for Smart 5G eMBB Network Slicing VNF Placement*” [4]).

Table 5.2 provides a mapping between the objectives of this research work and the outputs achieved, including the three software components produced. There are some cases where several outputs are associated with the same objective, and vice versa, with several objectives associated to the same output. This is why it was decided to incorporate this mapping, and thus allow a correct understanding for the association between outputs and objectives.

	Output 1	Output 2	Output 3	Output 4	Output 5	Output 6	Output 7
Objective 1							
Objective 2							
Objective 3							
Objective 4							
Objective 5							
Objective 6							
Objective 7							

Table 5.2 Mapping Objectives-Outputs

Additionally, Table 5.3 provides a timeline of the research work carried out. The time frame used for the development of each objective in this research work has been marked in colour. In addition, a final row has been added to include the time dedicated to the writing of this thesis.

PLOT LINE

		Q4 2017	Q1 2018	Q2 2018	Q3 2018	Q4 2018	Q1 2019	Q2 2019	Q3 2019	Q4 2019	Q1 2020	Q2 2020	Q3 2020	Q4 2020	Q1 2021
Objective 1	WP 1														
Objective 2	WP 1														
Objective 3	WP 2														
Objective 4	WP 2														
Objective 5	WP 3														
Objective 6	WP 3														
Objective 7	WP 4														
Write Thesis															

Table 5.3 Objectives Gantt timetable

Chapter 6

Design and Implementation

This chapter provides the design and implementation details about the developed work. First, the components for visualisation and monitoring are detailed, including a sequence diagram where the reader can see how they interact with each other, as well as their implementation details. Second, the components developed for spatial metric calculation and the use case for VNF placement are detailed, together with their implementation details.

6.1 Network topology visualisation and monitoring

To perform network topology visualisation and monitoring, the idea proposed in this research work is not just the creation of another network monitoring application, but the creation of a application that allows contextualised, immersive monitoring over all network components, in a unified way. This section details the process of design and implementation of an application that provides information in real-time about a network topology that is managed autonomously, and allows network administrators to know the status of the network infrastructure from a global perspective. To achieve this, it is necessary to have a complete view of the network topology, and to know the status of the resources of each component of the network, as well as the different events that may occur.

First, the model created to represent the multi-tenant 5G network topology is described in the following subsection. Then, details of the Layout Monitoring Agent (LMA) tool,

necessary to generate the layout of the network topology, are addressed. The design of the multi-tenant 5G network topology visualisation application is also explained in the following subsection. Subsequently, the extension of that application is detailed to support immersive monitoring and analytic features on the devices of the topology. Then, a sequence diagram presents the interactions between the visualisation and monitoring tool, and the rest of the components. Finally, implementation details about the previous components are described.

6.1.1 Topology model design

From a global perspective, the network topology model covers the entire network datapath, including User Equipment (UE), that are connected to antennas. Such antennas are connected to Remote Radio Head (RRH) that are then connected to physical machines in the edge segment of the network. From the edge, there exists a software datapath to access the VM deployed, using software switches such as OVS or linux bridges. The possible path to other machines in the core network segment is also included. In addition, this path can bear with multiple hops between switches through the infrastructure. In conclusion, network topology visualisation seeks to show the most detailed possible datapath.

The first step to achieve the model of the network topology is to determine what the elements that are going to compose such a model are, as well as the level of accuracy associated to the information associated to each of those elements. Figure 6.1 shows an example of several elements available in the model, with the intention to show different elements of the complete datapath. The figure includes a physical switch (that is connected to a PM), a PM (that is connected to a virtual one) and a VM. In addition, the PM is opened to allow the visualisation of the complete software datapath. This software datapath has never been rendered in any of the current state of the art tools, and constitutes a clear innovation and advance with respect to the state of the art techniques. The figure includes two software switches, as well as three modules of the Linux kernel that represent the L3 encapsulation/decapsulation module, L3 forwarding module and NetFilter module. These modules are included to provide a complete conceptual representation of the path that network packets are transversing when it is available inside of the machine. All the spheres in Figure

6.1 represent the physical and logical network interfaces available in such machines. Their different colour is used to determine the different types of interface. At the front part of the PM, it can be seen how the datapath comes from the physical interfaces (yellow), and how it goes to the software switches that are used to provide tenant isolation, control security policies and to allow communications between the VMs belonging to the same tenant. The datapath continues to the logical “*tun/tap*” interface that are used by the hypervisor to connect the PM to the interfaces of the VMs (red colour).

It is worth mentioning that there is another type of interface depicted in the figure (inside the PM) that represents the bridge interface (blue colour). One of the software switches has an IP address assigned; then, that interface is connected to the Linux network stack.

It is important to understand that the owner of the infrastructure should be able to see only the information until the outer part of the VM. Thus, all the elements inside are not of concern for the owner of the infrastructure due to privacy issues with the owner of the VM, until there is an agreement to share such information. If this is the case, another component is installed inside of the VM that is reporting the network topology discovered inside it. To allow flexibility in different scenarios where there are multiple discovery tools reporting information about the same machine, we need to establish clear boundaries to make sure the information is consistent and fusionable, despite the fact they are coming from different instances of software components. For example, the way to achieve the alignment of the topology model of the connection available between the physical and the virtual machine is a significant challenge, and it has been a significant innovation achieved in this research work. That connection requires to know the name of the interface decided by the operating system inside of the VM, and it should match with the name of that same interface, then inventoried in the PM. This has been overcome by making use of, very recently, the capabilities available in the Linux kernels called predictive naming of interfaces (see Section 9.6.3).

All the network components depicted in Figure 6.1 along with others not illustrated (e.g., UE, RRH, routers, etc.), have been studied according to their different behaviors. A model has been created that allows them to be expressed in JSON format. In this way, it is possible

Fig. 6.1 Screenshot of an edge physical machine opened to unveil the complexity of the software data path available inside. It is connected to a physical switch and logically connected to a virtual machine which is hosted in the physical machine.

to represent all the types of *devices* that compose the network, as well as to relate all the *interfaces* that exist with each device, and also establish *connections* between such interfaces.

The Resource Inventory Agent (RIA), 5G Monitoring Agent (5GMA) and Topology Inventory Manager (TIM) are in charge of discovering the network topology and reporting such model. RIA is installed in all the machines of the infrastructure, either physical, virtual, or both, depending on the use case. It is responsible for reporting virtual switches, PMs, VMs, Linux namespaces, RRH and their respective interfaces. 5GMA is in charge of report UE and their dynamic (mobile) connection to a given RRH, while TIM is in charge of reporting physical switches and routers.

Listing 6.1 shows an example of the three types of *resources* that represent a device, a device port (or network interface) and a connection between device ports. Each of them is composed of a series of attributes that represent the resource. In this way, taking some of these attributes, a unique hash (*resourceId*) can be established in the network topology to identify them uniquely.

It is worth to describe some attributes such as *hostDeviceId* attribute of the *device* that allows to indicate if this device is hosted in another device (virtualisation/containerisation), allowing to refer from one device to its parent. For example, in the case of a software switch or a VM, these can refer to the *resourceId* of the physical machine in which they are located. A similar attribute can be found in *device port* called *deviceResourceId*, which refers to the *resourceId* of the device to which it belongs. In the case of a *connection*, *srcResourceId* and *dstResourceId* are used to refer to the *resourceId* of the device ports that this connection inter-connects.

Listing 6.1 Extract of topology data model

```
"Device": {
  "hostname": "EDGE-IAAS-0-COMPUTE-3",
  "hostDeviceId": "0A0300D2",
  "deviceType": "PHYSICAL_HOST",
  "physicalZone": "2",
  "name": "COMPUTE-3",
  "model": "CyberServe-XE5",
  "resourceType": "DEVICE",
  "resourceId": "0E0900C3",
  "reportedTime": 1552506941247,
  "state": "STARTED"
}

"DevicePort": {
  "deviceResourceId": "0E0900C3",
  "iface": "eth0",
  "portType": "PHYSICAL",
  "mac": (hidden),
  "ipv4": "146.191.50.231",
  "ipv4Mask": "255.255.0.0",
  "linkDetected": true,
  "resourceType": "DEVICE_PORT",
  "resourceId": "B9AE3E22",
  "reportedTime": 1552506922142,
```

```
" state " : "UP"
}

" Connection " : {
" srcResourceId " : "B9AE3E22",
" dstResourceId " : "16635ED4",
" srcResourceType " : "DEVICE_PORT",
" dstResourceType " : "DEVICE_PORT",
" srcResourceSubType " : "PHYSICAL",
" dstResourceSubType " : "PHYSICAL",
" connectionType " : "PORT",
" resourceType " : "CONNECTION",
" resourceId " : "855E8BFD",
" reportedTime " : 1552506941353,
" state " : "UP"
}
```

This information about the model allows the reader to better understand the technical approach adopted in all the publications associated to this research work.

6.1.2 Layout Monitoring Agent

Once the model that defines network topologies has been obtained, the next step towards the achievement of real-time topology visualisation is to address the problem of performing a comprehensive layout. This layout has to contain all the components available in the topology to be really comprehensive for the final user. Figure 6.2 and Figure 6.3 allow the reader to understand the importance of providing an efficient layout of large amounts of information to allow humans to digest it efficiently. Figure 6.2 represents a layout with significant inefficiency of expressing information, where there is an ordered chaos hampering any attempt toward understanding, whereas 6.3 represents a more efficient layout where the reader can see a set of nodes spatially grouped, providing meaning for the viewer.

The achievement of an efficient layout algorithm that works quickly for large-scale networks is of paramount importance to enable efficient exploration and troubleshooting.

Fig. 6.2 Large-scale multi-tenant 5G network topology visualization from traditional 2D view

Such algorithm must distribute the elements of the topology along the space, so that each part of the network can be clearly distinguished as well as differentiate physical elements from virtual elements. Moreover, virtual elements can be owned by a different tenant or Internet Service Consumer (ISC), and the layout should allow the filter of information differentiated for each other.

Current multi-tenant 5G network topology is of a snowflake shape, where devices are inter-connected with each other forming the star of the snowflake and the leafs are UE. A network topology can be seen as a graph where the devices are the nodes and the connections are the edges. Thus, what is needed is a graph layout algorithm that works efficiently for large-scale graphs in real-time. Force-based graph layout algorithms [67] have been found to work well with star-shaped graphs. These algorithms are based on the application of a system of forces based on those applied in physics systems, where attractive forces between adjacent

Fig. 6.3 Large-scale multi-tenant 5G network topology visualization from Topology GUI

vertices and repulsive forces between all pairs of vertices are combined. The nodes finally achieve a stable position that makes them form a layout where they can be correctly visualised, by applying the movements to which these forces give rise, minimising intersections between edges. Current implementations of this type of force-based layout algorithms, that work with large-scale graphs, only exist for two-dimensional graphs, and thus they are significantly limiting of the usage of the third dimension to allow easier understanding; for example, laying out VMs on a different value of the third dimension. The main reason is that the addition of the third dimension may incur a significant overhead in terms of computational complexity.

Figure 6.4 shows an example where a layout is achieved for a graph that represents a network topology. In this network topology, physical devices and virtual devices belonging to two different tenants are differentiated. However, this topology is simple, and thanks to the colours applied to each tenant, it is easy to see the distinction by types and tenants. However, the purpose is to achieve a 3D display where space can be better utilised.

Figure 6.5 shows what a 3D version of the same network topology would be. Now, the number of nodes could be increased, however that would make it difficult to establish a clear

difference between the types of nodes, because their positions are only determined taking into account their connections. And thus, there is not any intrinsic meaning associated to the third dimension.

The innovative proposal to differentiate the types of devices in space is to create a horizontal 2D layer for physical devices, and another one for virtual ones. In such a way, a certain order is achieved, where the nodes can be differentiated and, it simultaneously enables to see the relationship and connections between them.

Figure 6.6 shows the proposed 3D version, where two horizontal layers are applied. The 2D version of the force-based algorithm can still be used to control the computational complexity, and thus ensure that the virtual devices connected to a physical device remain close to it. This is the system used to establish the positions of each device in the network topology in real-time.

Fig. 6.4 One layer 2D network topology graph layout concept

In order not to overload the application for the visualisation and monitoring of topologies, the layout algorithm has been implemented and executed to an external application. This application is LMA. LMA receives the topology in real-time, discovered for the different probes, and builds a representation of the network topology in the form of a graph. The application updates the layout when there are changes in the topology, and sends the 3D coordinates for each device in the form of metrics associated to the unique ID of each device.

Fig. 6.5 One layer 3D network topology graph layout concept

Fig. 6.6 Two layers 3D network topology graph layout concept

These metrics, in addition to visually representing the topology, can also be used to extract information about the relative positions between devices.

The specific algorithms that have been proven to work best with such large-scale networks have been Force Atlas [68] and Yifan Hu [69] algorithms. First of all, it is necessary to highlight certain characteristics of these algorithms. The first one is that these algorithms are non-deterministic iterative algorithms, and they minimise the tensions between the forces to achieve stability in each iteration. Second, when a new node is included in the graph, it is assigned a random position and this means that when the positions of all the nodes are generated for the first time, the algorithm may take time to converge. Thus, these algorithms can take long to produce a result if a network topology is very large and the positions are

required to be calculated for the first time for all the nodes of the network, i.e., for example, during the cold boot strapping of a system. Despite all this, these algorithms are still the best option for large-scale graphs.

Algorithm 1 shows the pseudocode of the layout algorithm. The algorithm is composed of two parts: the first part (see lines 2 to 20) corresponds to the base structure of a force base graph layout algorithm. The second part (see lines 21 to 23) is the extension that gives support for the 3D layout. The first part can be applied to both Yifan Hu and Force Atlas algorithms. The difference between them is the processes they use to calculate the forces, energy and step.

The algorithm is an iterative algorithm that stops when it has reached a `CONVERGENCE_LIMIT` (see line 17). This limit is reached when the difference between the previous positions and the new calculated positions is below that threshold. The algorithm recalculates the attraction and repulsion forces for every node in each iteration of the loop (see line 5). The attraction force is calculated from the current node to every connected node (see line 11). The repulsion force is calculated from the current node to every other node. Both forces are aggregated, and they are used to recalculate the position of the node using the step factor (see line 13). The step factor is a weight that makes the node to move faster, depending on the previous status. This is called a cooling system that makes the nodes to move slower when the algorithm is converging. After that, the *Energy* is recalculated (see line 14). This *Energy* varies in function of the calculated force. The *Energy* of the graph is used to recalculate the step weight, comparing it with the previous *Energy* (see line 16). Once the force based algorithm has converged, the height of every node is calculated (see lines 21 to 23), depending on the device type.

Validation tests using different topology scenarios have determined that the Yifan Hu algorithm provides a result where space is better used and the network topology is clearer. However, Force Atlas converges much faster and works better with larger graphs. Since both are force-based algorithms and produce similar solutions, it was decided to use Force Atlas along the first iterations, and then continue with Yifan Hu once the first positions are

```

1 Function LayoutAlgorithm(G,x):
2   converged  $\leftarrow$  FALSE;
3   step  $\leftarrow$  INITIAL_STEP_LENGTH;
4   Energy  $\leftarrow$  Infinity;
5   while converged == FALSE do
6      $x^0$   $\leftarrow$  x;
7     Energy0  $\leftarrow$  Energy;
8     Energy  $\leftarrow$  0;
9     for  $i \in V$  do
10      f  $\leftarrow$  0;
11      f  $\leftarrow$  f + AttractionForce_To_Neighbours(i, G);
12      f  $\leftarrow$  f + RepulsionForce_To_EachOtherNode(i, G);
13       $x_i$   $\leftarrow$  ApplyStep( $x_i$ , step, f);
14      Energy  $\leftarrow$  Update_Energy(Energy, f);
15    end
16    step  $\leftarrow$  Update_StepLength(step, Energy, Energy0);
17    if  $|x - x^0| < CONVERGENCE\_LIMIT$  then
18      | converged  $\leftarrow$  TRUE;
19    end
20  end
21  for  $i \in V$  do
22    |  $x_i$   $\leftarrow$  SetHeight( $x_i$ , GetDevice(i));
23  end
24  return x;

```

Algorithm 1: Layout algorithm

calculated to allow better convergences. This combination allows Yifan Hu to take less time to converge as the nodes are closer to the position they will reach when converged.

6.1.3 Topology GUI and Holographic GUI

The next step is the design and implementation of the Graphical User Interface (GUI). This application has some requirements. First, it should be able to connect to the communication middleware to receive information. Second, it should be able to receive a large amount of information in real-time. This information will contain the definition of the topology in real-time including all the changes that may occur, including the movement of UE, migration of VMs or switching off and on of PMs, among others. Third, it should be able to receive the metrics built by LMA that contain the information, with the position of each device to generate the topology layout. In addition, performance monitoring metrics must also be able to receive information such as about the resources of a machine, or even about the measurements taken by any Internet of Things (IoT) sensor in the infrastructure.

Figure 6.7 provides an overview of the design of both PC GUI and holographic GUI. Both applications follow the same design, however there are some changes in the implementation due to the usage of different input systems, as well as specific libraries such as those that connect to the communication middleware.

The process followed by the application to render a topology is as follows. First, the application receives the information about the discovered topology through the communication middleware, in the *TopologyHandler* thread. It is challenging to receive and manage such a huge amount of information continuously, therefore *TopologyHandler* is the thread to solve this problem with a non-blocking behaviour. The main function of this thread is to en-queue the received elements so that *TopologyManager* can un-queue them on demand. *TopologyManager* is another thread whose function is to take each of these elements that are coming in JSON format and deserialise them into an object of the application's data structure. At the same time, there is the *MetricsHandler* thread that receives metrics about the components of the topology. Among these metrics, it contains those produced by LMA about the spatial positions to draw the devices in the rendered topology. These metrics are also en-queued so

that they are ready to be consumed on demand. *RenderingController* is the thread in charge of dealing with the Unity3D engine to perform the rendering of the network topology for its final users. This happens when *RenderingController* has received the position metrics associated with each device, which are en-queued asynchronously. *RenderingController* is also in charge of managing the input of the GUI through the *InputManager*, so that if a device is clicked in the topology view, the detailed view of it will be shown. Unity3D works in such a way that items can only be rendered from its main thread, thus *RenderingController* runs in such a thread.

Fig. 6.7 Topology GUI and Holographic GUI design

Figure 6.8 shows a complete example of a topology rendered by topology GUI. This topology follows the layout defined in Section 6.1.2, where it can be differentiated an upper layer where the VMs of TENANT-A and TENANT-B are located, and a lower layer where the physical devices composing the topology are placed. Among them, there are PMs, physical switches, Distributed Unit (DU) and UE. For more details about the elements that make up this infrastructure, see Section 9.7.2.

The elements that compose this sample topology do not provide so many details. This is because when viewing a large-scale topology, first, these details cannot be distinguished, and second, it is too expensive to render so many details in one view with Unity3D. This would make the frame rate go down, so that user will experience jumps between frames.

Fig. 6.8 Screenshot of a 5G Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC) Infrastructure. This figure is included in Output [1], part of this thesis as Figure 9.5

This is a current challenge that depends on hardware and affects more the holographic GUI, due to the reduced capabilities of the Augmented Reality (AR) headset. Thus, to solve this problem and visualise the details of each device as mentioned above, the purposed solution consists on providing a reduced view of each device, and when a user clicks on an element of the topology, the application shows a detailed view with the information about its internal datapath. This datapath has been explained in Section 6.1.1.

Fig. 6.9 Screenshot of an Edge physical machine opened to unveil the complexity of the software data path available inside. This figure is included in Output [1], part of this thesis as Figure 9.6

The result of the detailed visualisation of a physical machine is shown in Figure 6.9. In this example, the selected device is a physical machine called *EDGE-IAAS-0-COMPUTE* located at the edge network. Inside, two software switches and some network interfaces can be visualised.

It should be noted that the GUI has different modes to filter the information to display, according to the different business roles using the application. These business roles can be Internet Service Provider (ISP) or ISC. ISP has access to a global overview of the infrastructure but with the privacy aspect of the ISC components, while ISC is not able to visualise the global infrastructure and only able to render its own components. This information received by each of the business roles depends directly on the topology discovery tools that are deployed in the devices, to which the business roles have access. The tools will then report the information to a communication middleware. Thus, they will only receive the topological information available to that particular business role.

Both figures 6.8 and 6.9 are screenshots that have been taken from the PC GUI. More screenshots about both GUIs can be found in Output [1] for PC GUI and [3] for holographic GUI.

6.1.4 Monitoring and analytic

The PC GUI and Holographic GUI has been extended with more visualisation capabilities, adding functions that allow to visualise monitoring data in real time. Note how the applications are already designed to receive metrics. Thus, it is a natural extension to allow the possibility of visualising metrics about the devices and their interfaces. This is achieved by clicking on the device. Once its detailed visualisation is on screen, you can see also the metrics available for such machine. In the same way, you can click on any interface of the device and show the metrics available for such interfaces (see section 11.5 for more details and examples).

Listing 6.2 shows how these metrics are defined and how their values are received. `MetricDefinition` contains the definition of a metric. This definition is used to know for the type of resource the metric is defined for, e.g., `Device`, `DevicePort`. In addition, it

contains specifications about the metric, as well as the name, the type of metric, the metric unit (e.g., a percentage), the type of the data, if the metric will be received periodically or only occasionally, how often it will be received, etc. Listing 6.2 shows an example of MetricSample. A MetricSample represents the value of the metric associated to a device or interface. The MetricSample is link to the definition of the metric; this example shows a CPU usage performance metric, as defined by the MetricDefinition.

Listing 6.2 Extract of metrics data model

```
"MetricDefinition": {
  "definitionMonitoredResourceType": "DEVICE",
  "metricDefinitionName": "CPU Usage",
  "metricType": "PERFORMANCE" or "SPATIAL"
  "metricUnit": "PERCENTAGE",
  "metricUnitType": "FLOAT",
  "reportingType": "PERIODIC",
  "samplingPeriod": "5",
  "resourceType": "METRIC_DEFINITION",
  "resourceId": "21FA2AC3",
  "reportedTime": 1552506945321,
}

// Performance MetricSample
"MetricSample": {
  "monitoredResourceType": "DEVICE",
  "monitoredResourceId": "0E0900C3",
  "metricDefinitionResourceId": "21FA2AC3",
  "metricValue": "35.2",
  "startSamplingTime": 1552506941247,
  "resourceType": "METRIC_SAMPLE",
  "resourceId": "1FA3324D",
  "reportedTime": 1552506945321,
}
```

The application has also been extended to receive alerts about events that are happening on any of the devices or interfaces. These alerts are accompanied by actions that have been carried out to resolve these alerts. An icon will be displayed on screen indicating the type of alert that has been received in three different colours (red, yellow and green). If alerts of different types have been received for the same device, the colour of the most critical will be displayed. The user can click on these icons to see a detailed view of the device together with the alerts received (for more details on this, see section 11.5).

Listing 6.3 shows an example of an alert, and an action that has been taken to resolve such alert. The alert contains the name that defines it, the type of alert, a brief description, information about the device or interface to which it refers, a timestamp of when it happened and extra information to identify the alert. In the case of the action, it includes the name of the action, a brief description, a reference to the alert (*actionReasonId*) for which this action has been carried out, information about the device or the interface in which it has been carried out, and information to identify the action.

Listing 6.3 Extract of alert-action data model

```
"Alert": {
  "alertName": "Bottleneck",
  "alertType": "1",
  "alertDescription": "Bottleneck in \hostname - QoS Agreement Violated",
  "affectedResourceType": "DEVICE",
  "affectedResourceId": "0E0900C3",
  "alertTime": 1552507520012,
  "resourceType": "ALERT",
  "resourceId": "11A2C2D4",
  "reportedTime": 1552507525232,
}

>Action": {
  "actionName": "VNF deployed",
  "actionDescription": "New VNF deployed for service 'CDN-base'",
```

```

"actionReasonId" : "11A2C2D4" ,
"affectedResourceType" : "DEVICE" ,
"affectedResourceId" : "0E0900C3" ,
"actionTime" : 1552507598571 ,
"resourceType" : "ACTION" ,
"resourceId" : "23EA12C3" ,
"reportedTime" : 1552507611312 ,
}

```

Figure 6.10 shows the additional changes required to provide support for alerts and actions in the topology GUI. The alerts handler receives all the alerts reported from the *Anomaly Based Analytics Module*, the topology GUI en-queues them so that the rendering controller can update the visualisation in the topology view, as well as the details of the alert when it is selected (see Figure 6.11). The actions handler does the same with the information received from the *Decision Making Module*. The rendering controller reads the en-queued actions and manages the timeout for those alerts, solved by any received action. This timeout will expire alerts and actions after a fixed period of time, so that they will be removed from the interface. The support for the monitoring metrics is provided by the metrics handler, already presented in the previous design to receive the metrics reported by the LMA.

Fig. 6.10 Topology GUI and Holographic GUI design with extension for Alerts and Actions

Figure 6.11 shows the result of the visualisation of the monitoring metrics (see 6.11a) and the alerts/actions metrics (see 6.11b). These are screenshots have been taken in the holographic GUI deployed in HoloLens 2nd Gen. Figure 6.11a shows the percentage of used

CPU in EDGE-IAAS-0-COMPUTE-3. Figure 6.11b shows two alerts received for the same compute server. The alert on top has been solved by taking an action reported by the *Decision Making Module*. The alert at the bottom has not been solved yet and the red colour means that it should be fixed manually (see Section 11.5 for more information about alert types).

Fig. 6.11 Holographic GUI showing monitoring metrics and alerts/actions metrics. This figure is included in Output [3], part of this thesis as Figures 11.4 and 11.5

In summary, the usage of this feature including alerts, actions and monitoring metrics allows the network operator to detect and locate faster where an event is happening. In addition to the information they provide, the GUI presents a summarised way of visualising the alerts using the different colours, and allowing the navigation with hand gestures in the case of the holographic GUI.

6.1.5 Sequence diagram

Figure 6.12 shows the sequence diagram of the topology framework composed by three different processes. The first process represents the rendering of the topology (see 1 in Figure 6.12). The second process represents the rendering of alerts and actions (see 2). Finally, the third process represents the rendering of the metrics, once a specific metric of a device has been selected (see 3).

Fig. 6.12 Topology framework sequence diagram

The components that participate in the topology rendering process (see 1) are the periodic topology discovery tools, the LMA tool that generates the layout structure, and the GUI that allows to visualise the topology. The topology discovery tools (5GMA, RIA and TIM) are the tools that periodically send information about the devices, interfaces and connections that are discovered from the topology network. This information is sent to the topology exchange, where LMA and the GUI listen (see 4). As LMA receives information from the topology, it

begins to generate the layout structure. When LMA generates a layout structure, it sends it to the metrics exchange (see 5). The GUI is listening from this exchange as well, so that when the GUI receives a metric containing the position of a device, the application renders such a device in the topology layout (see 6). A connection will be rendered only if both devices have already been rendered.

For the alert/action rendering process (see 2), the components that are involved are the alert tools (Anomaly Based Analytics Module and Decision Making Module) that send information about alerts and actions and the GUI. When an alert is raised by the *Anomaly Based Analytics Module*, it is reported to the alerts exchange (see 7). The GUI is listening from this exchange, so that when an alert is received, it is persisted in the GUI and rendered on top of the device it belongs to (see 8). Similarly, when the *Decision Making Module* detects that an action has been taken, this action is reported to the actions exchange (see 9). The GUI which is also subscribed to this exchange; when it receives an action, it is persisted and the rendering is updated (see 10).

The GUI has defined timeouts for every type of both alerts and actions, so that when that timeout has passed these alerts/actions will disappear.

Finally, the components involved in the Metric Rendering process (see 3) are the sensing tools and the GUI. In this case, every time an instance of a sensing tool is started, it sends the MetricDefinition of the metrics that it will report to the MetricDefinition exchange (see 11). Thus, the GUI that is subscribed to this messaging exchange persists every MetricDefinition. These sensing tools then start reporting metrics samples periodically or eventually, depending on the type of sensing tool. When a user clicks on a metric for a specific device or interface (see 12), the GUI subscribes to the metrics exchange to start receiving metrics (see 13). The GUI will filter these metrics to only show those that correspond to the MetricDefinition, and the selected device or interface. More information about the metric rendering process is detailed in Output 3 [3] (see Section 11.5).

This is a fully functional innovative component that achieves a 3D representation of the 5G multi-tenant topology in real-time, and allows the immersive representation as holographic headsets.

6.1.6 Implementation details

Implementation details about the software components produced during this work are provided in this section. The communication middleware has been implemented using RabbitMQ [70] which supports the protocol Advanced Message Queuing Protocol (AMQP) 0-9-1 [71]. This protocol allows a multiple queue system that support asynchronous communications between different components. Moreover, it implements the usage of *topic* exchanges that consist on the separation of messages, using routing keys. This feature can be used as a filter to route messages, and thus receive a lower amount of unnecessary messages. For example, the resources discovered in the topology (Device, DevicePort and Connection) are sent to the same exchange but making use of different routing keys.

LMA is implemented in Java 8 so that it can be executed in all operative systems. Its database and layout generation is based on the Gephi Toolkit [72]. All the layout algorithms used for the holographic representation have been adapted to provide a 3D graph layout. Both relevant layout algorithms, *ForceAtlas2* [68] and *Yifan Hu* [69], have been adjusted to provide a 3D layout, modifying the 2D implementation provided by Gephi Toolkit.

Both GUI implementations have been carried out using Unity3D [73] game engine with C# as backend scripting language. This game engine is freeware and allows the development of applications with content in 3D. Unity3D has compilers for different platforms which makes it possible to migrate a project from one platform to another. In addition, Unity3D is the main game engine to develop for Microsoft HoloLens, to allow the development of the application for visualisation and monitoring of network topologies in AR. The mixed reality toolkit [74], a framework developed by Microsoft, has been used for the adaptation of the application for HoloLens. This framework provides a set of components and features used to accelerate cross-platform mixed reality app development in Unity3D. Moreover, due to the 32 bit architecture of Microsoft HoloLens 1, all libraries have to be built for this architecture. It has presented significant implementation challenges which may be obvious but they are not. For example, RabbitMQ is now available for support on Universal Windows Platform on 32-bits. As a result, a simple library that apparently should be available nowadays is not there;

therefore, there is a need to develop a wrap of the C library compiled for 32 bit, to enable support for Universal Windows Platform - the standard execution platform of HoloLens.

Although both GUIs share the same design, the choice of creating a holographic GUI brings certain restrictions with regards to computational power. There are some other headsets such as virtual reality and mixed reality headsets that make use of more powerful computers to externalise the computational part. However, these headsets need to be attached physically to the computer. Microsoft HoloLens has been used because they are a completely autonomous headset, and currently the only one providing a good performance for holograms on AR. AR brings more functionalities than mixed reality, and even more than virtual reality. Microsoft HoloLens also allow interaction with hand gestures which makes the navigation through the topology more intuitive.

6.2 Spatial metrics

In the previous section, the design and implementation process of the different innovations that make up a tool for visualisation and monitoring of multi-tenant 5G network topologies has been explained. This section advances the study of these network topologies, and thus exploits the potential of a tool capable of extracting information from a spatial perspective of the topology. First, the design of the novel spatial metric algorithm is presented for multi-tenant 5G network topologies. Then the design of the Topology Monitoring Agent (TMA) tool that makes use of this algorithm is explained. After that, the use of this tool is expanded for a specific use case. Finally, the most relevant implementation details are detailed.

6.2.1 Spatial metric algorithm

Closeness centrality metric provides a measure of the importance of a node in a graph, depending on the distances to the rest of the nodes. The challenge to overcome in terms of the implementation of this metric is its application to large-scale graphs. This is a challenge because this metric calculates the shortest path between each pair of vertices available in the

graph. The existing algorithm out there to calculate the shortest paths is Dijkstra's algorithm that exposes a $O(m + n \log n)$ complexity. This is a challenge since the complexity is really high, and it directly depends on the number of nodes and edges of the graph.

To solve this problem, the proposed solution consists of applying different tailored optimisations for multi-tenant 5G networks. These optimisations take into account the spatial shape of the network topology, the elements for which it is really necessary to calculate this metric, and how the network changes over time, since it will be necessary to recalculate the metric each time the network topology changes.

The first optimisation consists of making a selection of the nodes for which the metric is to be calculated, i.e., filtering. This is because depending on the use that will give to the metric, it will not always be necessary to calculate it for all the nodes of the network. For example, if you want to identify servers where to place a new virtual machine, the metric will only be necessary for the set of servers capable of allocating virtual machines. This reduces the number of shortest paths to calculate, since now the shortest path between, for example, two UEs, will not be necessary.

The second optimisation is node prune. It exploits the number of UEs present in the network as well as their position in the topology. The number of UEs in the network add up to more than 90 percent of the elements that make up the network. UEs are leaf nodes, if we view the graph as a tree. Therefore, it can be assumed that the shortest distance from any server will be the same to all UEs that are connected to the same ac DU. In this way, once the shortest path to one of these UEs has been calculated, the distance to the rest of the UEs of the same ac DU can be calculated with a simple calculation. For this, it is necessary to have structures in memory where the UEs for each ac DU as well as their weights are kept updated.

The third and last optimisation, 5GCC retrieval, is focused on the calculation of the metrics when changes occur in the network topology. Most of the changes in a network topology arise from the mobility of users, through different access points. Therefore, the optimisation consists of taking advantage of the caching of the shortest paths to the UEs. By

doing so, you can use the previous value of the metric and modify only the part of the UEs when there have only been changes in the topology produced by UEs.

Fig. 6.13 5G Closeness Centrality algorithm design

Figure 6.13 shows a flowchart showing the different functions that take part in the calculation of the 5G Closeness Centrality (5GCC) metric as well as their interactions. The functions for adding and removing nodes and edges are shown at the top of the figure. These functions are important as they help optimisations take effect. When a node (device) is added to the graph, if it is not a UE, this node is added to a structure, where the topology is stored. If it is a UE, this addition is omitted as it will be added when the connection between such UE and its respective DU arrives. When an edge (i.e., a network connection) is added, if such connection contains a UE then the cache structure stores the relationships with the DUs, and the weights of those connections are maintained are updated. If it does not contain a UE then this connection is directly added to the graph where the rest of the topology is stored.

The calculation of the metric 5GCC begins at the left part of the figure. The first step is to check if the topology has received changes only on UEs, with respect to the previous time the metric was calculated. If it has received changes not only from UEs, then a selection is made of candidate nodes (ps) for which the metric is to be calculated. For each of these nodes, the sum of the minimum distances to all other nodes in the graph is calculated. It is necessary to differentiate if the destination node is a DU or not. If it is a DU, then the function named *5G Distance* is used. *5G Distance* is depicted in the right part of the figure. This function calculates the weighted path to the DU and uses the information about the UEs connected to this DU (node prune optimisation). With such information, it can be assumed that the shortest path to every UE connected to the DU is one step more. The weights stored in the “UEs weight in DU” are used to calculate the weighted path to those UEs. Thus, *5G Distance* function returns the distance from ps to the DU, and also to each of the UEs connected to it. With this function, the node prune optimisation is achieved. The shortest path to the DU is calculated using the Dijkstra algorithm. If the destination node is not a DU, the shortest path is also achieved using Dijkstra’s algorithm, but no cache is used in such process.

Once the shortest paths are achieved, the weight of each connection is added. The result of the metric is the inverse of this calculation. This result is stored in a cache, in order to carry out the 5GCC retrieval optimisation, in case there are only topology changes that only

concern the UEs. More level of detail for the spatial metric algorithm is available in Section 10.5.

This is a fully functional innovative component achieving a practically implementable Closeness centrality metric, tailored for multi-tenant 5G network topologies, regardless of the application domain.

6.2.2 Topology Monitoring Agent

TMA is the component that implements the spatial metric 5GCC previous described. This component receives the information about the topology and calculates the metric for each selected node in real time.

Fig. 6.14 Topology Monitoring Agent design

Figure 6.14 shows the layout of the application. TopologyHandler is a thread in charge of receiving the information about the topology and puts it into a queue. TopologyManager is the thread in charge of taking the information about the topology and persisting it in memory, taking into account the functions to add and remove devices and connections seen in Section 6.2.1. The SpatialMetric generator is the thread in charge of calculating the metrics, therefore it is where the 5GCC is implemented. This thread will recalculate the metrics each time the TopologyManager reports topology changes. Finally, MetricSender is the thread in charge of

reporting the metrics every time there are changes in their values. More level of detail about TMA framework is available in Section 10.4.2.

This is a fully functional innovative component achieving a software element in charge of providing the calculation of such spatial metrics for every component of the network. Practically, this component could be named a spatial metric probe or something similar.

6.2.3 VNF placement Use Case

An example of the usage of the 5GCC metric is presented as a way to implement an efficient strategy for Virtual Network Function (VNF) placement. This consists of choosing the best location to deploy a new VNF, taking into account the state of the network and where the best use of resources can be made while providing a good quality of service. This strategy proposes the usage of bandwidth of the connections as weights of the graph to calculate the metric. With this information, it is possible to find the candidate node closest to where most of the UEs are located, taking into account the bandwidths of the different paths, thus limiting the number of hops as a consequence.

Fig. 6.15 VNF Placement strategy

Figure 6.15 shows a diagram with the different steps for the use case. VNF Scheduler is the one who receives the request to choose a node to deploy a new VNF. This component has real-time information about the resources available on each candidate device. At the same time, it also receives real-time 5GCC metrics for each candidate device. When a request arrives, it filters the candidate devices, taking into account the available resources and the

type of VNF to be deployed. The selected devices are ordered by the metric value, and the one with the best value is returned. More details about the proposed VNF Placement strategy are available in Section 12.6.

6.2.4 Implementation details

TMA is implemented in Java 8 to make it easier to deploy in different operative systems. The graph database is an in-memory database that uses the Apache Tinkerpop framework [75]. This framework implements the usage of Gremlin traversal language which allows to navigate the graph. The calculation of the 5GCC metric has been implemented using Gremlin, which implements Dijkstra's algorithm to obtain the shortest paths. TMA is integrated with RabbitMQ to receive the messages about the topology discovery, and to send the calculated metrics. More implementation details are described in Section 10.7.

Chapter 7

Results

The empirical results obtained for each of the components previously described are outlined in this section. The main purpose of the section is to show a series of global results in order to express the different limits regarding the scalability of each component. In each of the papers published, more specific results for each component are shown, together with the corresponding validations that have been carried out in the data centre available on the premises of the Beyond 5G Hub group. Thus, the purpose of this chapter is to show the scalability results of the different components for a set of similar scenarios, and to compare them in a transversal way to allow the reader to gather the inter-relationship which can not be shown in the published papers. This allows a global view of the results published in the different outputs. To establish the limits of each component, this chapter provides a series of graphs measuring the execution time for the largest topologies that have been used for each component.

Layout Monitoring Agent (LMA) and PC-GUI have been deployed on a management computer Dell T5810, with Intel Xeon CPU E5-2630 v4 2.20GHz, 32GB RAM, 512GB SDD, NVIDIA Quadro M4000 and Windows 10. The holographic GUI has been deployed in HoloLens 1st Gen and HoloLens 2nd Gen. TMA has been deployed on a Cyberserve XE5-308S v4 computer, with Dual E5-2660 v4 Intel Xeon, 14 Cores, 2.00GHz, 35M Cache, 105Watts with hyperthreading activated, 128GiB DIMM DDR4 Synchronous 2400 MHz, 1.6 TB Intel SSD PCIe, and Ubuntu 18.04.2 LTS.

To test the scalability, a varied set of scenarios have been used for which some parts of the topology, such as UEs, have been emulated in order to scale beyond the infrastructure established in the premises of the Beyond 5G Hub group. In the outputs published during this work, a broader set of these experiments can be found, along with a more varied set of topologies. The results shown in this section are based on the variation of the number of UEs in the topology.

Component	Number of <i>UE x DU</i>	Number of <i>DU x Edge</i>	Number of <i>Tenants x Edge</i>	Number of <i>Edge</i>	Number of <i>Servers x Tenant</i>	Number of <i>Tenants x Core</i>	Number of <i>Core</i>
LMA and PC-GUI	1 - 64	2	4	256	1	4	64
Holographic GUI	8 - 512	2	2	4	1	2	4
TMA	1 - 1024	4	8	256	1	8	64

Table 7.1 Ranging of generated scenarios for empirical validation experiments

The scenarios used to carry out the experiments on both LMA and PC-GUI (see Table 7.1) consist of 64 PMs in the core network, and each one has an associated extra PM as a server, in addition to four VMs (one for each tenant) in each of the core machines. On the edge network, there are 256 PMs with four VMs on each PM (one per tenant). Each core physical machine has two Distributed Unit (DU) connected. For each topology, the number of UEs connected in each DU varies from one to 64 by powers of two.

Figure 7.1 shows the time required to generate the complete structure, with the topology layout for each scenario analysed. The number of UEs on the abscissa axis shows the total number of UEs that the analysed topology contains. Since the values of this axis are shown on a logarithmic scale, it can be concluded that the trend of the results follows a linear order. Therefore, a direct relationship can be established between the number of devices that the topology contains and the time it takes to generate the layout structure. For the scenario with more UEs, the time it took to generate the layout is 317 seconds. This is not excessive, since it must be taken into account that the layout is not generated from scratch for such a large topology, and instead the topologies are being reported by different components at different times; thus, the results presented herein are the worst possible cases and will happen only if all the computers of the data centre are switched on all at once. The layout algorithm is non-deterministic, and it modifies the position of each element from the previous position, so

adding a new element or a small set of components should not modify the position of the other elements too much, and this would take significant less calculation time to produce the updated layout. Comparing our obtained results against the work of Lu and Si [76] (2020), where they studied the performance of force-directed 3D graph layouts, they rendered a graph with 4941 nodes in 600 seconds and for a similar size graph (see Figure 7.1 4096 UEs) LMA needed less than 100 seconds. Therefore, it is worth emphasising the performance improvement against their research.

Fig. 7.1 Layout Monitoring Agent total time needed to create a complete layout structure ranging the number of UEs in the topology from 512 to 32,768

Figure 7.2 shows the time required to render the complete network topology for each scenario analysed. This time is measured from the moment when the first spatial position is received from the LMA, until the last device is rendered. A device will not be rendered until its position has been received. In the case of PC-GUI, the total number of UEs is also displayed on the abscissa axis. Notice again the logarithmic scale on this axis which makes the trend of the results also linear. In this case, times are higher than LMA times, especially from 8192 UEs onward. For that 8192 scenario, it took 822 seconds to render the entire network topology. The largest scenario with 32768 UEs took a total of 6229 seconds; this time is too long. However, since the first positions are obtained, the user can start to visualise and explore the topology while it continues incorporating new devices. In section 9.7.4, the

reader can see additional empirical results about the performance analysis of the GUI while rendering a topology.

When comparing both Figures 7.1 and 7.2, calculation and rendering times, respectively, it clearly indicates that the time to calculate after all the optimisations are achieved is significantly lower than the time to render on screen - 317 seconds against 6229 seconds, respectively, for the larger scenario analysed.

Fig. 7.2 PC-GUI total time needed to render a complete multi-tenant 5G network topology ranging the number of UEs in the topology from 512 to 32,768

Topology scenarios used for holographic GUI scalability testing have been selected to be smaller, due to reduced hardware capabilities of the headsets. Both HoloLens 1st Gen and HoloLens 2nd Gen are limited by the wearability of the hardware, which makes the rendering of the topology more expensive. These scenarios (see Table 7.1) are composed of four PMs in the core network as well as in the edge. Two tenants share the physical infrastructure, which means two VMs per PM. Additionally, there is a server PM connected to each PM in the core network. There are two DUs per PM in the edge network. The UEs connected to these DUs ranged from 8 to 512, which means 64 to 4096 UEs in total.

Figure 7.3 shows the time required to complete the rendering of each topology scenario for the two headsets analysed (HoloLens 1st Gen and 2nd Gen). As the number of UEs increases, there is an associated increase in the time experienced by the final user. This increase follows a linear growth, taking into account the steps that occur in an exponential

increase (powers of 2). Furthermore, it can be seen that in the two largest scenarios (2048 UEs and 4096 UEs), the time difference between both headsets is greater. Thus, HoloLens 1st Gen is approximately 19 percent slower than HoloLens 2nd Gen in the scenario with 2048 UEs, and 35 percent slower in the scenario with 4096 UEs. Taking into account the size of these scenarios, and those used for PC-GUI, the following comparisons can be made. The scenario with the least number of devices used for PC-GUI has a total of 5068 devices, and the largest scenario used for holographic GUI has a total of 4184 devices. Comparing these two results, PC-GUI manages to render the complete topology in 227 seconds, HoloLens 1st Gen takes 1,367 seconds, and HoloLens 2nd Gen 1,010 seconds. Even though the scenario is slightly smaller for the holographic GUI, it takes four to six times longer to render the entire topology. These numbers are probably one of the first successful attempts to achieve the same application running in both the PC and the holographic headset with comparable conditions, and thus allowing the extracting of conclusions in terms of the effective computational capabilities of the holographic headsets when used for network topology rendering, monitoring and management.

Fig. 7.3 Total time needed to render a complete multi-tenant 5G network topology using both HoloLens (1 Gen) and HoloLens (2 Gen) ranging the number of UEs in the topology from 64 to 4,096

The network topology scenarios selected to perform the scalability experiments with TMA have a similar structure to the ones used in the previous experiments (see Table 7.1).

However, in this case, the scenarios are composed of a larger number of devices. The topology has the same number of physical machines in the core (64 PMs) and edge (256 PMs) networks. The number of tenant VMs is now eight per PM, which means that there is one VM per tenant in each PM of the core and edge networks. In addition, these scenarios have four DUs connected to each PM on the edge network. The number of UEs connected to each DU ranged from one to 1024. Thus, the smallest scenario had connected a total of 1024 UEs, and the largest scenario had connected 1,048,576 UEs.

Figure 7.4 shows the time required by Topology Monitoring Agent (TMA) to generate the spatial metrics for all candidate nodes in each topology scenario. The reader can see how the number of UEs in this case does not affect the scalability of TMA. The times required for each scenario are between 120 and 140 seconds. This is a good result when dealing with topologies that contain more than a million UEs in the largest scenario. Comparing TMA performance with obtained results in Shao et al. [77], our tailored version of the Closeness centrality achieves better results. They calculated the Closeness centrality for a graph containing 317,080 nodes in 6002.13 seconds. TMA achieved it in less than 140 seconds for a graph with more than one million nodes.

When the results of the TMA are compared against results of LMA, it can be easily seen that in the scenario with 32768 UEs, the LMA already takes more than twice the time to generate the layout. Regarding the PC-GUI results, already in the first scenario, with 512 UEs, PC-GUI takes 227 seconds to render the topology. As for the holographic GUI, both HoloLens 1st Gen and HoloLens 2nd Gen take more than 140 seconds from the topology scenario with 1024 UEs. These numbers can be clearly used to understand further directions in terms of performance improvement.

It is worth mentioning that once the topology is rendered on the screen, the user of the application is able to feel a complete immersive experience at a minimum of 20 Frames Per Second (FPS), and thus the results are fully operational and practical in industrially relevant scenarios (results measuring FPS of the holographic GUI are provided in Section 11.6). Moreover, the user is able to explore the topology and interact with the devices.

Fig. 7.4 Topology Monitoring Agent total time needed to calculate the metrics for a complete multi-tenant 5G network topology ranging the number of UEs in the topology from 1,024 to 1,048,576

Context-aware monitoring and alert/actions metrics are visualised in real-time. This allows the user to perform network troubleshooting and identify the location of problems easily.

The results obtained show action times that allow the tools to display the data in real-time (20 FPS). As for the tools to generate the topology layout, it takes a long time when it initially generates the layout at the same time as the complete topology (e.g., 6229 seconds for 35k nodes). However, it is able to generate a new layout after the new topology changes in a shorter period of time (around 1 second, which can vary depending on the number of changes in the topology). This means that the tool is able to achieve real-time results.

As for the topology visualisation tools, both PC GUI and holographic GUI take a long time when trying to render the topology all at once (e.g., PC GUI 227 seconds for a topology with 5068 devices, and holographic GUI between 1000 and 1400 seconds for a topology with 4184 devices). However, once stabilised, both GUIs manage to update the topology rendering in less time than it takes to receive the new changes, and perform well at rendering with more than 20 FPS. All of this makes possible to visualise the network topology in real-time.

In reference to the calculation of the spatial metrics, TMA is able to generate new values with each topology update in less than one second. This means that it is able to give updated

metrics in less time than the topology changes, and therefore they are values calculated in real-time.

7.1 Critical Analysis

This research work has successfully accomplished the completion of the objectives proposed in Chapter 1.1. The achievement of these objectives has been proved by the peer reviewed publication of four direct outputs, two international journals, and two international conferences. These publications describe clearly the novelty proposed by the work carried out. In addition, three different software components have been developed to show performance and scalability results through empirical experiments. The development of this work has been linked to the European project H2020 SliceNet, where the candidate has been involved in contribution to deliverable 9.3, and different activities carried out by the consortium. Moreover, this work has also been linked to the UWS Immersive project, where the candidate has been involved in diverse outreach activities.

The work carried out is based on the study of the multi-tenant 5G network topologies, where solutions have been proposed to support a better understanding of these topologies. In this way, the management of the new 5G networks can be significantly facilitated, and opens the way for new extensions that allow high-level control over the network. The future outlook for managing large-scale networks is based on zero-touch systems that operate autonomously. These systems must be supervised by experts, especially in the development phases. The solutions proposed in this work allow (LMA and topology GUI) to monitor the status of the network topology in real time, as well as the events that occur and information about resources and sensing. In addition, solutions are proposed that allow to carry out a more intelligent control of the network management (TMA), with the generation of spatial metrics that allow the identification of key nodes of the topology.

LMA is a component exclusively dedicated to generating a logical layout of multi-tenant 5G network topologies. However, behind this specific perspective there is much more. This component is capable of grouping information about a complete topology including logical

parts, such as VMs and tenant namespaces. All this information is represented in an orderly way in the form of a graph, where both physical and logical connections are used. With this perspective, the direct relationship of VMs and PMs, and where they are housed are achieved. This is a key step in order to achieve completeness of the graph. With the use of tenant namespaces, it is also possible to join the virtual networks of each tenant. This allows a correct positioning when it comes to separation of business roles. This layout is not related to the location of the devices, as it is based on the connections between them, and is built to facilitate the visualisation for the user. However, this could be a future extension for the component adding positions based on the geolocation of the device. Despite the specific use case of LMA, which is to provide a layout, so that the topology GUI is capable of orderly rendering the network topology, it is worth exploring other use cases that could be given to these positions in a 3D space. The scalability of LMA has been tested in topologies of up to 37k devices, for which it is possible to generate a complete layout from scratch in approximately five and a half minutes. These topologies do not represent a large-scale topology, so it would be advisable to carry out experiments for larger scenarios. It is important to realise that these experiments have been prepared so that the topology is received at once by LMA; however, once LMA is deployed in a real-time system, the topology constantly changes and grows little by little. From this point of view, LMA does not need to generate the complete layout. LMA will only generate new positions for the new devices, and those of the devices that were already included will be slightly varied. Only the new devices will entail a relatively higher cost to calculate their position.

Topology GUI is the application that allows users to monitor a 5G multi-tenant network in real-time. Through this graphical interface, the complete network topology can be viewed in real-time, which includes both physical devices (e.g., PMs, physical switches, UEs, etc.) and virtual devices (e.g., VMs, software switches, etc.). In addition, it allows browsing and expanding the information about the devices, in order to monitor the physical and virtual network interfaces, as well as the internal software datapaths of each device. Topology GUI also allows access to real-time graphs that show metrics associated with the devices and their interfaces, such as the available resources, the information captured by the sensors of IoT

devices, etc. Topology GUI is provided in two formats, the first is implemented for PC (PC-GUI) in which you can explore the network using the keyboard and the mouse. The second is implemented as an Augmented Reality (AR) application (holographic GUI) for HoloLens 1st Gen and HoloLens 2nd Gen, in which you can explore the network with the movement of your head and using your hands to interact with the network. In the results chapter 7, experiments have been presented that test the scalability of topology GUI in its different implementations and devices, where it has been executed. Furthermore, experiments on device performance while rendering a complete topology can be found in the corresponding results sections of the published articles [1, 3] .

Interpreting the results obtained, it can be seen that the scalability of the application is strongly linked to the hardware of the device, where it is executed. The rendering task is an expensive task that requires a lot of calculations to be able to generate each frame. Graphics engines work by creating polygons for which the visible part is calculated, and these in turn can occlude other polygons that are part of the view. Therefore, the scalability of the application can be related to the number of polygons that a view has. For the development of the topology GUI, the number of polygons necessary has been minimised to be able to visualise a topology correctly; however, it is difficult to achieve large-scale network topologies. Unity3D allows the use of composite meshes in which several elements can be joined to minimise the number of GameObjects, instead of having them separated. The problem with this approach is that it does not allow interaction with the devices in the topology, which would make this functionality impossible. The scalability results obtained allow the PC-GUI to render a topology of 37k devices in approximately 100 minutes. The holographic GUI, due to the smaller hardware characteristics of both headsets, presents longer times. To render a topology of 4,184 devices, HoloLens 1st Gen took approximately 22 minutes and HoloLens 2nd Gen took less than 17 minutes. For a topology of similar size, the PC-GUI was able to render it in less than four minutes. It is clear there is room for improvement in this respect, to allow higher numbers of simultaneous GameObjects to be represented in the screen. The Unity Engine team is currently working on it by investigating

remote rendering farms, but this is currently in its early development stages, and we will see the first results in the incoming years.

TMA is a component capable of generating metrics based on the spatial distribution of the network topology. These metrics are complex metrics that allow you to identify key nodes in the topology, and can be applied in various use cases for network management. The metric studied is Closeness centrality, which measures how far a node is from the rest. This metric provides a way to identify nodes capable of disseminating information very efficiently. Like other metrics based on the centrality of the nodes, this one requires the calculation of the shortest distances between them. For this calculation, the Dijkstra algorithm is used. This algorithm runs in time $O(m + n \log n)$, which is a challenge when scaling the size of the graph (the graph that represents the topology, in this case). Therefore, the approach that has been followed in this work was reducing the number of times it was necessary to calculate the shortest path. For this, three optimisations have been developed: 1) Reduce the set of nodes for which the metric is to be calculated, identifying the possible candidates for a specific use case. 2) Take into account the layout of the topology, assuming that all UEs are leaf nodes and that the shortest path to them is the shortest path to the antenna where they are connected, plus an extra hop. 3) Establish a caching strategy that allows the metric to be recalculated when the topology changes, using the calculations of parts of the topology that have not changed. With the implementation of these optimisations, it is possible to reduce the time of the 5G Closeness centrality algorithm by six orders of magnitude. The scalability results carried out for TMA empirically demonstrate that the component is capable of generating metrics for a topology of approximately one million devices, in little more than two minutes. Therefore, this component is able to work for large-scale topologies and provide metrics in real-time. Moreover, the TMA has been designed to allow integration with other metrics, such as Betweenness centrality, Eigenvector centrality, or PageRank centrality. It would be interesting to investigate these metrics in the future to identify which problems they can solve related to 5G and Beyond network topologies.

Chapter 8

Conclusion and Future Work

There have been seven outputs as a result of this research work: two international journals, two international conferences and three different software intellectual property rights. The primary aim of this research work has been achieved, as well as each of the proposed objectives, as proven in the outputs previously indicated.

In summary, in the research, a component (Layout Monitoring Agent (LMA)), has been designed, developed and empirically evaluated, which is capable of generating a layout structure to logically position the elements of a multi-tenant 5G network topology. This layout structure contains the 3D positions for each device on the network, allowing effective differentiation by users of the physical and virtual network levels. LMA is capable of generating a complete layout structure from scratch for a topology of about 37,000 devices, in approximately 5.5 minutes. This is probably one of the first implementations available for this kind of software.

The topology GUI component, which consists of an interface for the visualisation of multi-tenant 5G network topologies, has been successfully designed, implemented and empirically evaluated. This component uses the layout structure generated by LMA to render the network topology, in a way that is easy for users to understand. PC-GUI supports multi-tenancy, user mobility and business role separation between infrastructure service providers and infrastructure service consumers.

The topology GUI includes validated functionalities that allows the user to explore the network topology, and obtain detailed information for each device. Once a device has been selected, its network interfaces are displayed as well as the internal software datapath. This is probably the first achievement of this kind of accuracy in the rendering of datapaths. In addition, real-time metrics are displayed on the device and its interfaces, as well as those captured by IoT devices. Topology GUI also incorporates a real-time alert system that classifies the events that occur in the devices at three levels of importance, and provides information on the actions taken to resolve these alerts.

Topology GUI has been successfully designed, implemented, and empirically tested in two different versions. PC-GUI is the PC implementation that allows all the above functionalities, through the use of a conventional Windows PC. Holographic GUI is the augmented reality version of the application that has been implemented for HoloLens 1st Gen and HoloLens 2nd Gen. Holographic GUI also allows all the functions detailed above, using the head (to navigate the topology) and hand gestures as the input system.

While the PC-GUI is capable of rendering a topology of about 37,000 devices in approximately 100 minutes, the holographic GUI implementation for HoloLens 1st Gen is capable of rendering a topology of 4,184 devices in about 22 minutes, and HoloLens 2nd Gen in less than 17 minutes. For a topology of similar size, the PC-GUI has been able to render it in less than four minutes.

An innovative algorithm has been proposed to calculate metrics based on the spatial localisation of nodes within the multi-tenant 5G network topologies. This algorithm is based on the Closeness centrality metric for graphs, which has been proven to be useful to identify key nodes, by calculating the shortest paths between them, using the Dijkstra algorithm. The algorithm has been tailored (5G Closeness centrality) for the graphs formed by the multi-tenant 5G network topologies. Furthermore, the 5G Closeness centrality includes three optimisations that reduce execution time by three levels of magnitude. This innovation significantly pushes the state of the art ones, making the calculation of the metric feasible for large-scale networks.

The TMA component has successfully been designed, implemented and empirically evaluated. This component implements the novel 5G Closeness centrality algorithm previously designed. TMA is able to collect all the information about the network topology, and stores it as a graph. Thus, this graph is used to calculate the 5G Closeness centrality periodically, taking into account real-time network updates and reporting them as metrics. The scalability of TMA has been empirically evaluated using large-scale scenarios of multi-tenant 5G network topologies. TMA is capable of generating the metrics for a network topology composed of more than one million devices in approximately two minutes.

Additionally, a use case has been proposed and designed to use the 5G Closeness centrality metric to establish a new Virtual Network Function (VNF) placement strategy. This new strategy uses information about the resources available in each candidate's device, in addition to the proposed spatial metric. The efficiency achieved in the placement of VNFs validates the quality of the metrics investigated.

As future work, different research directions are proposed to face the challenges that have appeared during the implementation of this work, and to continue advancing in the development of the proposed solutions. It is proposed to study the different graph layout algorithms and explore ways to prepare the initial state of the topology. This could make the iterative process of construction of the layout more efficient to improve the scalability and performance of LMA.

The researcher plans to explore ways to optimise topology rendering, as a way to improve the scalability and performance of topology GUI, for both PC-GUI and holographic GUI versions. For example, Microsoft recently introduced remote rendering, which can especially benefit the holographic GUI when running on Augmented Reality (AR) devices. In addition, the integration of features for network control in the topology GUI is another research direction, as well as the integration of features that provide digital twinning as an option to view the digital version of the devices together with their physical version in the real world. This feature is interesting in the holographic GUI due to the nature of AR devices.

As long-term future work, the investigation is planned to continue on to the next-generation of mobile networks. As the trend for communication networks is to achieve

fully autonomous management systems, the idea is to investigate new options for telecommunication operators to allow them identify problems in these systems, and understand how the intelligence of the system is taking the decisions. For example, for self-protection against cyber-attacks, self-optimisation of resource utilisation, self-healing of resource shortages and self-configuration of large-scale infrastructures are some ideas to be further investigated.

The improvement in the scalability of TMA was also proposed. Also, the adaptation for other types of network topologies that are emerging, such as cell-free topologies, where UEs can be connected to more than one base station at the same time, also can form another interesting research direction. Similarly, the spatial metrics are proposed for application to other usage cases such as cache allocation, load balancer allocation, etc.

Also, the new Graph Neural Networks (GNN) can be an interesting way to extract information from the topology, and use such information to implement strategies to carry out network management tasks.

Finally, in for the long haul, new ways of exploiting the topological information to contribute in the autonomous decisions of the future generations of networks will be explored. For example, network slicing seems to be a promising technology that will stay in the future to provide determinate Quality of Service (QoS) in the different segments of the network, as well as the end-to-end network slicing. It is possible that the spatial status of the network topology can be used to achieve an optimised way to help in the creation of the slices.

Part II

Publications

Chapter 9

5GTopoNet: Real-Time Topology Discovery and Management on 5G Multi-Tenant Networks

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9.1 Abstract

The Fifth-Generation (5G) mobile networks leverage virtualisation and softwarisation to reduce both capital and operating expenditures whilst benefiting from network programmability and flexibility for various use cases. Meanwhile, virtualisation and softwarisation introduce unprecedented complexity to network infrastructure topologies, which poses substantial challenges to network topology management. This paper proposes a novel architecture to enable network administrators to achieve real-time network discovery and spatial representation of the software data path, containers, virtual machines, and geographically distributed edges to help network troubleshooting and management tasks. Another important innovation is the flexibility to support a significant number of business roles by means of a novel method to perform data model alignment between different business roles. The architecture has been designed, prototyped and validated, and experiment results have demonstrated promising scalability of the proposed solution.

9.2 Introduction

Virtualisation and softwarisation are the cornerstone of the forthcoming Fifth-Generation (5G) mobile networks. The resultant 5G software data paths, combining virtual and physical networks, pose significant challenges in understanding the network topology of the novel virtualised and softwarised 5G network architectures for data centre administrators, telecommunication operators, and infrastructure providers for network management purposes. The challenges are exacerbated by 5G multi-tenancy, which enables multiple tenants such as network operators to share the same physical infrastructure, to reduce capital and operating costs significantly [11]. Multi-tenancy imposes the usage of overlay networks to perform resource and network isolation for each of the tenants over the same physical infrastructure. Such isolation requires the creation of new logical networks and virtual machines (VMs) per tenant, which in turn leads to a more complex network topology and thus more complicated troubleshooting of networking issues. Furthermore, the challenge is propagated to different geographical locations in 5G networks where multi-tenancy is extended to the edges of

the network in the Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC) paradigm to facilitate localised processing and thus help meet ambitious 5G Key Performance Indicator (KPI). Moreover, there is a clear need to differentiate business roles associated to the multi-tenant infrastructure. This separation between Internet Service Provider (ISP) and Internet Service Consumer (ISC) is currently happening in various cases involving public cloud providers, telecommunication providers, digital service providers and other business roles. The separation of business roles entails the definition of the topological boundaries between the ISP physical network and the ISC virtual tenant networks. This has significant implications in terms of technical and legal responsibilities, since this business role separation can determine the physical and virtual scopes of the administrative domains. The complexity of the network topology is even greater when the infrastructure needs to deal with the mobility of user equipment between different access points, which is associated to 5G networks where user mobility, multi-tenant isolation and virtualisation are key elements. The understanding of such complexity in network topology is a critical aspect for the successful adoption of these technologies and efficient network management. In operational 5G environments, services need to be delivered to a large number of users, and network issues can rise from any of the physical and virtual network interfaces. Therefore, the complexity in 5G network topology has become prohibitively high for conventional network management platforms to handle, and existing network topology awareness tools are not capable of circumventing these challenges.

The main contribution of this paper is the design, implementation and validation of a highly innovative architecture to enable network administrators to obtain real-time network discovery and spatial representation of 5G network topology, thereby empowering them to handle the complexity of the 5G multi-tenant network infrastructure. The proposed architecture enables both physical and virtual network topology representations and their interconnection. The main innovation is the proposed solution that addresses the following outstanding challenges:

1. The architecture should deal with the complexity associated to the software data path and the usage of virtualisation and containerisation.

2. The architecture should deal with the complexity associated to the geographical distribution of the architectural components in the novel 5G networks (edge and core networks).
3. The architecture should support both multi-tenancy and user mobility.
4. The architecture should be flexible enough to allow use cases with the ISP and ISC business role separation.
5. The architecture should be flexible enough to allow the representation of the network topologies from different perspectives: ISP, ISC, and ISP and ISC (ISP + ISC), respectively.
6. The architecture should be able to identify and understand the topological boundaries between ISP and ISC.

The proposed architecture has been designed, prototyped and integrated in a real multi-tenant 5G network, currently deployed in our premises. An intensive functional validation has been carried out to validate the innovations indicated above. The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 analyses the state of the art in network topology architectures and software. Section 3 describes the proposed novel architecture, including details of each component in the architecture. Section 4 presents a sequence diagram to explain the design and behaviour of the architecture. Section 5 shows implementation details and challenges associated to the different software components prototyped. Section 6 presents empirical results about the validation and scalability of the proposed architecture. Finally, Section 7 provides conclusions and future work.

9.3 Related Work

Multi-tenant 5G networks pose several challenges that the current topology tools are unable to overcome to allow real-time spatial representation of the network. This section provides a comprehensive enumeration of these challenges, as listed in Table 9.1. Furthermore, Table

9.2 provides an overview analysis of the challenges introduced in Table 9.1 in the state of the art compared with the proposed architecture in this paper to allow a clear identification of our contribution. In the following, we provide a detailed review of these work.

ID	Description of Discovery Challenge
I	Physical Network Topologies (L1) between Devices
II	Logical Network Topologies (L2) between Computers
III	Virtual Machine Overlay Topologies
IV	Virtual Network Overlay Topologies
V	Container Machine Overlay Topologies
VI	Container Network Overlay Topologies
VII	Multi-tenant Information for III (see III)
VIII	Multi-tenant Information for IV (see IV)
IX	Geographical Distribution of Machines (Edge/Core)
X	Specialised Physical Devices (Software-Defined Radio Devices)
XI	LTE/5G UE Topologies
XII	LTE/5G UE Mobility across Radio Access Networks (Antennas)
XIII	Supported Business Role: ISP
XIV	Supported Business Role: ISC
XV	Supported Business Role: ISP + ISC
XVI	Alignment between ISP and ISC reported topologies
XVII	Integrated ISP / ISC Perspectives

Table 9.1 Challenges to achieve a real-time multi-tenant 5G network topology

	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI	XII	XIII	XIV	XV	XVI	XVII
Total Network Inventory[23]	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗
R. Sanby et al. [78]	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗
AixBOMS [24]	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗
nuGEN [25]	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗
Zhou and Ma [26]	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗
Wang et al. [27]	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗
Jiang et al. [79]	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗
Rojas et al. [28]	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗
NMSaaS [29]	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗
Network Topology Mapper [30]	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗
Toufga et al. [31]	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗
OpenDayLight [35]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗
Skydive [12]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗
MidoNet[36]	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗
5GTopoNet (Ours Contribution)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Table 9.2 Analysis of the state of the art with respect to our contribution against the challenges required to achieve real-time multi-tenant 5G network topologies

Total Network Inventory [23] and AixBOMS [24] are examples of traditional network inventory management system for use in offices, companies, and small and large corporate networks. They provide tools for layout plans, rack management and visualisation, power

management, reports and detailed technical device information. Sanby et al. [78] reported a Traceroute study carried out on African NRENs, demonstrating the joint use of different probing protocols to achieve a 65% reduction in the number of probe packets sent to discover the network topology. All these systems rely on Open Systems Interconnection (OSI) Layer 3 (L3) discovery mechanisms so that they simply do not show any device along the path and just connectivity between devices and at most Internet Protocol (IP) network topologies.

nuGEN™3D Visualisation for IoT Networks [25] is a Visual Network Visualisation Management System (NMS) for physical networks. It simplifies the management and optimisation of networks via visualisation of the entire network and its dynamics in real-time. nuGEN™ has cloud-based and on-premise versions, with real-time analytics. NuGEN claims to be suitable for discovering virtual networks; however, the discovery methods supported do not indicate so. They are ping sweep, Secure SHell (SSH), Telnet, Domain Name System (DNS) and Simple Network Management Protocol (SNMP) and none of these methods allows discovering overlay networks, which are directly associated to virtual infrastructures.

Zhou and Ma [26] proposed an algorithm to discover physical layout topology structure of Ethernet networks with incomplete address forwarding table information. Their algorithm can handle both Layer-2 switches with Virtual Local Area Network (VLAN) and Layer-3 switches. Analogously, Wang et al. [27] introduced a network topology discovery algorithm based on SNMP, which can discover the target topology completely and accurately through combining the topology discovery of the network layer and link layer. They identify that there are many different manufactures and various kinds of equipment in the network, and every manufacture has their own support on SNMP whilst the impact of the heterogeneity is left for future work. In addition, Jiang et al. [79] relied on SNMP to propose an effective topology algorithm that improves the efficiency and quality of the discovery process.

Rojas et al. [28] presented a Tree Exploration Discovery Protocol (TEDP), an alternative protocol to the Link-Layer Discovery Protocol (LLDP), proving that shortest paths can be built simultaneously when the topology information is gathered, without extra messages compared with LLDP. They also analysed two alternative implementations for Tree Exploration Discovery Protocol (TEDP) and give insights into some features that Software-Defined

Networking (SDN) platforms should ideally provide for an efficient topology discovery service. They provide support for the discovery of overlay networks. In the same direction, NMSaaS [29] is another network discovery software, which uses SNMP (V1, V2c, V3) (Cisco Discovery Protocol (CDP)), WMI, ICMP, WMI, VMware and more to discover IT assets and creates dynamic maps based on Layer 2 and Layer 3 connections. It is noted that the integration with the hypervisor allows the discovery of the virtual assesses. SolarWinds provides the Network Topology Mapper software [30] that automatically discovers and delineates network topology and produces comprehensive, easy-to-view network diagrams. It supports multiple discovery methods, including SNMP v1-v3 (CDP and LLDP protocols), Internet Control Message Protocol (ICMP), Windows Management Instrumentation (WMI), CDP, VMware, Hyper-V, and more. It can provide reports on switch ports, VLANs, subnets, and inventory. It also directly addresses PCI compliance, FIPS 140-2, and others that require maintenance of an up-to-date network diagram. Toufga et al. [31] presented an effective topology discovery service for SDN-based hybrid vehicular networks. They demonstrate that the “defacto” OpenFlow-based topology discovery service is not adapted for Software-Defined Vehicular Networks and thus they propose some directions to follow in order to address the highlighted limits and to design an efficient topology discovery service more suited to vehicular networks.

OpenDaylight (ODL) [35] is a modular open platform for customising and automating network control, monitoring and discovery at scale. ODL provides control for multi-tenant isolation in cloud computing stacks such as OpenStack. Thus, it is aware of the multi-tenant overlay networks. Moreover, Skydive [12] and MidoNet [36] are advanced open-source real-time network topology tools able to discover physical and overlay networks of both virtual machines and containers with multi-tenant support.

However, none of the above solutions is able to provide support for the creation of 5G network topology where 5G users need to be discovered, and tracked while moving across antennas, where 5G VMs are migrating in a matter of seconds leading to the change of the network topology, and where specialised hardware such as radio equipment needs to be also discovered. Almost all the software analysed could be executed in either ISP or ISC, and

they can discover the corresponding topology for the respective business role. However, none of these systems is able to perfectly align the topologies reported from the different business roles together. This lack of alignment makes impossible use cases where both ISP and ISC are the same organisation, which is a typical scenario for 5G mobile operators. It also hampers providing network discovery as a service to ISCs and integrated ISP and ISC network topology view to ISPs for troubleshooting support to ISCs. All these open issues have been the main motivation of this research.

9.4 5G Multi-tenant Infrastructure

Fig. 9.1 Multi-tenant 5G Network Overview

This section describes the 5G multi-tenant network infrastructure managed by our proposed architecture. This infrastructure is illustrated in Fig. 9.1. Two different levels of network infrastructure are depicted to represent an illustrative example of a 5G multi-tenant network topology where the essential components of both physical and virtual overlay network infrastructures. The lower network is the Physical Network. Multiple 5G users gain access to this physical network by being connected to the Radio Access Network via different Distributed Unit (DU) using the 5G terminology [16]. Multiple DUs are then connected to a pool of Centralized Unit (CU) at the same Edge of the network using a Cloud-RAN deployment. An Edge is a Points of Presence (PoP) of the infrastructure located very close to the final users where computational processing can be allocated to achieve low-latency communications between the infrastructure and users. Multiple Edges are connected to the

Core Network where there is a set of physical machines, usually located in the data centre premises. An Edge has limited processing capabilities, whereas the Core has significantly higher capabilities. The Core network has a data centre layout where there are several compute machines (only one compute machine is shown for clarity). These compute machines gain access to the Internet by mean of a network device. This physical infrastructure runs a cloud stack that allows multi-tenant isolation of the different physical resources through virtualisation. This cloud stack is able to deal with physical machines that are geographically separated from the data centre, such as the different Edges of the infrastructure.

Analogously, the upper level of Fig. 9.1 is the Virtual Network. It is composed by a set of virtual machines, containers and/or name-spaces, depending on the vitalisation technology employed. Henceforth all of them will be referred indistinctly as VMs even though they are a mix of these technologies for brevity. The logical components of the 5G network run inside of the physical machines and each logical component belongs to a particular tenant of the network. As shown in Fig. 9.1, switches join both physical and virtual networks. They are software switches such as Linux Bridges or Open vSwitch [80], which allow the enforcement of the tenant isolation between different VMs.

VMs are depicted in different colours to emphasize the ownership of them. It is noted that there are VMs that are deployed on Edge physical machines and others deployed in Core physical machines; it extends multi-tenancy support to the edge of the network, creating a MEC infrastructure. In Fig. 9.1, there are two different tenants sharing the same physical infrastructure. The tenant network is represented as a conceptual “virtual hub”, which is just an illusion for the perception of the ISC and allows communication among all the VMs that belong to the same tenant. This architecture allows every tenant to share the same physical infrastructure to have its own isolated network. Such “virtual hub” is in reality implemented using overlay networks such as Virtual Extensible Local Area Network (VXLAN) and Generic Routing Encapsulation (GRE) network encapsulation technologies.

Other architectural components in the 5G architecture include User Plane Function (UPF) for access to the Internet, Access and Mobility Function (AMF) for User Equipment (UE) based authentication, authorisation and mobility management, Session Management Function

(SMF) for session management and IP address allocation to UE, and so on (Kim et al. [16]). All these 5G components with the only exception of the DU are fully softwarised. In this work, we focus on the AMF and SMF components for handling user mobility and tracking a user throughout the network.

9.5 5GTopoNet Architecture Overview

Fig. 9.2 5GTopoNet Architecture Overview

This section describes the 5GTopoNet architecture proposed to achieve the real-time topologies of 5G multi-tenant networks. This novel architecture is illustrated in Fig. 9.2. Each box represents a software component, and each circle represents a topic in a publication/subscription message bus architecture. These topics allow all the subscribed components (those with an arrow from the topic) to receive the message sent by the publishing component (those with an arrow to the topic). Some of these components are also depicted in Fig. 9.1 to show where they are deployed in the network. Those not shown are deployed in another physical machine for management purposes. The architecture comprises a set of software agents that are responsible for gathering the topological information, keeping it up-to-date and reporting the changes about such information to the “Topology” exchange topic. These agents are described as follows:

Resource Inventory Agent (RIA) is a component deployed inside each physical machine of the 5G multi-tenant network (if the use case requires ISP topological information). This agent is responsible for generating the topological information for all the devices, ports and

connections between ports and devices available in the machine. To achieve this purpose, RIA is responsible for discovering the following information: i) Physical Machine and its logical and virtual network interfaces, ii) VMs and their virtual network interfaces, iii) Containers and their network interfaces, iv) Software switches, v) Specialised Physical Devices such as Software-Defined Radio (SDR) and their network interfaces, vi) Interconnection between network interfaces, and vii) Multi-tenant information of VMs. It is noted that the responsibility of v) is to overcome the challenge X depicted in Table 9.2.

Similarly, RIA can also be deployed inside the VMs of the 5G multi-tenant network (if the use case requires ISC topological information). When RIA is deployed only in physical machines (ISP domain), the VMs are considered as a black box where there is no information about what network topology is available inside such VMs. When RIA is deployed only in VMs (ISC domain), the topology reported is only the overlay network view for this particular tenant, and no information is revealed about the real ISP topology underneath. In a third case, when RIA is deployed in both ISP and ISC, both topological reports are combined in order to provide a complete topological overview. This is a significant innovation not achieved before, and the details of this joining process is described in Section 9.6. This is exactly the challenge XVI in Tables 9.1 and 9.2. The fulfilment of this new feature will allow overcoming challenge XVI by natural extension since once the alignment of data models is performed, the use case where ISP and ISC business roles are associated to the same business entity is supported.

Topology Inventory Manager (TIM) is a centralised component that provides information not available inside the computers/devices where RIA is deployed. This lack of availability could be for two different reasons. Firstly, RIA cannot be installed in closed hardware appliances and thus, in this cases, topological information needs to be extracted out of the appliances from a centralised place. This is the reason why TIM is responsible for generating the topological information of all the hardware appliances where RIA cannot be installed, including managed switches and routers. Secondly, there are some cases where information is stored in the management software and not distributed to computers. These are architectural decisions of the management stack used and thus implementation-dependant.

Therefore, in the cases where RIA cannot access such information, TIM will extract the information by its integration with the management stack. For example, in the case of Open-Stack, the tenant information about the networks is only made available through management interfaces and never distributed into the computer nodes. The details of this integration will be explained in Section 9.6.

5G Mobile Agent (MA) is a centralised component that is deployed in each of the tenant networks that need to provide topological information about the UE and their mobility across different cells of the radio access networks. Monitoring topological information of UE across the different access points enables new capabilities related to the detection of deny of service attacks as proposed by Al-Dulaimi et al. [81]. To achieve so, this component is directly integrated with the Mobility Management Entity (MME) for the case of 4G architectures and with both SMF and AMF for the case of 5G architectures. SMF and AMF already track the UE to allow connectivity to them so that this 5G-MA just extracts such information to publish it in the “Topology” topic. This architectural component allows overcoming challenges XI and XII available in Tables 9.1 and 9.2.

Apart from these three topology agents, the proposed 5GTopoNet architecture has three more architectural components for management purposes as described below:

Layout Monitoring Agent (LMA) is the component that helps the spatial positioning of the topology reported by the different topology agents. LMA receives all the information about topologies being reported and runs customised algorithms to determine the best spatial allocation of all these components with the main intention to provide useful and effective rendering of large-scale information to the network administrators. As a result of the layout algorithms, it publishes metrics indicating the spatial locations, which are later on used by other 5GTopoNet components to render the devices, ports and connection in the best possible locations for human understanding.

Graphical User Interface (GUI) renders the topology to the network administrators in order to facilitate troubleshooting. Fig. 9.2 shows how the same architectural component is divided into two different configurations. In one configuration, the user of this graphical component is the ISP, which implies that it can see every device, port and connection

available in the topology. If ISC RIAs are instantiated, this mode allows seeing as well the topology of each of the tenants in a white-box approach. In the other configuration, the user is the ISC, and only the topology associated to that particular ISC is shown. An important filtering mechanism has been implemented in this component to make sure it does not receive unnecessary information to avoid privacy leakage.

Topology Persistor (TP) achieves the persistence of the topology information into a database, following a data lake approach where all the information is stored in a common place.

9.6 Design and Implementation

9.6.1 Design Approach

Fig. 9.3 5GTopoNet Architecture Design

Fig. 9.3 depicts the architectural design of all the software components in 5GTopoNet. All the components for extracting the topology information (RIA, TIM and 5G-MA) have a similar design based on a plug-in based architecture that provides an extensible mechanism to on-board new capabilities to the architecture. They periodically extract the topological

information from the managed system and keep it in an in-memory database that tracks the topological changes. Such changes are also reported periodically. Topology information is simultaneously received by TP, LMA and GUI. TP keeps an updated representation of the network topology in the database whereas GUI performs the rendering of such topology for the final users. To do such rendering, every device part of the topology needs to have associated their spatial coordinates. The coordinates are provided periodically by LMA by executing the algorithms implemented in the *GraphManager*. This layout algorithm is our customised version of Hu's algorithm [69].

9.6.2 Data Model

Let us introduce the general principles of the 5GTopoNet data model used to describe the topological information. There are three key concepts in the data model: *Device*, *DevicePort* and *Connection*. A *Device* is any of the physical or logical devices in the infrastructure. It is described by means of a set of attributes such as a *deviceType*, a *model* or a *managementIPAddress*, among others. Among these attributes a subset is used to identify uniquely such a device. They are i) *HostName*, and ii) *tenantId* referring to the owner of the device (if any). A *DevicePort* is any network port in a *Device*. It has several attributes such as *macAddress*, *ipv4Address*, *ipv4Mask*, among others. Among these attributes, a subset is used to identify uniquely such a port. They are i) *interfaceName*, ii) *HostName* and iii) *tenantId*. A *Connection* is mainly composed by a *srcResource* and a *dstResource* and represents connections between *Devices* or between *DevicePorts*.

9.6.3 ISP and ISC Data Model Alignment

Physical and Virtual Host Alignment

The challenge is to achieve that the reporting of the *Devices* and *DevicePorts* for VMs/containers is exactly the same for those attributes that identify uniquely such resources, thereby allowing the alignment of data models.

To do so, 5GTopoNet leverages the usage of a new functionality in recent Linux kernels coined as *Predictable Network Interface Names*. This feature has been included in v197 of the systemd/udev kernel module, and it is activated by default onward. The original reason why this feature has been included in the kernel is that classic naming scheme for network interfaces makes the assignment of the interfaces' names not deterministic. Thus, classic naming assigns names in order (“eth0”, “eth1”, ...) to all interfaces as they are probed by the drivers. However, the driver probing is generally not predictable for modern technology, which makes the naming not deterministic as soon as multiple network interfaces are available.

This new feature incorporates the name of the network interface and the type of interface, e.g. on motherboard interfaces (eno1) and PCI Express (ens1). The name also includes the PCI slot ID or the index number of the interface for on-board devices. Thus, for example, the interface enp2s1 refers to the PCI Express network card connected to the second PCI slot and within the network card, refers to the first port available in the card.

Thus, when RIA is installed in the physical machine, it has access to the inventory of VMs/containers created inside this machine. The inventory contains the description of such machines, including memory size, hard disk and network interfaces. The description of such network interfaces includes to which virtual bus ID they are connected, and to which virtual port in such virtual network cards they are connected. This information is retrieved from RIA, and it is able to “predict” the name that the interface will have inside the operating system of this machine. The “prediction” of the *hostName* of such a VM will correspond to the name of the VM in the management stack. The management stack injects such a name when the VMs are created using the cloud-init mechanisms¹ so that they can be “predicted” as well. Finally, the information about the owner/tenant of such a VM is directly available in the host machine. Thus, for example, a virtual network interface of a given VM that is connected to Bus 3 and port 1 will be predicted as *enp3s1*. The reported information about such interfaces would be *DevicePort=enp3s1; HostName=AMF; tenantId=24423-52341-35287-32345*.

¹Cloud-init is available at <https://cloud-init.io/>

When RIA is installed inside the VM of a given tenant, it receives the ID of the tenant it belongs to as a configuration parameter. Thus, when extracting the topological information, it uses such configuration parameters as *tenantId*, and both hostname and network interface name will match those predicted by the RIA running in the physical machine.

5G Distributed Unit Alignment

The challenge is to achieve that the reporting of the *Distributed Units* (DUs) for VMs to be exactly the same for those attributes that identify uniquely such resources, thereby allowing the alignment of data models. Two different types of DUs have been investigated. On the one hand, there are some 5G DUs that are connected using an Ethernet interface. In this first case, the strategy is to follow exactly the same approach indicated in the alignment between virtual and physical machines. On the other hand, there are 5G DUs that are connected to the physical machine using a USB interface. In this second case, the USB is connoted directly to the VM/containers using a USB pass-through technology. The key approach used to align data models employs the USB serial number and USB PCI address that are a unique identifier of the DU and its communication interface, respectively. Both are accessible from both VMs and physical machines. Moreover, the USB pass-through is initiated by the management plane of the physical machine. Thus, the RIA can know what *tenantId* is the target VM being passed through and in consequence, is able to report information about such interfaces as *DevicePort=2500:0200; HostName=070001874500; tenantId=24423-54341-35287-32345*. Analogously, when the RIA is installed inside the VM of a given tenant, values will match those extracted by the RIA running in the physical machine.

Aligned Data Models

As a result, both data models are aligned to allow a dual view of ISP and ISC topologies and also allow the support of the corresponding use cases. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first attempt to align data models belonging to different 5G business roles under the same common umbrella. Moreover, there are several implications to this alignment. One is the first definition of the security and privacy boundaries between business roles. The information

exposed between them is equivalent in the physical world to allow one's customer to enter one's premises to see the chassis of a computer but not allow the customer to interact with this computer. It is noted that to see the chassis allows someone to infer a lot of information, including the number of physical devices connected, if it is powered on or off, how many PCI slots it has and what PCI slots are the cards connect to, among others. This is analogous to what it means in the virtualisation/containerisation world when using our enabling approach.

9.6.4 Implementation Details

In terms of implementation, all the components have been implemented in Java 8, and they are executed in computers running Linux with the only exception of the Graphical User Interface (GUI) which has been implemented in .Net C# and running in Windows. TIM has been integrated with SNMP devices with support for both LLDP and CDP discovery protocols and also with OpenStack Queens ² to extract multi-tenant information. RIA has been integrated with Linux namespaces/containers (ip netns) , Linux Hardware inventory tools (lshw and lspci), software switches (Open vSwitch and Linux Bridges) and LLDP/CDP Discovery tools (lldpcli). 5G-MA has been integrated with both Mosaic5G Stack (development branch) ³ and also NextEPC (development branch) ⁴. In both cases, 5G-MA extracts the topological information in the following way. 5G-MA is integrated with MME and Packet Data Network Gateway (PGW) in the Core Network for pre-5G core implementations and will be integrated with SMF and AMF when 5G native core networks are available. The integration with MME allows extracting the relationship between the International Mobile Subscriber Identity (IMSI) and DU id. The integration with the PGW allows extracting the IP address of the UE associated to the IMSI. With the DU id, the 5G-MA knows which DU the UE is connected to. This information allows continuously tracking UE along the network. TP has been integrated with MySQL 5.5 ⁵ as a persistence back-end. This integration has been carried out to validate all the functionalities claimed, and the plugin-based approach makes the

²OpenStack Queens is available at <https://www.openstack.org/software/queens/>

³Mosaic5G is available at <http://mosaic-5g.io/>

⁴NextEPC is available at <https://nextepc.org>

⁵MySQL is available at <https://www.mysql.com/>

architecture extensible, and thus further functionalities can be added later on. GUI has been integrated with Unity 2018.1 ⁶. The integration of TIM to OpenStack was especially challenging, and it is worth mentioning the approach. Fig. 9.3 shows a simplified OpenStack architecture where both Nova and Neutron components are publishing to different topics the internal information of OpenStack, and at the same time this is stored in a database. Our integration has been hooked in both OpenStack database and also message bus in order to allow a rapid near real-time response in topological changes.

9.6.5 Workflow of the Framework

Fig. 9.4 5GTopoNet framework sequence diagram

To provide a better understanding about the interaction between all the architectural components of the proposed framework, a sequence diagram is provided in Fig. 9.4. RIA, TIM, 5G-MA, LMA and GUI are the software components that compose the framework and they interact with each other using two message exchanges by employing a message broker middle-ware system: topology exchange and metrics exchange.

⁶Unity is available at <https://unity.com/>

The operation of the framework can be reduced to four loops. The first one represents a RIA software instance (as example of all the distributed RIA instances deployed in the system). It reports periodically changes in the topology of the machines they are installed. Similarly, TIM and 5G-MA gather their corresponding topological information at the same periodic interval. These actions are repeated every x seconds to keep the information updated, but it does not mean that the three agents have to do it in the same time interval. These components send the topological information discovered to the (*Topology Exchange*) where LMA and GUI are subscribed and therefore they receive such topological information.

The forth loop represents a different procedure. After LMA receives a change in the topology, it generates a topology structure. This structure is reported to *Metrics Exchange* where the GUI is subscribed. Then, the GUI will update the topology structure rendering the topology components with respect to the new spatial positions.

9.7 Empirical Results

This section describes a set of validation and scalability tests that have been conducted over the 5GTopoNet architecture in order to prove the claimed contributions with the level of scalability achieved.

9.7.1 Testbed Description

The validation tests in this work have been performed in a real 5G multi-tenant infrastructure testbed. This infrastructure is composed of one computer in the Core network, and one computer in each of the two Edge networks. Each of these computers is a high-performance laptop EUROCOM Sky X9E3, with Intel CPU i7 7700K 4.2GHz and 64GB RAM DDR4-2400. In both Edges, there are two Universal Software Radio Peripheral (USRP) B210 SDR DUs to connect 5G mobile phones. Each SDR DU has an antenna operating at Band7 with a duplexer. The core and edges are connected through a switch that allows a complete data path. The management computer where the 5GTopoNet architecture has been deployed is a Dell T5810, with Intel Xeon CPU E5-2630 v4 2.20GHz, 32GB RAM, and 512GB SDD. It

runs a Windows 10 platform where TIM, TP, LMA, 5G-MA and GUI are installed. RIA is deployed in each of the computers of the infrastructure.

9.7.2 5G Multi-tenant Infrastructure Validation

Fig. 9.5 5GTopoNet ISP screenshot of our 5G MEC Infrastructure

Fig. 9.6 5GTopoNet ISP screenshot of an Edge physical machine opened to unveil the complexity of the software data path available inside

The infrastructure is managed by OpenStack ⁷, a well-known cloud stack platform. Two different tenants of the infrastructure are deployed. Each of the tenants has a set of VMs in

⁷OpenStack is available at <https://www.openstack.org/>

the Core network and one container in each of the Edges. KVM⁸ and LXC⁹ have been used for this purpose. Each tenant runs Mosaic5G¹⁰ as the 5G radio access platform to allow the UE devices to access the network. To be concrete, the CU runs in the containers at the Edges, and the whole EPC runs inside of the same machine in the Core network for simplification. NextEPC has been employed as the Core network since Mosaic5G has not provided support for UE handover across antennas. Both are supported by 5G-MA by their integration with the MME and Serving Gateway (SGW)/PGW software components. The modular architecture of the 5G-MA will allow extensible support for native implementations of 5G Core networks when available. The SDR has been configured to use 2x2 Multiple-input Multiple-output (MIMO) and to broadcast the network, via Public Land Mobile Network (PLMN) broadcast, for the tenant network it belongs to. Fig. 9.5 shows a screenshot of the result of the discovery of the 5G topology using 5GTopoNet. As shown, there are two different Edges where two different SDR DUs are connected to each of the Edge. Then, eighth different UE devices are discovered to be currently connected to the network. The Edges are located on different floors, and the two SDR DUs are allocated on the same floor whilst belonging to different tenants. This is why the balance in the number of UE devices connected to each SDR can be controlled. The Edge physical machines host two different containers (running the CU software). They are depicted in different colours to represent the tenant information. The two Core computers are used to get access to the external servers (two connected to each Core network) through a switch. The Core computers run two VMs, one per tenant with the EPC software. There is a fifth physical machine close to the centre of the network, which is the OpenStack Neutron machine used to get access to the Internet. This machine also hosts two different containers used by Neutron to provide Dynamic Host Configuration Protocol (DHCP) services for each of the tenant networks. The figure shows the complexity associated to the software data path by making using of a tailored 3D spatial disposition of the components. Moreover, when the user clicks on any of the machines, it is opened in order to show the complex data path available inside of it. Fig. 9.6 shows the discovered

⁸KVM is available at <https://www.linux-kvm.org>

⁹LXC is available at <https://linuxcontainers.org>

¹⁰Mosaic5G is available at <http://mosaic-5g.io/>

information about such a data path. It is worth mentioning how a software switch is depicted in the figure connecting the different VMs with the physical machine and its physical network interfaces. This is an Open vSwitch software employed to perform tenant isolation, to control security policies and to allow communications between the VMs belonging to the same tenant. A user can see logical "tun/tap" interfaces, physical interfaces, interconnections with the Linux kernel in a very simple way, even with the incredible complexity associated with the discovery of these configurations.

The visual distribution of the devices has been tackled by LMA to maximise the visibility understandably. The figure shows how both 5G users and multi-tenancy are visualised. When a user is experiencing a handover across antennas, it is animated in the GUI. Thus, this section has validated the three first innovations claimed in Section 9.2.

9.7.3 Validation of Business Role Separation

Fig. 9.7 5GTopoNet screenshot of the ISC view

Fig. 9.5 described in Section 9.7.2 represents the case where the ISP can see the complete overview of the infrastructure. When the ISP clicks on a physical machine, it is able to see the content of the machine since it is the owner, as depicted in Fig. 9.6. However, when the ISP clicks on a VM, it will see either an empty box with no further information or the complete

rendering of the software data path, similar to the one depicted for the physical machine, depending on if the ISP also has an ISC role (ISP + ISC scenario) or not. The scenario running in our infrastructure is an ISP + ISC scenario where both RIAs report information to validate the alignment of data models. Both figures of the software data path of a VM has been included as sub-figures in Fig. 9.8. It is noted that the links from the physical machines depicted in Fig. 9.5 exactly match the link interfaces of the VMs shown in Fig. 9.8, and this has validated the alignment of interfaces between physical and virtual machines described in Section 9.6.3.

Fig. 9.8 5GTopoNet screenshot of the software data for VMs on different business roles

Another scenario is that when a given tenant (ISC) is logged in the 5GTopoNet GUI, it can only have access to the information related to its virtual network, and all the information related to other tenants or to the physical machines will be hidden. Fig. 9.7 displays the information shown to ISC - Tenant A. It is noted that it matches all the red boxes depicted in Fig. 9.5, although now the tenant is not able to have any information about the location of their VMs with respect to the physical machines or how many physical machines are available, and so on. Probably, the most significant change of this view is related to the fact that now the DU is connected directly to the VM/container rather than to the physical machine (see A). Such a connection represents the USB pass-through described in Section 9.6.3. An ISC is only able to see the DUs and 5G UE devices under its control. It is noted that this section has validated the last three innovations claimed in Section 9.2.

9.7.4 Overhead and Performance Analysis

The purpose of this subsection is to provide an analysis of performance and overhead of each software component available in the proposed framework. The components in charge of reporting topological information are RIA, TIM and 5G-MA. Regarding TIM and 5G-MA, they are deployed in specific management machines due to their centralised nature and they are integrated with the control plane of the network, leading to an almost no consumption of resources and to no scalability concerns. However, RIA needs to be installed in every physical and virtual machine (depending the business role). This means that this is crucial for scalability and its computational cost need to be analysed.

Fig. 9.9 RIA computational load while discovering all the resources of a compute server

Fig. 9.9 provides two graphs, aligned in time, plotting RIA behaviour along two minutes of execution. This RIA instance was running in the core network described in the *Testbed Description* and responsible for discovering only the devices of such machines. RIA was reporting 115 devices being discovered. Graph 9.9a shows the percentage of CPU consumed. It is noted that after 30 seconds the component reached a steady state and the percentage of CPU was less than 3%. Graph 9.9b shows the memory usage in the same period of time. In this case, the amount of memory for stabilisation in approximately 5 seconds was around 80 MiB. This is the real footprint in terms of control overhead.

To represent the communication load in the system, Fig. 9.10 shows the bandwidth usage required when discovering the largest topology scenario analysed in this manuscripts (35000 devices). Each peak of the graph is approximately 290 Kbps and it happened at

Fig. 9.10 Communication load when discovering a whole topology

regular intervals, which matched the refresh rate of all the discovery components (TIM, RIA, 5G-MA). In the bootstrapping process (the first 15 seconds of execution), there was one peak of exactly 2.27 Mbps where the whole topology was being discovered for the first time and then it was updated at regular intervals.

Fig. 9.11 5GTopoNet GUI computational load from starting until stabilisation after render the whole topology

Finally, Fig. 9.11 provides two graphs, aligned in time, depicting the computational load of the GUI. These results have been taken again for the largest scenario analysed. Graph 9.11a shows the percentage of CPU used in the machine where the GUI is deployed. After

rendering the topology, the GUI stabilised at around 20% of CPU usage. Graph 9.11b shows the total amount of memory used along the whole process of receiving and render the topology. The memory stabilised at around 670 MiB when the topology has been rendered. This is a clear demonstration of the scalability of the proposed architecture.

There are two important moments in the graphs plotted in Fig. 9.11. The first one is at the beginning, where the GUI was receiving the topological information and the second one is at second 115 approximately where the GUI started receiving the information from LMA about the layout positions and when the GUI started rendering the topology.

9.7.5 Scalability Results

This section performs a scalability test of the 5GTopoNet architecture to analyse how much complexity in the topologies can be handled by the proposed approach. To this end, an emulator of the JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) interface reported by *RIA*, *TIM* and *MA* has been created to be able to scale up the managed infrastructure far beyond the current infrastructure available in our premises. It has been used to emulate the behaviour of a significant number of *RIA* components as if they were deployed in each of the emulated physical and virtual machines of the topology to analyse how the architecture behaves under stressed conditions.

Property	Min value	Max value	Function
Number of <i>UE</i> x <i>DU</i>	1	64	$\sum_{i=0}^6 2^i$
Number of <i>DU</i> x <i>Edge</i>	2	2	$CONST(2)$
Number of <i>Tenants</i> x <i>Edge</i>	4	4	$CONST(4)$
Number of <i>Edge</i>	1	256	$\sum_{i=0}^8 2^i$
Number of <i>Servers</i> x <i>Tenant</i>	1	1	$CONST(1)$
Number of <i>Tenants</i> x <i>Core</i>	4	4	$CONST(4)$
Number of <i>Core</i>	1	64	$\sum_{i=1}^6 2^i$

Table 9.3 Ranging of generated scenarios for empirical validation experiments

Table 9.3 shows how the complexity of the topology was ranged, using an exponential incremental step in complexity and a fixed value respectively. The tests ranged the number

of UE devices connected to each DU, the number of Edge locations and the number of computers available in the Core network, since these are the key aspects of a 5G MEC infrastructure, thereby allowing a realistic analysis of the usability in these scenarios. The number of tenants, DUs available in each of the Edge locations, the number of servers in each of the Edge and the number of servers connected to each of the Core computers were fixed for simplicity. Scenarios were ranged up to $37,328 (256 + 256 * 4 + 256 * 2 + 256 * 2 * 64) + (64 + 64 * 4 + 64 * 4 * 1) + (3344 \text{ from other devices})$ devices and 74,656 connections (two connections per device in average), for the most complex scenario analysed, constituting a very realistic topological size for a small city scale.

Fig. 9.12 Sequence diagram of the experiment setup

Fig. 9.12 depicts a sequence diagram of the scalability results to understand how times were gathered. Experiment Controller is a script that started all the components from a cool start, and the topology information (JSON) was sent in chunks at regular intervals (1 sec). Then LMA and GUI received such information. LMA then recalculated the layout on every reception and when the layout was calculated, it sent the coordinates to the GUI. When the GUI had both coordinates and topological information, the end user e.g., an administrator would be allowed an interactive navigation along the virtual world for troubleshooting and other purposes.

Fig. 9.13 5GTopoNet performance GUI- completed drawn time for each scenario

Fig. 9.13 shows how 5GTopoNet behaved when the complexity of the topology to be discovered was exponentially growing in terms of both the number of UE devices and the number of Edges. The scenario depicted had 64 computers in the Core network. The time shown was the time from the arrival of the first JSON file from the RIA (emulator) until the latest device was rendered in the GUI. This is a black-box analysis where the interaction between all the components is not analysed, whilst only the final user perception was taken into consideration. To be precise, the time interval was from the first (3.1) step to the last (3.3) step in Fig. 9.12. Fig. 9.13 plots two different series related to the analysis of the two different business roles: ISP and ISC. For the ISP, as shown, for up to 128 Edges running 32 UE devices or up to 32 Edges running 128 UE devices. 5GTopoNet provided very reasonable results of around 300 seconds, i.e., 5 minutes to converge a network composed by more than 6,992 devices and 13,984 connections to be discovered, positioned in space and rendered. In all the cases, more than 25 Frames Per Second (FPS) were achieved. The same scenarios executed for the ISC provided better performance results of 216 seconds, due to the fact that fewer devices were rendered in the topology, to be precise, 1,477 devices and 2,954 connections. For the most complex scenario analysed, it went out of the scale and thus was

plotted in the sub-figure depicted in Fig. 9.13. This scenario, for the ISP, took 100 minutes to discover and render 37,328 devices with 74,656 connections among them. The same scenario, for the ISC, took almost 10 minutes to discover and render 8,966 devices with 17,932 connections among them. After this initial discovery, the GUI resulted in 4-5 FPS in both business roles, too slow and impracticable to navigate the topology.

Fig. 9.14 5GTopoNet performance LMA- metrics generation time for each scenario

Fig. 9.14 follows a black-box analysis of the LMA component to understand how much LMA contributed to the total times shown in Fig. 9.13. Fig. 9.14 shows a very similar trend with respect to the behaviour of the whole architecture. It is noted that the LMA algorithm is non-deterministic. A total of 10 different executions were conducted. The best and the worst executions were removed to avoid outliers. These results correspond to the averages of the other eight executions. It is worth mentioning that the shapes of both Fig. 9.14 and 9.13 are similar but the time scales are completely different. The acceptable response times was around 100 seconds from the scenarios previously analysed. In the case of the most complex scenario, 328 seconds were required to position the devices and connections in the space. This was the time required to process the spatial layout of the complete infrastructure being discovered.

Fig. 9.15 5GTopoNet performance GUI- the number of elements drawn for each interval of 5 seconds

In order to better understand the limits of the scalability of 5GTopoNet, further tests were executed for the largest topology scenario with 128 UE devices, 256 Edges and 64 Cores (37,328 devices with 74,656 connections). Then, a white-box approach was taken for the understanding of the behaviour of the GUI, which is the component that contributes more to the time required to deal with the scalability of the system. To this end, Fig. 9.15 shows, at 5-second intervals, how many elements the GUI was able to draw at each interval for this scenario. It is noted that this representation allows measuring the performance of the GUI along the time when the level of stress was progressively increased. The figure shows how the performance of the system was dropping with the number of rendered objects in the screen was increased. This dropping arrived to an inflexion point (see A) in Fig. 9.15 where the degraded performance was then maintained regardless of the size and complexity of the number of objects being rendered on screen. This point A in Fig. 9.15 represents the case where there were around 60 devices every 5 seconds, and thus at 1,800 seconds, there were around 35,000 devices with their respective connections. This is the scalability boundary of the proposed architecture.

Fig. 9.16 5GTopoNet GUI screenshot of a topology with 16 UE devices per Edge, 16 Edges and 16 Cores

In order to allow understanding the complexity and the shape of the topologies being discovered and rendered in 5GTopoNet, Fig. 9.16 shows a screenshot of one of the mid-sized topologies executed in the previous scalability tests. It displays a scenario featured with 512 UE devices connected to 32 different DUs that were located in 16 different Edges, 64 different computers allocated in the Core network, and 64 servers deployed to cross different administrative domains. As shown in the figure, the complexity is far beyond the understanding of a human being. Therefore, key tools to navigate that complexity and aid administrators to fulfil their tasks are critical for the reduction in both capital and operating costs associated with network administration. This scenario is composed of 2,576 devices and 5,152 connections among them, and it took 67 seconds to discover and render this highly complex topology.

9.8 Conclusions

A novel architecture for the discovery of network topologies suitable for the novel 5G multi-tenant MEC architecture has been presented and validated. The architecture provides significant innovation beyond the state of the art, by allowing discovering not only physical infrastructures but also logical infrastructures that cannot be seen by humans directly for troubleshooting and other network management tasks. It provides a suitable alignment of the data models of ISP and ISC, enabling an enhanced level of flexibility by providing support to the vast majority of business models available in this kind of infrastructures. The prototype has been validated over a real 5G multi-tenant MEC infrastructure where complex physical and virtual data paths were discovered and rendered, and users were enabled to navigate them to perform troubleshooting. The architecture has been proven to work with up to 37k devices, discovered and displayed in 5 minutes when everything runs in a simple desktop computer. This is the level of scalability required for a small city scale, and thus the scalability performance is advantageous. The benefits achieved by using the 3D space to deal with the complexity of the topology has been significant, allowing end-users to understand, at a glance, where a VM is located, what tenant it belongs to, how a 5G user is moving across antennas, what is the concrete data path available in the infrastructure and so on.

For future work, it is planned to provide metrics on each device and interface. It is also planned to include real-time flow monitoring. It will transform the current framework into a large-scale 3D monitoring tool. Moreover, to improve the scalability, by dealing with the group of devices together, with the ambition to achieve more than 10 millions of devices discovered, monitored and rendered on the screen and users being able to understand these levels of complexity. Finally, it is also planned to use the tool as a debugger of the autonomic actions that are conducted by a cognitive pipeline where the management of the infrastructure is performed without any human intervention.

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Chapter 10

Advanced Spatial Network Metrics for Cognitive Management of 5G Networks

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10.1 Abstract

The emerging Fifth-Generation (5G) mobile networks are empowered by softwarization and programmability, leading to the huge potentials of unprecedented flexibility and capability in cognitive network management such as self-reconfiguration and self-optimization. To help unlock such potentials, this paper proposes a novel framework that is able to monitor and calculate 5G network topological information in terms of advanced spatial metrics. These metrics, together with enabling and optimization algorithms, are purposely designed to address the complexity of 5G network topologies introduced by network virtualization and infrastructure sharing among operators (multi-tenancy). Consequently, this new framework, centred on a Topology Monitoring Agent (TMA), enables on-demand 5G networks' spatial knowledge and topological awareness required by 5G cognitive network management in making smart decisions in various autonomous network management tasks including but not limited to Virtual Network Function (VNF) placement strategies. The paper describes several technical use cases enabled by the proposed framework, including Proactive cache allocation, Computation offloading, Node overloading alerting, and Load balancing. Finally, a realistic 5G testbed is deployed with the central component TMA, together with the new spatial metrics and associated algorithms, implemented. Experimental results empirically validate the proposed approach and demonstrate the scalability and performance of the TMA component.

10.2 Introduction

Network management in the forthcoming Fifth-Generation (5G) mobile networks is notably influenced by the softwarization of network infrastructures where several hardware components are virtualized and by the multi-tenancy of the network infrastructures where hardware components are shared by different mobile operators. The main motivation of these 5G capabilities is the reduction of both capital and operational costs. 5G Virtual Network Functions (VNFs) can now be deployed automatically and on-demand on the Edge and the Core segments of the 5G network and can be migrated between the computers that belong to

the same network segment or across network segments as required. These characteristics, along with the mobility of 5G users across the different antennas of 5G networks, make 5G network topologies highly dynamic and dependent of the status of the network and the dynamics of the human behaviour. This complicates the optimal management of resources and services in the 5G networks.

Unlike previous 3G/4G networks, the dynamic nature of the novel 5G topologies imposes continuous decisions about the concrete location where to perform VNF placements and migrations to maximize the effectiveness of the services delivered by such VNFs (e.g., cache, load balancer, and baseband unit). For example, a cache service will reduce bandwidth consumption in the network links located after such a cache service due to the hits into the cached content, and will reduce the latency in the delivery of cached content to the final users. Thus, the placement strategy of such a cache service will play a vital role in deciding where is the current most effective location to maximize latency reduction and to minimize bandwidth consumption.

A way to address the placement strategy of services in 5G networks is to make use of spatial network metrics to identify critical locations in the 5G network topology, represented as evolving graphs with hardware and software resources. Spatial network metrics are indices that provide insights about the centrality of the vertices of a graph and can be interpreted as a level of effectiveness of a given resource due to the spatial location with respect to the whole topological structure of the network.

Spatial network metrics can be combined with other key 5G performance metrics to create composed metrics used to enhance the dynamic placement of services. A cognitive network management framework that monitors, calculates and aggregates in real-time such metrics, can make use of them to perform autonomous decisions, such as dynamic VNF placements, load balancing, caching, network communication dynamics and VNF migration, among others.

In this research work, we present a new cognitive network management framework, focusing on topology monitoring based on new spatial metrics in 5G networks. There are several use cases that can benefit from our cognitive framework. For instance, composed

spatial metrics can be used to infer the optimal placement for key 5G architectural components such as CU, DU or UPF for providing support to different 5G use cases such as Ultra-Reliable and Low-Latency Communications (URLLC) and Enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB) where latency and throughput need to be minimized or maximized, respectively. Massive Machine Type Communications (mMTC) refer to Internet of Things (IoT) networks where millions of 5G devices create complex topologies and where IoT services can be offloaded to the MEC platform, to perform computation offloading of the resource-constrained IoT devices to the network edges, thereby overcoming the resource constraints and achieving energy consumption reduction in the IoT devices. Spatial metrics can help determine the closest geographical areas to perform such offloading. Analogously, the optimal placement of caches and load balancers in the network will further enhance the effectiveness of such uses cases. In case the reader is interested, [16] provide a comprehensive description of the 5G architecture and its components.

Recent research work such as [82] [83] rely on diverse performance metrics to trigger autonomous behaviours in the cognitive network management framework according to the current status of the network. These metrics encompass resource metrics (e.g., memory, disk, CPU), network metrics (e.g., throughput, latency, delay, capacity), wireless metrics (e.g., Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI), and Received Signal Code Power (RSCP)) and service metrics (e.g., cost, revenue, request/second). However, 5G cognitive management frameworks should consider not only those traditional performance and capacity metrics, as it has been studied so far, but also spatial network metrics that can empower the cognitive network management framework to make more meaningful management decisions by leveraging the spatial context-awareness in determining optimal operation locations. To the best of our knowledge, there is not yet any framework able to calculate or make use of 5G spatial network metrics combined with traditional ones to make valuable network management decisions. A cause that has contributed to this lack of support has been the complexity associated to the calculation of this type of metrics, which increases exponentially according to the size of the topology, and thus it is impractical, even for small topologies

(hundreds of devices), to calculate these metrics in a useful time scale, i.e. seconds, to enable real-time cognitive network monitoring and management.

This research work demonstrates how spatial network metrics can be monitored and calculated for large-scale 5G topologies, and how they can be combined with traditional performance metrics to serve as an enabler for our 5G cognitive management framework, to make valuable decisions that optimize the allocation and management of 5G VNFs and traffic. Specifically, our new composed spatial metrics would allow higher 5G network resources utilization efficiency, reduced latency, increased availability, optimal VNF allocation, migrations of VNFs, balancing the network traffic, and balancing the computational load among edge nodes. Nonetheless, the computation of spatial metrics on 5G network topology with millions of resources (switches, physical machines, virtual machines, users, etc.), is challenging. To meet this challenge, we propose an efficient 5G TMA to quantify those new spatial metrics. This agent has been significantly optimized over the traditional ways to calculate spatial centrality metrics in graphs. Our TMA makes computationally feasible the on-demand quantification of combined 5G metrics in large topologies with hundreds of thousands of nodes.

The contributions of this paper are manifold:

- This paper defines a new 5G cognitive network management framework for continuous monitoring and calculating spatial metrics in 5G networks.
- The paper proposes new 5G-tailored, efficient and scalable spatial network metrics over evolving 5G network topologies to meet 5G multi-tenant and virtualized networking requirements.
- The paper proposes new composed metrics useful for the cognitive management framework to make allocations decisions such as cache allocation, load balancing, function computation offloading in 5G networks.
- Finally, the proposed approach has been successfully designed, implemented and deployed in a realistic 5G testbed. The paper demonstrates the feasibility and scalability through empirical performance evaluation in this testbed.

The rest of this paper is structured as follows. Section 2 reviews related work. Section 3 introduces the 5G cognitive network management framework. Section 4 delves into the design of the novel 5G spatial metrics, followed by Section 5, which describes concrete use cases for the usage of the proposed metrics. Section 6 describes the most relevant implementation details of the proposed framework focusing on the TMA. Subsequently, section 7 is devoted to the performance evaluation in a realistic 5G testbed. Finally, section 8 concludes the paper highlighting the main achievements.

10.3 Related Work

	Exploits Spatial Information	Applies Closeness Centrality	Metric Based	Optimized for 5G Topologies	Scalable Solution
[52]	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗
[48]	✓	✗	✓	✗	✗
[49]	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗
[50]	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗
[62]	✗	✗	✓	✓	✗
[53] and [54]	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗
[55]	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗
[58]	✓	✗	✓	✓	✗
[51]	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗
[56]	✓	✗	✓	✗	✗
[13]	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗
[14]	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗
[57]	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗
[84]	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗
Our Contribution	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Table 10.1 Analysis of the state of the art with respect to our contribution against the challenges required to achieve Advanced Spatial Network Metrics for 5G Cognitive Network Management

Table 10.1 provides a comparative analysis of the current state of the art against the challenges proposed in this research work and how our contribution compares with them to allow the reader to clearly identify our contribution. Each column in the table is a key enabler to achieve the proposed challenges.

Spatial network metrics such as Closeness Centrality proposed in [45] and Betweenness Centrality in [46] can identify influential nodes in a graph, but, as it is known, they are difficult

to be applied in large-scale networks due to the computational complexity as reported by [47], even more in evolved graphs such as those resultant of 5G monitored networks as the algorithm runs in $O(n^2)$ time.

Calculating centrality metrics over large graphs is a challenging problem. The problem of efficiency in centrality metrics calculation has been studied in the past and recently. [52] propose a scalable algorithm for betweenness centrality in large graphs using MapReduce, that scales by adding more compute nodes. Even with this kind of parallelization optimization, it might take 10^5 seconds with a 100k graph size, which makes this unfeasible for 5G network real-time management. Therefore, in our approach, instead of betweenness centrality, we leverage closeness centrality metric, that provides similar insights about network graphs, but with less complexity time $O(nm)$ to make practicable real-time and online network management.

In [48], the authors present a Routing Betweenness Centrality metric for communication networks, by considering network flows created by arbitrary loop-free routing strategies, where routing decisions depend on the packet target alone and considering the source-target of the packet.

In [49], the proposed scheme relies on centralness index to calculate the best placement of access points for vehicular networks, or to deploy Road Side Unit (RSU) proposed in [50]. However, in both cases, the results are based on simulation environments and they considered small network topologies (20-200 nodes) that are not actually affected by the complexity of spatial metrics.

[62] propose an optimization algorithm of DU placement optimization in 5G for Cloud-based Radio Access Networks (C-RAN), considering diverse network metrics such as traffic requests, fiber per link, fronthaul latency, network metrics, but they do not consider centrality metrics.

In [53] and [54], the authors analyze the spatial structure of networks to perform effectively a proactive caching in 5G small cells networks. Unfortunately, they do not deal with large-scale graphs and do not consider optimal centralness indexes to maintain up-to-date metrics in the evolving 5G graphs.

The work in [55] resorts to spatial network metrics to calculate influence nodes to serve as content-centric mobile 5G networks. However, again, they focus their experiments on small network graphs (85 nodes).

[58] propose a "Caching-as-a-Service" (CaaS) for 5G, either cloud-based radio access networks and virtualized Evolved Packet Core (EPC). They discuss the allocation performance evaluation according to diverse metrics, but they just mention the possible usage of shortest path betweenness centrality as a potential metric, without delving into details.

Recently, [51] study the optimal placement of cloudlets in IoT access points (MEC nodes) for access delay minimization in large scale IoT networks. Their fitness function considers several attributes, including the evaluation of closeness centrality of the access points. However, they have validated the approach in a simulated environment with only 1000 IoT devices and 40 access points.

Network metrics aggregation and composition are still not being broadly adopted in currently available monitoring tools, even less on inter-domain and complex communications networks. In this regard, some software implementations such as [56] allow metric composition considering intra-domain performance measurements in communications networks. They analyse metrics for quantifying end-to-end minimum-mean delay in spatial composition, but they do not consider spatial centrality metrics. Indeed, given the current state of the art surveyed in [13] and [14], there is not any implemented model or monitoring tool for computing aggregated spatial metrics for 5G networks, and they focus only on network metrics such as end-to-end latency, last-mile latency, latency-under-load, mean latency, end-to-end packet loss or jitter, upstream-downstream throughput-goodput, network availability, etc.

Similarly, the work in [57] leads to a routing algorithm for SDN, evaluated at small-scale, that considers Centrality in the weight functions to prevent the bottleneck in the multicast routing and choose the nodes or links that can balance the loads across the network.

Spatial metrics can be used to enrich the graphical representation of network topologies, thereby helping on human-centric network management, where administrators can directly govern the network resources and flows.

In [84], the authors discuss the usage of centrality indexes for control algorithms in communications networks, including allocation capacities, design and dynamic control of physical/virtual network topologies.

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first proposal of monitoring and calculate efficient and optimized spatial centrality metrics, used as a baseline for cognitive management at the scale of evolving 5G networks.

10.4 Cognitive 5G Network Management Framework

Fig. 10.1 5G Cognitive Management Framework

Figure 10.1 introduces the 5G multi-tenant network deployment and the proposed cognitive management framework to manage such networks, according to the contextual information, including our proposed spatial metrics to be defined in Section 10.5. The following subsections provide details of the framework.

10.4.1 5G Multi-Tenant Network

The bottom part of Figure 10.1 depicts the deployment of a 5G multi-tenant network where both physical and virtual layers are presented. The physical layer is composed of the hardware available in the infrastructure. The antennas provide coverage to the 5G users to gain radio access to the network. These antennas are connected by means of the front-haul to a DU. A DU controls the new 5G radio interface, sending the radio signals through the mid-haul network segment to the edge of the network. The edge is the closest location where a VNF can be deployed close to the final users, in order to achieve computational off-loading and low-latency capabilities. Usually, a CU can be deployed in this network segment to do not insert delays in the control of the radio interface, to allow quick handovers. The edges of the network are connected by means of the back-haul to the core network where the main 5G VNF Core services are deployed. The UPF VNF is the mobile anchor where all the mobile traffic is received to get access to the Internet. In the control plane, An AMF VNF provides mobile equipment authentication, authorization and mobility management. A SMF VNF is responsible for session management and allocates IP addresses to UE devices. It is noted how all the different 5G architectural components are virtualized with the only exception of the DU and that multiple instances of such components are instantiated inside the same physical machine in multi-tenancy scenarios. The Core network is finally connected to the Internet through the backbone network segment.

In production-ready deployments, the idea is to maximize the number of 5G subscribers that can be supported with the minimal set of hardware resources while providing the expected quality of service.

10.4.2 5G Cognitive Management Framework

The upper part of Figure 10.1 illustrates the 5G cognitive management framework proposed. The architecture has been aligned with the H2020 5G SliceNet project, which is a high-profile EU project on cognitive network management for 5G networks and whose consortium comprises 16 partners including leading telecommunication operators, vendors and other 5G

stakeholders. The 5G multi-tenant network has been instrumented with sensors, actuators and discovery agents in order to enable the management of the infrastructure. They are depicted in the Control layer of Figure 10.1. The sensors provide metrics to the management framework. The discovery agents provide topological information about the 5G multi-tenant infrastructure. The actuators are in charge of controlling resources, communications and services of the infrastructure.

The autonomic layer depicted in Figure 10.1 contains all the components that provide cognitive management capabilities. First, the monitoring component collects both topological information and sensed metrics to make them homogeneous and processable over a common format. The aggregator component produces composed metrics that are defined as a temporal or spatial aggregation of the elemental metrics sensed. The analyzer component is in charge of identifying alerts in the 5G network. An alert is an alarm that requires attention by the administrator. A sub-optimal device configuration, hardware failure or bad configuration in devices or services or an external attack are good examples of alerts. The analyzer correlates the information received from the monitoring component in order to determine existing or emerging issues. The policy framework component then performs decisions about actions to deal with such alerts. This decision is an implementation plan that indicates how to overcome the issues expressed in the alerts. The orchestrator component is in charge of executing, step by step, in an orderly manner the plan provided by the policy framework. This plan is executed by interacting with actuators and VNF Management. The architecture is fully aligned with the ETSI NFV Management and Orchestration (MANO) architecture. The VNF Manager deals with the life cycle and controls services, whilst the Virtual Infrastructure Manager (VIM) manages the life cycle of virtual resources in a multi-tenant environment.

This architecture enables a closed control loop where the system can react autonomously through executing a mitigation plan against several alerts that have been defined in the system without any human intervention. Finally, the SliceNet one-stop Application Program Interface (API) allows onboarding new autonomic capabilities and controlling the exposure of information to the final users about the status of the network, among others.

10.4.3 Monitoring and Discovery of 5G Network Topologies

Fig. 10.2 Continuous 5G Monitoring and Discovery Framework

Figure 10.2 shows a detailed description of the part of the cognitive management plane dealing with monitoring and topology discovery. This is a zoom of the components under the dotted square labelled as A in Figure 10.1. On the topology discovery side, our architecture proposes the following three components to provide updated information about the topology.

- The *Physical Topology Agent (PTA)* relies on traditional technologies such as the SNMP to provide information about the physical topology of the 5G network. There is only one PTA deployed in the infrastructure. This component performs a periodic SNMP walk from different entry points defined by the administrator. This SNMP walk interrogates recursively the status of the LLDP learned neighbours of each node and then their neighbours.
- The *Multi-Tenant Topology Agent (MTTA)* utilizes the cloud stack APIs to retrieve information about the virtual topologies available in the 5G network and about the tenants that own such topologies. To this end, some key management APIs such as OpenStack and Kubernetes have been integrated. It retrieves periodically the list of containers and virtual machine allocated in each physical machine in order to

generate the virtual topological information. There is only one MTTA deployed in the infrastructure.

- The *5G-Topology Agent (5G-TA)* provides information about the attachment of the 5G mobile users to the specific 5G DUs and keeps tracking the user mobility across antennas. To achieve this, it has been integrated with the control plane of both 4G and 5G networks by retrieving such information from the 4G MME and 5G AMF/SMF, respectively. To be concrete, this integration has been performed by creating an ad-hoc API in the MME implementation of the Mosaic 5G project as described by [85]. [86] provide a comprehensive explanation of this API.

These three monitoring components pull topological information from the infrastructure at periodic intervals. This periodic interrogation is used to maintain in memory the updated network topology. Then, they only report the topological information when there are changes with respect to the previously reported state to deliver only the topological changes. The three components report the topological information using a common topological model to a common message bus. The key is the separation of responsibilities of each of the components with respect to the devices being reported by them. To be concrete, the PTA reports on physical devices and their connections, including switches, routers, and DUs. The MTTA reports on virtual machines and containers and their connections with the physical machines. And finally, the 5G-TA reports on UE devices and their connection to the DUs.

On the sensing side, our architecture employs four components. Firstly, the following three provide performance metrics about resources, flows and operating system processes (services) respectively.

- The *Resource Monitoring Agent (RMA)* reports metrics about the following: i) the physical device where it is installed, such as CPU Usage, Memory Size, Memory I/O, Disk Size, Disk I/O, Cache faults, and kWatt/Hour; ii) the virtual machines allocated in such physical machine, such as Memory I/O, Disk I/O, and Memory Used; iii) both physical and virtual network interfaces, such as Bandwidth Consumed, Bandwidth

Capacity or Bandwidth Negotiated. This component is installed in each physical machine of the 5G infrastructure.

- The *Flow Monitoring Agent (FMA)* reports metrics about the flows of the interfaces that are being monitored. These metrics include Experienced Data Rate (Downlink), Experienced Data Rate (Uplink), Area Traffic Capacity (Downlink), Area Traffic Capacity (Uplink), Overall User Density and End-to-End Latency. This component is installed in each physical machine of the 5G infrastructure.
- The *Process Monitoring Agent (PMA)* is installed in each physical machine of the 5G infrastructure. It reports metrics about each of the services/processes that are running in such machines. These metrics include process I/O, memory I/O, disk I/O, context switches, sleep time, idle time, and so on.

In addition, a *Topology Monitoring Agent (TMA)* is proposed as the cornerstone component of the monitoring framework. It is in charge of computing in real-time the 5G spatial metrics (defined later in the next section, Section 10.5), according to both sensing and topological information. Unlike the rest of the sensor's components, the TMA receives both topological information from all the topology discovery sensors and metrics from the other sensing components as inputs. The TMA keeps the 5G topology updated in a graph structure using the add/remove primitives described in the next section. The TMA performs periodic calculation of the 5G spatial metrics. The calculation of the spatial metrics is detailed in the next section and it may require the usage of performance metrics, and this is the reason why this component also receives such information. The TMA computes dynamically diverse metrics over the 5G network, which is represented as an evolving graph. The graph changes continuously according to the reports coming from the topology discovery sensors. The framework computes continuously the metrics for each node, as the nodes and resources evolve along the time. Then, it provides periodic reports of the spatial metrics associated with such nodes of the 5G topology. Those metrics are then exploited by the cognitive layer of the framework to make advanced context-aware decisions for 5G network management.

Both the spatial and performance metrics are received by the aggregator, which is able to compute composed metrics based on spatial or temporal aggregation of the elemental metrics. Thus, the aggregator combines diverse network metrics, resource metrics, and topology information, along with spatial metrics, to come up with complex 5G spatial network metrics. Such composed metrics are also reported back again to allow the cognitive system to utilize them.

10.5 Spatial 5G Closeness Centrality Network Metric

All the segments of the 5G network including Radio Access Network (RAN), Edge, Core network as well as mobile users are continuously monitored by the topology discovery sensors, which allow modelling dynamically the 5G network as a connected directed graph $G = (N, E)$, consisting of a set N nodes or vertices, corresponding to the 5G network devices, and set E of edges corresponding to the network connections between devices.

Our graph G changes continuously as the 5G network evolves, considering physical devices holding virtual network functions (VNFs), and their connections. The network links are directed edges with associated metrics, which are calculated continuously and reported by the sensing components per node, such as for instance, latency $l(v, v')$, bandwidth utilized $b(v, v')$ and bandwidth available $ba(v, v')$.

Figure 10.3 represents graphically the graph of the 5G network topology, where nodes N are represented in circles and edges E are represented in lines. As explained in 10.4.1, UE represents the users mobile terminal, DU and CU represent Distributed Units and Centralized Units, respectively. It is noted that some nodes have a "v" prefix, representing that this is a virtual machine where such a service is running. The VNFs are the set of Virtual Network Functions deployed in the 5G network to perform computational off-loading to the edges. The vSMF, vAMF, vPCF, vUDM, vAUSF are all the architectural components of the 5G network running in virtualized machines. In the figure, nodes with heptagonal shape represent Physical Machines P located in both the Edge and the Core Networks that are potential candidates for deploying Virtual Machines V for implementing virtual network

functions. Thus, $V = \{v \in N \mid v.type == VirtualMachine\}$ and $P = \{p \in N \mid p.type == PhysicalMachine\}$.

Fig. 10.3 5G Network Graph representation

Spatial networks metrics rely on networks graphs, obtained dynamically from the topology discovery agents to calculate meaningful information that is ultimately used by the cognitive network management framework to make wise control decisions to manage the 5G network. However, the current state of the art in sensing tools, topology discovery tools, and inventory systems are not yet capable of providing spatial network metrics of 5G multi-tenant infrastructure. So far, 4G networks did not have to deal with virtualization of the network functions and the multi-tenancy capabilities needed to enable concurrent operations over the 5G infrastructure. These 5G characteristics combined with the dense deployments foreseen in 5G networks where thousands of UEs can be connected to the same DU lead to an explosion of the number of nodes (physical/virtualized and 5G users) and their connections in the network topology.

It can result in topologies with hundreds of thousands of Vertices and Edges, which makes the management of 5G network topology graphs impracticable, above all when computing those metrics in real-time and considering the whole 5G Network topology.

Certain network management decisions require the whole network picture to make valuable decisions, for instance, allocation of caches functions in a proper MEC node depends on the number of connected nodes (including users) and their spatial locations and demands. The load balancing function allocation is also influenced by the combination of the current flows, and spatial network representation, since such a network function should be allocated on-demand wisely in central and strategic locations to perform balancing to the network traffic wherever and whenever is needed.

10.5.1 Tailored Spatial Metric for Multi-Tenant 5G Networks

Our tailored spatial metric for multi-tenant 5G network features several optimizations over traditional spatial metrics based on centrality. Such optimizations make the calculation of the metrics treatable and computationally feasible for real-time management of the 5G network.

$$CC(v) = \frac{1}{\sum_{n \in N} d_G(v, n)} \quad (10.1)$$

Our proposal extends and adapts the Closeness Centrality metric by [45], defined as how close a node is to all the other nodes of the network. Nodes are more central as they are closer to the majority of the other nodes. Closeness Centrality ($CC(v)$) is mathematically defined in Equation 10.1, where $d_G(v, n)$ is the function that calculates the distance of the shortest path from node v to node n in the Graph G . This distance is the minimum length of any path between both nodes in the graph. Being the path the sequence of vertices and edges beginning in v and ending in n , where each edge connects its previous with its subsequent vertex. The distance is the sum of the weights of its edges, where the weight measures the strength of a link. In our case, the weight will be embodied by additional 5G network performance metrics calculated by our sensing components, such as latency or bandwidth, depending on the specific use case being addressed (e.g. cache allocation, load balancing, computation offloading, etc. as shown in the next section). The distance function requires an algorithm supporting weighted graphs able to calculate the shortest-path to other vertices, such as Dijkstra's algorithm, which runs in time $O(m + n \log n)$ (being m the number of edges

and n the number of nodes) and as a result, the complexity of traditional Closeness Centrality ([45]) is defined as $O(nm + n^2 \log n)$.

Our newly proposed 5G Closeness Centrality (5GCC) metric, presented in the following subsections, performs two main optimizations over the traditional way of calculating closeness centrality in a whole graph: node selection optimization which defined the set x as a subset of N as nodes to calculate the metric ($O(xm + xn \log n)$ where $x < n$). This complexity is further reduced by the node prune optimization which decreases the set of destination nodes y , defined as a significantly reduced subset of N , leading to a decreased complexity when calculating the shortest path defined as $O(xm + xy \log y)$ where $y < n$.

Node selection optimization

This optimization aims to create a subset of nodes $P = \{p \in N \mid p.type == PhysicalServer\}$ which includes only those nodes that are subject to serve as possible candidates v to allocate VNFs, i.e. only physical nodes p in the graph $G(N, E)$ will be considered for calculating their $CC(v)$. It significantly reduces the number of nodes v required to calculate the $5GCC(v)$, and therefore the number of pairs to which quantifying the distance functions $d_G(v, n)$, and consequently the weighted shortest-paths. It should be noted that reducing the number of nodes needed for calculating the $5GCC(v)$ does not imply reducing the number of target vertexes n of the distance function $d_G(v, n)$ that will still consider the whole Graph $G(N, E)$. Therefore, it requires calculating the shortest path between the candidate physical node v to every single node n in the graph (either physical, virtual or mobile-UE nodes).

Node prune optimization

The second optimization is the pruning of the leaves nodes of the 5G graph, i.e. the user mobiles attached to DU nodes while maintaining the same resultant closeness centrality index values when computing $CC(v)$ for each $n \in P$. This optimization reduces significantly the number of nodes in the graph, as the mobiles represent the vast majority of nodes in the 5G network topology. It minimizes the time needed to quantify the distance function $d_G(v, n)$ (which implies quantifying the shortest-path).

$$\begin{aligned}
D &= \{d \in N \mid d.type \neq Ue \text{ AND } d.type \neq Du\}, \\
R &= \{r \in N \mid r.type == Du\}
\end{aligned}
\tag{10.2}$$

$$5GCC(v) = \frac{1}{\sum_{d \in D} d_G(v, d) + \sum_{r \in R} 5Gd_G(v, r)}$$

Thus, our 5G Closeness Centrality metric, defined in Equation 10.2, splits the closeness centrality quantification in two spaces. For those 5G nodes n in set D , which are not part of UE mobiles or DU sets, it computes the distance function as it is done traditionally in $CC(v)$ metric, i.e. using function $d_G(v, n)$, whereas for those nodes r of type DU (set R), the distance is calculated with our new function $5Gd_G(v, r)$ defined in Algorithm 2.

Function $5Gd_G(v, r)$ requires two structures that are kept in cache memory. The first one $UEInDu(DU)$ holds up-to-date the actual UE mobiles belonging to each DU. The second one $UEsWeightInDu(DU)$ maintains the sum of the weights for each edge connected to the DU. These two structures are needed to allow the system to get the shortest path to every UE. Basically, when the shortest path to a DU is calculated from a node n , the shortest path from this node n to every UE connected to this DU is the same plus the additional weight for every UE connected to the DU. These structures are managed by our topology manager that performs the network graph management and quantifies the metrics, adding and removing continuously the nodes in these structures and in the graph, as the 5G network evolves.

Data: $G(N, E)$, $UEInDu(DU)$, $UEsWeightInDu(DU)$

```

1 Function  $5Gd_G(v, r)$ :
2    $out \leftarrow 0$ ;
3    $duPathWeight \leftarrow d_G(v, r)$ ;
4    $mobilesPath \leftarrow duPathWeight * UEInDu[r] + UEsWeightInDu[r]$ ;
5    $out \leftarrow out + duPathWeight + mobilesPath$ ;
6   return  $out$ ;
7 End Function

```

Algorithm 2: 5G distance function

As can be seen the function $5Gd_G(v, r)$ defined in Algorithm 2, adds to the total summation of $d_G(v, r)$, the weights from the DU towards each UE connected, taking those weights from the $UEsWeightInDu$ structure.

As a result, our 5GCC metric, using as baseline $CC(v)$, and after applying the optimizations, is defined in Algorithm 3. This algorithm requires access to the whole graph $G(N, E)$. Also, it requires access to a set of Physical Servers (PS) containing the candidate nodes selected to calculate their 5G Closeness Centrality. The set of all DUs used in the calculation of the shortest path for the optimized 5GCC. UE set comprises the UEs available in the graph. And finally, a set D containing the rest of destination nodes in the graph for which the shortest path to them must be calculated. The algorithm returns the vector with the 5G Closeness Centrality values for each node that is worth calculating the 5G spatial metrics, i.e. those physical nodes that might allocate a VNF.

Data: $G(N, E)$, $PS = \{ps \in N \mid ps.type == PhysicalServer\}$,
 $DU = \{du \in N \mid du.type == Du\}$, $UE = \{ue \in N \mid ue.type == Ue\}$,
 $D = \{d \in N \mid d \notin UE \text{ AND } d \notin DU\}$

Result: $5GCC[]$

```

1 for  $ps \in PS$  do
2    $out \leftarrow 0$ ;
3   for  $du \in DU$  do
4      $out \leftarrow out + 5Gd_G(ps, du)$ ;
5   end
6   for  $d \in D$  do
7      $out \leftarrow out + d_G(ps, d)$ ;
8   end
9    $5GCC[ps] \leftarrow \frac{1}{out}$ ;
10 end
11 return  $5GCC[]$ ;

```

Algorithm 3: 5G Closeness Centrality algorithm.

10.5.2 5G Network Graph Management

5G networks are subject to continuous topology changes that require autonomous and dynamic management of the associated evolving network graph. The topology changes are

motivated by different factors. On one hand, due to 5G mobility, users are continuously performing handovers from one DU to another. Besides, UE devices are continuously connecting/disconnecting from the network, e.g. user devices restart or simply lose their coverage. These kind of changes are minimal for the topology but sufficient to force a recalculation of the closeness centrality in the whole graph. On the other hand, the virtualization and on-demand provisioning of VNFs lead to continuous and dynamic changes in the network topology beyond the leaves nodes in the graph, that requires recalculating our 5GCC indexes, as this quantification depends on the overall status of the graph. This section defines the procedure followed by our topology manager to maintain in real-time the graph and associated structures, as well as calculate efficiently the 5GCC metrics.

Add and remove nodes/edges in 5G graph

The 5GCC is calculated by the TMA of the framework, updating the 5G graph according to those dynamic changes, and recalculating the 5GCC for each node in the graph. To this aim, it relies on two main functions defined in Algorithm 4.

The *addEdge()* function updates the graph when a new connection whose source (or destination) is a physical or virtual 5G node. However, when the change is minor, i.e. a connection related to a UE node has been added, it only updates the cache structures *UEInDu* and *UEsWeightInDu*. The *addNode()* function basically adds the node in the graph, but only if it is not UE, thereby avoiding changes that might trigger a recalculation of the 5GCC in the whole 5G graph. The *removeNode()* and *removeEdge()* functions are intended to detach the UE from a DU in the event of a handover or disconnection, and they are defined in a similar way as the add ones, but subtracting the weights from the *UEsWeightInDu* and removing the node and edges whenever necessary in the graph (i.e. if it is not UE). When an *addEdge* implies any node beyond UE devices, then it triggers the execution of Algorithm 3.

10.5.3 5GCC retrieval optimization

This optimization is intended to minimize the number of times needed to recalculate the entire 5GCC when a topology change is produced in the 5G network. To this aim, we exploit

```

Data:  $G(N, E), UEInDu(DU), UEsWeightInDu(DU)$ 
1 Function addEdge( $e$ ):
2   if ( $e.getSource()=UE$ ) then
3      $UEInDu(e.getDest()) \leftarrow UEInDu(e.getDest()) + 1;$ 
4      $UEsWeightInDu(e.getDest()) \leftarrow$ 
        $UEsWeightInDu(e.getDest()) + e.weight;$ 
5   else
6      $G(N, E) \leftarrow G(N, E) + e;$ 
7   end
8 End Function
9 Function addNode( $n$ ):
10  if ( $n.type \neq UE$ ) then
11     $G(N, E) \leftarrow G(N, E) + n;$ 
12  end
13 End Function

```

Algorithm 4: Graph Management. Add nodes/edges functions

the memory structures presented previously so that when there is only a minor change i.e. a variation related to UE nodes, the 5GCC index for the rest of the nodes does not need to be recalculated entirely as it is traditionally done, which avoids executing fully Algorithm 3.

Thus this optimization avoids computing the shortest-path $d_G(ps, d)$ each time a UE node is added to the graph, reducing to the minimum the complexity to keep up-to-date the 5GCC metric in the entire 5G network topology. Thus, for these cases, which might represent more than 95% of changes in the 5G network, Algorithm 3 is given as input the set D empty, meaning the loop of lines number 6-8, which calculates distance function $d_G(ps, d)$ are not executed. In addition, for this case, we have defined another 5G distance function $5Gd_G^l(v, r)$ similar to the one defined in Algorithm 2, but slightly changed, without code of line number 3, meaning the distance function $d_G(v, r)$ is obtained from another structure *DistanceVR* kept in memory-cache that holds the distance values for each pair physical server and DU. The rest of the function description is kept, where lines 4-5 in Algorithm 2 update the weights, and therefore the resultant 5GCC, according to the added/removed UE in the graph. It is noted that when this function is executed, the *UEsWeightInDu* structure is up-to-date since the add/remove functions managed by the TMA have already updated those structures.

10.5.4 Network Function Placement Optimization based on 5G-Spatial Metrics

When a service request reaches the cognitive management framework, the policy framework component must decide how to allocate optimally certain VNFs in the substrate physical nodes, depending on the service request necessities and the current status of the entire 5G management network, including physical and virtual appliances.

$$\forall p \in P, \forall r \in R_v : \sum_{v \in V_p} C_r^d(v) \leq C_r^a(p) - C_r^s(v') \quad (10.3)$$

We formulate the placement problem as an optimization procedure that starts firstly by checking hard constraints, either, placement constraint (e.g. nodes resource restrictions and current status in terms of computing, memory, etc.), as well as network constraints (e.g. resource's connections bandwidth, latency constraints, or flows). This hard constraints phase ends up with a subset of potential candidates to allocate the VNF, as defined in Equation 10.3, where V_p denotes the subset of V that are already allocated in a physical p machine and R_v is the set of resource requirements for a given node v . Thus, an $r \in R$, might refer, for instance, to resource storage requirement or a memory requirement of the VNF v .

$C_r^d(v)$ refers to the constraint function that gets the requirement value r , deployed d for a given virtual node v . Similarly, $C_r^a(p)$ denotes the constraint function value for that requirement r , currently available a in a given physical node p . Similarly, $C_r^s(v)$ denotes the constraint function value of the requested of the requirement r , of the virtual service s to be allocated, in a given v' virtualized node.

When the inequality is met $\forall r \in R_v$, the node p satisfies the constrains requirements and becomes potential candidate to allocate the VNF in the node v . Thus, the set $PS = \{p_1..p_n\}$ that satisfies the requirements is used as input for Algorithm 3, which calculates the 5GCC for each $p \in PS$.

The objective function for the allocation problem in those candidates depends on the use case being faced by the cognitive framework. In the case of the cache allocation, the

objective function minimizes the latency, selecting less loaded physical edge in the graph, which is closer to the final UE terminals, and at the same time, is central to the maximum number of UE terminals to maximize the number of cache hits.

For this second phase, the 5G spatial metric defined above, combined with the actual network conditions, such as consumed bandwidth or latency retrieved from the FMA, RMA and PMA components of our framework, can help to determine optimally those allocations. The following section delves into complex and novel spatial metrics that combine both our 5GCC metric and other network metrics to address the particular objective of certain 5G use cases.

10.6 Spatial-Based Network Management - 5G Use Cases

This section outlines a number of representative technical 5G use cases, where the proposed spatial metric can be further augmented to create new composed metrics that meet the specific requirements of the services for the purpose of smart 5G network monitoring/management.

10.6.1 Proactive Cache Allocation for 5G Ultra-Reliable and Low-Latency Communication (URLLC)

Content Distribution Networks (CDN) are composed of data center and a set of cache proxy servers deployed in strategic geographic locations to maximize the availability and performance in the network while reducing the latency of the content delivery applications such as video streaming and software downloads. The CDNs can be deployed over the 5G networks, exploiting the capabilities of the 5G infrastructure, thereby deploying on-demand the proxy caches as VNFs in Edge nodes.

The proper place to allocate those virtual caches (vCaches) varies dynamically as the network topology changes due to the user's mobility, and the geographic video demands, among others. Spatial metrics are perfect allies in this scenario to quantify the most influential physical edges to increase the content cache hits, and they can be combined with the actual

end-to-end latency metrics to quantify locations with the lowest latency from the end-user to the cache through diverse network hops.

Thus, the proposed 5G Closeness Centrality metric, as defined in Section 10.5 and calculated by the TMA component of our framework, can be weighted with the latency measurements calculated in real-time by the RMA component, resulting in a new metric called *5G-Cache Closeness Centrality*, which computes the indexes for each of the best physical nodes in the network topology represented in the graph to deploy a vCache VNF, thereby minimizing the delay of the user towards the cache.

Thus, the resultant metric is directly influenced by the network graph, the number of mobile users attached to the set of DUs connected to the Edge, along with the physical network conditions and the actual network conditions, network latency from the UE towards the edge node that deploys the vCache. The low mean UE-Edge latency values assigned to the Edge nodes will prioritize them in the spatial metric against physical machines in the core.

10.6.2 Computation offloading in mMTC

The *5G-Cache Closeness Centrality* metric can also be employed in the MEC scenario to assist in the Computation offloading in mMTC.

The metric can be employed to find out the best Edge node in the 5G network to allocate certain IoT computing tasks, performing computation offloading of IoT devices towards those nodes. Distributed MEC nodes (e.g. Fog Nodes as VNFs) allows reducing the data traffic at the Core network.

In addition to *5GCC* and latency, the decision-making considers other indicators such as the number of available resources in the MEC node in terms of hardware/software capacities, during the constraint satisfaction defined in 10.5.4.

10.6.3 Node Over-Provisioning

Network operators need to quantify continuously network dimensions to satisfy committed network service guarantees specified in the Service-Level Agreement (SLA). Over-provisioning considers, on one hand, the contracted SLAs e.g., in terms of bandwidth and latency, and, on the other hand, what is currently demanded in real-time, considering the network's topology, and on-going measurements and metrics such as the consumed bandwidth.

The degree centrality metric is the simplest centrality index and is defined as the number of connections a node has in a graph. The degree centrality can be calculated using weights, and concretely for this case, the weights can refer to the bandwidth consumed in each of the network interfaces (connections) by a node.

$$E_v = \text{Edges of } V$$

$$OPC(v) = Capacity_b(v) - \sum_{e \in E_v} Bandwidth_c(e) \quad (10.4)$$

Our proposed Node Over-provisioning Centrality $OPC(v)$ metric, combines the degree centrality weighted with the current bandwidth consumed. The resultant metric is defined in Equation 10.4. This metric allows the operator to identify proactively those nodes that are near to be overloaded and could lead to a breach in the contracted SLA.

According to this metric's values, when the node is about to be overloaded $OPC(v) < threshold$ under a certain threshold, the *planner* module of our cognitive management framework is notified, and it can infer certain actions to mitigate the over-provisioning, such as disconnecting certain UE terminals from the DU to force a reconnection to a less overloaded DU (it is noted that the RMA has means to monitor the on-going DU's reachability by the UE). In another example, if the $OPC(v)$ affects a physical node in the Core network, the *planner* can migrate a particular VNF to another physical node with a higher $OPC(v)$ value.

10.6.4 Optimal Location of Load Balancers

Load balancers address scalability in distributed systems by balancing the workload among different servers. The optimal allocation of such VNFs can have a significant impact on the global performance of the network. Different criteria can be used to perform load balancing. It can be done based on real-time bandwidth, latency, the number of requests, etc. Let us consider bandwidth since it is widely adopted nowadays to take load balancing decisions. Our *5GCC* can be combined with such metrics to determine the critical point in the network where more bandwidth is concentrated and, at the same time, where this selected node is more in the middle of the paths between servers and clients. To achieve this, $d_G^b(s, d)$ is defined as the shortest path weighted by bandwidth between the source (s) and the destination (d). Thus, replacing this function in equation 2, we can define the metric for the Optimal Location of Load Balancers (*OLLB*).

Therefore, human dynamics such as sleeping, working, relaxing, and moving to different locations will have an impact on the spatial aggregation of the real-time consumed bandwidths along the time, causing a recalculation of the *OLLB*. This *OLLB* metric can then be utilized to determine the location where to migrate or deploy a load balancer in real-time to keep optimum the placement to maximize the balancing of the workloads in the network. *OLLB* considers available resources in MEC nodes, thereby it allows balancing the load among MEC and Core virtual and physical network nodes.

10.7 Implementation Details

The proposed cognitive network management framework has been prototyped by focusing on implementing the core contribution of this paper, i.e., the TMA, the 5G spatial metrics and the enabling and optimization algorithms, all in a realistic 5G infrastructure testbed.

Specifically, the TMA has been implemented in Java 8 using RabbitMQ v3.7.16¹ as a message broker to receive both topology information and performance metrics, and also to

¹RabbitMQ is available at <https://www.rabbitmq.com/>

publish the calculated spatial metrics into the publication/subscription message bus. The TMA uses as an in-memory graph database, Apache Tinkerpop v3.4.2 backend ².

The TMA has been implemented using three different execution threads. Firstly, a reception thread is in charge of receiving information from both topology and metrics and updating the graph database accordingly. This thread maintains the cache structures required for the calculation of our *5GCC* metric. Secondly, a calculation thread is running at periodic intervals and it performs the update of the values of the spatial network metrics for all the devices of the graph. To do so, the definition of the metric is implemented in the graph engine using the Gremlin query language. Gremlin is a functional, data-flow language that enables users to express queries over their graph. The execution of the Gremlin query makes use of the cached structure or triggers the complete recalculation of the metrics depending on the status of the cache. To allow this optimization to happen, we have combined Java code with Gremlin queries in order to create the optimized iteration of the graph. As a result, this thread keeps in memory the updated values of the spatial metrics. The third and last thread is the sender, in charge of sending periodically the metrics of the devices that have changed with respect to previous values (due to a recalculation). This is a way to optimize the overhead of the cognitive management framework which needs to deal with several metrics for thousands of devices and thus it improves scalability.

The TMA allows on-boarding different metrics from a configuration file where the metrics are defined based on their gremlin query associated. Each metric runs in a different calculation thread. The node selection optimization has been implemented directly as a filter of the Gremlin language whereas the node prune optimization has been implemented by a wrapper of the management functions of the graph (add/remove vertex/edge) to decide if the node needs to be added to or removed from the graph and if the cache structure needs to be updated. The implementation of the algorithm matches exactly the approach presented in the previous section. For the cache, the TMA has implemented the *UEInDu* structure as a *HashMap<String, Set<String>>* and the *UEsWeigthInDu* structure as a *HashMap<String,*

²Apache TinkerPop is available at <http://tinkerpop.apache.org/>

Long> as a way to make the most efficient acceleration in the calculation of the spatial metrics.

10.8 Empirical Validation

All the empirical executions performed in this research work have been carried out in a Cyberserve XE5-308S v4 computer, with Dual E5-2660 v4 Intel Xeon, 14 Cores, 2.00GHz, 35M Cache, 105Watts with hyperthreading activated, 128GiB DIMM DDR4 Synchronous 2400 MHz, 1.6 TB Intel SSD PCIe, and Ubuntu 18.04.2 LTS. That computer runs the TMA software component for the calculation of the spatial metrics. Our 5G infrastructure is composed of nine Cyberserve computers with the same specifications indicated. They run OpenStack Newton³ where one computer is the cloud controller and the other eight are computes employed for a 5G mobile edge computing network. These computes have deployed inside the Mosaic 5G stack⁴. The infrastructure is deployed with Ethus USRP X310 as DU. All the switches of the infrastructure are Netgear GS724T at 1 Gbps ethernet. Three different testbeds have been designed and executed to validate the suitability of the approach proposed. They are explained in the following subsections together with the results achieved.

10.8.1 5G Topology Scalability Results

Firstly, a scalability test has been conducted with the main aim to show how the proposed metrics can be calculated on large scale infrastructures. To emulate large-scale infrastructures with up to 1 million UE devices, we have collected our own topological information of the 40 UE devices and 3 DUs we have in our premises and then created an augmented dataset for different sizes and topology shapes. The dataset created triggers real 5G events such as adding or removal of nodes/edges in the network. For this purpose, we use exactly the same APIs as those used in our 5G deployment in production in order to make sure we gather the

³OpenStack is available at <https://www.openstack.org/>

⁴Mosaic 5G is available at <http://mosaic-5g.io/>

same results in terms of performance as if running in such large-scale infrastructure. Our 5G deployment matches that described in subsection 10.4.2.

The different topologies analyzed are depicted in Table 10.2 where the number of UE devices connected to a DU is ranged exponentially from 1 to 1024, the number of physical machines in the edge of the network is ranged exponentially from 1 to 256, and the number of physical machines in the core of the network is ranged from 16 to 64. The rest of the values have been kept constant and set to realistic numbers. Four DUs have been allocated per edge physical machine and Eight tenants share each of these physical machines in both edge and core. In 5G operations, it implies that Eight different telecommunication operators share the same edge, which is a very realistic scenario. For instance, Edotco which is a tower company owned by Asian telecommunications group has at least six subsidiary mobile operators sharing the same infrastructure [87]. Also, it is expected an increment on the number of tenants sharing the same edges due to the accessibility of 5G networks for start-ups network companies [88]. In addition, it has been decided to connect only one server to each of the physical machines of the core network. Such computer represents an access point to the Internet. Finally, the bandwidth available and latency values have been fixed to specific values to represent real scenarios. However, these values don't affect the performance of TMA but only the result value of the metric. The bandwidth has been fixed to 10 Gbps between the RAN and the Edge and 100 Gbps between Edge and Core. These values are expected values in 5G networks due to the maximum capacity of network cards used in these segments. The latency has been fixed to 30 μ s for all the segments which are a typical average value.

It is noted that the largest scenario represented in Table 10.2 to be executed corresponds to a 5G topology with $1024 * 4 * 256 = 1,048,576$ mobile users connected which is the size of a very realistic medium-size city. For that scenario, Figure 10.4 shows the description of the population of nodes and edges that conform that topology in order to allow a reader to understand the nature of the graph. As shown in Figure 10.4, 99.21% of the nodes and connections represent UE devices. It is also worth remarking that only the 0.03% represented

Table 10.2 Ranging of generated scenarios for empirical validation experiments

Property	Min value	Max value	Function
Number of <i>UE</i> x <i>DU</i>	1	1024	$\sum_{i=0}^{10} 2^i$
Number of <i>DU</i> x <i>Edge</i>	4	4	$CONST(4)$
Number of <i>Tenants</i> x <i>Edge</i>	8	8	$CONST(8)$
Number of <i>Edge</i>	1	256	$\sum_{i=0}^8 2^i$
Number of <i>Servers</i> x <i>Tenant</i>	1	1	$CONST(1)$
Number of <i>Tenants</i> x <i>Core</i>	8	8	$CONST(8)$
Number of <i>Core</i>	16	64	$\sum_{i=4}^6 2^i$
Bandwidth <i>RAN</i> – <i>Edge</i>	10 Gbps	10 Gbps	$CONST(10Gbps)$
Bandwidth <i>Edge</i> – <i>Core</i>	100 Gbps	100 Gbps	$CONST(100Gbps)$
Global Latency	30 μ s	30 μ s	$CONST(30\mu s)$

physical machines in edge and core network segments are the candidates to allocated VNFs. This largest scenario is composed by a graph with 1,056,724 vertices and 1,059,291 edges.

Fig. 10.4 Distribution analysis of the population of the 5G network topology

To facilitate a 3D representation of the spatial-temporal relationship, we represent each dimension of the three in different figures. Thus, Figure 10.5, 10.6 and 10.7 represent analogous graphs when it exponentially increases the number of physical machines used in the core network segment. Each of these figures shows an exponential increase in both the number of UE (x-axis) and the number of edges (y-axis). The time shown in the z-axis follows a linear increase. From the three figures, in all the cases, it can be seen how the increase in the number of UE does not affect the time to calculate the 5GCC metric. This is a significant achievement since they are the vast majority of nodes connected to the 5G network. It can be seen as well in all the figures that when the number of edges is increased, the calculation time increases accordingly. Similarly, comparing the same data series in different plots, it can be seen how increasing the number of cores, the calculation time also

increases, accordingly. It means that the internal topology of the 5G network has an influence on the calculation time, mainly due to the fact that the algorithms calculate the shortest paths. The overall execution time increases almost linearly regardless of the workload in the number of edges.

Let us focus on the largest scenario, with 1 million 5G UE connected to the 5G network. The reader can see how each of the Figures 10.5, 10.6 and 10.7 represents three series plotted in different colours. They represent different scenarios over the same 5G topology. Specifically, they represent the levels of stress of the 5G topology. If the infrastructure is not running any service inside, all the physical machines can be candidates to host services due to the fact that the constraint satisfaction will not discard any unsuitable candidates. However, if the infrastructure is running several services and close to be out of remaining free capacity, the number of physical machines that can be candidates to be selected to allocated services is significantly reduced. The different series represent the percentage of physical machines that are suitable to allocate the new service. They are 100% candidates (theoretical - no stress), 20% of candidates (realistic - highly stressed scenario) and 80 % of candidates (realistic - low stressed scenario). Other intervals have been calculated and they follow the expected trend. It is noted that when the infrastructure is more stressed, the time to calculate the metric is significantly reduced. It helps on the scalability of the calculation of the metric. For 256 edges, 16 core machines and 1 million UE devices in Figure 10.5, the metric is calculated in fewer than 20 seconds for very realistic scenarios with 80% of suitable candidates, thereby allowing decision-making related to the structure of the network in a very short time, e.g., allocating a virtual Cache or a virtual Load Balancer. For a similar scenario but with a much more complex core network of 64 core machines, the time to calculate the metric is 60 seconds, which is still within a very acceptable boundary in practical terms. It is very important to remark that all the results presented herein do not make use of the *5GCC* retrieval optimization and they are the time to calculate the metric without any cached data (i.e., worst case scenario).

Figure 10.8 shows how the number of core physical machines affects the calculation time of the metric when fixing the number of edges to 128. It can be seen how the impact on

Fig. 10.5 Time required by TMA to calculate 5GCC without cached data for a topology with 16 Core physical machines when ranging the number of edge machines and the number of UE devices connected to the DU of such edges

Fig. 10.6 Time required by TMA to calculate 5GCC without cached data for a topology with 32 Core physical machines when ranging the number of edge machines and the number of UE devices connected to the DU of such edges

ranging the edges is more dominant than ranging core machines. Moreover, in all the cases analyzed, the metric shows a linear trend despite the exponential aspect of the axis. This is a clear sign of the high scalability results achieved with our proposal, and thus the proposed

Fig. 10.7 Time required by TMA to calculate 5GCC without cached data for a topology with 64 Core physical machines when ranging the number of edge machines and the number of UEs connected to the DU of such edges

approach can be applied in large-scale networking scenarios such as the Load balancing case in mMTC. These results make the metric usable and feasible and can bring significant improvements over the decision-making in the cognitive framework.

Fig. 10.8 Time required by TMA to calculate 5GCC without cached data for a topology with 128 Edge physical machines when ranging the number of core machines and the number of UE devices connected to the DU of such edges

10.8.2 Algorithm Computational Efficiency Results

Secondly, a comparison of performance has been undertaken to show the improvement in computational complexity achieved with the different optimization schemes proposed in the calculation of the spatial metrics over the traditional reference *CC* metric.

Figure 10.10 shows the time to calculate the spatial metric for a small-size scenario with 4 DUs, 256 UE devices per DU, 4 Edge machines and 4 Core machines where all of the machines are potential candidates to allocate a VNF. It is noted that this small-size scenario is to establish a comparison with the traditional Closeness Centrality (*CC*) metric shown in the "No optimization" series of Figure 10.10. The reader can see that it follows an exponential trend in complexity. The points of the graph for 2048 and 4096 UE devices are plotted out of the scale, and this is why the small sub-figure embedded in the right side has been embedded to allow the reader to see the impractical nature of this *CC* metric due to the complexity associated to its calculation. It takes about 1,500.000 milliseconds to compute the largest scenario. The complexity is significantly reduced by two levels of magnitude when the node selection optimization is executed, leading to about 10,000 milliseconds. It is further optimized by another level of magnitude when the prune optimization is also applied over the previous optimization, resulting in about 1,000 milliseconds. These results are plotted in Figure 10.10. When the 5GCC retrieval optimization is further utilized and the calculation of the metric is cached, the execution time is reduced by yet another extra three levels of magnitude. The y-axis in Figure 10.10 does not show enough resolution, and this is why it has been decided to create the sub-graph located in the left-side of Figure 10.10 with a zoom in the scale. It can be seen that the calculation time is remarkably reduced to only around 1 millisecond for the largest scenario analyzed. This excellent result clearly indicates that the proposed approach is able to support real-time use cases such as the Proactive cache allocation case and also the computation offloading case. It is noted that it is foreseen that in the vast majority of the time the metric will be cached and only when new VNFs are deployed or migrated it will need to invalidate the cache. These results clearly validate the scalability and practicality of the results achieved in this contribution and the feasibility of the practical application into the 5G networks.

Fig. 10.9 Whisker plot showing insert time to the database for vertices (Devices) and edges (Connections)

10.8.3 Graph Management Results

Lastly, Figure 10.9 depicts the analysis of the performance of the TMA component in terms of the management of topological changes in the infrastructure. This experiment has monitored the time required to insert each of the elements of the largest graph utilized in this research work, i.e. the scenario composed by 64 Cores, 256 Edges, 8 tenants which implies 8 VMs in every Core and Edge, 1 server per Core VM, 4 DUs per Edge and 1024 UEs per DU, in total 1,048,576 mobile users. The graph is composed of 1,056,724 vertices and 1,059,291 edges, representing devices and connections between devices respectively. This times plot includes both the addition of the components to the Gremlin graph framework and the updates for all the different cache structures used in the TMA for optimizing the

Fig. 10.10 Comparison of Computational Complexity in the calculation of 5GCC metric over the different optimization schemes

calculation of the metrics (described in previous sections). Figure 10.9 shows a whisker plot with the analysis of such behaviours. It is worth mentioning that the four quartiles of the distribution are concentrated in one point, representing almost 100% of the cases, yielding around 0.05753782 and 0.05263078 milliseconds, respectively for the insertion of vertices/devices and edges/connections. These results show very similar behaviour between the management of topological changes for both devices and connections. Moreover, these results are at the microsecond scale, which clearly demonstrates the stability on the behaviour of the proposed system and the efficiency in dealing with constant topological changes. It is noted how there are some outliers shown in both plots, which may be due to the fact that the calculation of the metrics maybe work in parallel in another thread while the topological change has arrived, thus causing some sharing of resources of the same machine. They represent the 0.00001 percent of the cases and the worst-case scenario is around 200 ms, which is still acceptable in use cases that do not have a strict time constraint.

10.9 Discussion

This section presents a discussion about other alternatives that could be considered and developed in future work. In this paper, four different use cases for the novel multi-tenant 5G networks have been analyzed. However, the solution proposed in this work is not restricted to these use cases since it is based on the universal definition of closeness centrality.

Our proposal has optimized the number of nodes where 5GCC has been calculated by selecting a smaller subset. The reader may think of a possible optimization where the metric is tailored for specific purposes and the destinations used for the calculation of the shortest path are also restricted to a smaller subset, shaping the graph according to a specific problem faced. E.g. to calculate the closeness to respect to a concrete type of VNF, rather than the closeness to respect to all the other nodes in the network. However, we would lose generality achieved in our proposed 5GCC metric. Moreover, the algorithm would need to iterate anyway to all the nodes available to determine their type of node (e.g. type of VNF) and, in consequence, it will not be any improvement in terms of performance. The alternative would be to have an in-memory graph for each type of metric, which its associated consumption in memory and scalability limitations are associated with.

Another possible optimization could be based on the extension of the support in the framework for additional kind of spatial metrics. For instance, *Degree Centrality*, a much simpler metric in computational cost, can provide the number of neighbours that every node has connected. This metric can be applied when deciding where to deploy a new router in the infrastructure depending on whether a router can route the maximum number of different destinations. In addition, *Betweenness Centrality* metric, that measures how many times a node appears in the shortest path between any other nodes in the graph, might be applied in similar 5G scenarios as the ones discussed in this paper, giving meaningful information about the centrality. However, such a metric requires higher computation cost on average, and cannot be easily optimized simplifying the graph, as it is done in our proposal.

As future work, authors would like to parallelize the calculation of the metrics using a map-reduce or other alternative distributed framework to further increase both efficiency and

scalability. In addition, authors will look into the adaptation and applicability of the proposed model to efficiently manage beyond 5G networks and IoT complex network topologies.

10.10 Conclusions

5G cognitive network management requires advanced network topological knowledge in a new complicated networking paradigm featured with virtualization and multi-tenancy. This paper has proposed a novel framework that is capable of meeting such challenging requirements for various use cases such as cache allocation, computation offloading and load balancing. In particular, within this framework, new spatial metrics especially a 5G Closeness Centrality metric has been designed, and a set of enabling or optimization algorithms have been proposed. Furthermore, a new 5G architectural component TMA is introduced to monitor such spatial metrics over virtualized, multi-tenanted 5G networks. Moreover, a set of optimization schemes have explored to accelerate the calculation of the new 5G spatial metrics. A realistic testbed has been deployed to test, validate and evaluate the proposed approach. Empirical results have demonstrated the high scalability of the approach over varied network topologies of large scales (with over 1 million mobile user devices and over 1 million connections), and the real-time performance in calculating the spatial metrics to allow timely cognition (only about 1 ms when optimization schemes are applied) and in handling constant topology changes in 5G networks (in the order of 10s of ms).

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Chapter 11

New Immersive Interface for Zero-Touch Management in 5G Networks

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11.1 Abstract

Network management have posed ever-increasing complexity with the evolution of virtualized and softwarized mobile networking paradigm, demanding advanced network visualization and automation technologies to address this significant paradigm shift. This paper provides a novel holographic immersive network management interface that extends the standardized ETSI Zero-Touch Network and Service Management (ZSM) reference architecture to allow network administrators to understand real-time automated tasks in a 5G network without human intervention. This augmented reality based system has been validated and prototyped using Microsoft Hololens 2 in a realistic 5G infrastructure.

11.2 Introduction

Virtualization and softwarization are cornerstone technologies for 5G and beyond next-generation networks. These technologies have led to a significant reduction of capital expenditure (CAPEX) thanks to the employment of commercial-off-the-shelve computers and the better usage of available resources due to the consolidation of workloads. However, the complexity of the networks has also significantly increased with the introduction of virtual switches, routers, kernel-bypass networking technologies and others. This complexity would result in a notable increase of operational expenditure (OPEX). Consequently, Zero-Touch Management (ZTM) has become a hot topic currently in the process for standardization, e.g., by the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) Zero-Touch Network and Service Management (ZSM) working group[89]. The main aim of ZTM is the automation of configuration, monitoring and control tasks in large-scale networks to obtain a full end-to-end architecture framework designed for closed-loop automation without requiring human intervention. The usage of ZTM is expected to enable automating essential network management tasks that are traditionally manually handled by network administrators to be executed automatically by a computer system. This will accomplish a substantial reduction in OPEX.

In this context, ZTM targets to achieve autonomic management of large-scale 5G networks using automation as a key technology. However, when an autonomous system takes the control of the network, it makes autonomous decisions at different speeds. Thus, the human can easily miss out at least part of the information about the system's behaviour or may be unable to understand the underlying reason why the system is behaving in such a way at runtime. It leads to the challenge and requirement of monitoring and judging if the ZTM system is functioning correctly in a timely and direct fashion.

To address these problems, it entails the creation of a novel visualization-based immersive approach that enables network administrators to interact with a ZTM system in an intuitive manner, by introducing an immersive graphical user interface (GUI) that allows humans to understand the autonomic processes being executed. This GUI should provide debugging capabilities so that the user can visualize and understand the behaviour of the autonomous system and determine the correctness of the behaviour. The design of this ZTM GUI is the main motivation of this work.

The key innovations achieved in this work are as follows:

- A novel extension of the ETSI ZSM framework with holographic capabilities to enable the attachment of holographic interfaces.
- A new immersive holographic Human-Computer Interface assuming a full autonomous behaviour and the user being a spectator that can visualize the current status of the system and the different actions taken by the ZTM system.
- Both the extended framework and the GUI have been designed, prototyped and validated using a 5G multi-tenant network testbed deployed in our premises.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Section II provides an overview of the state of the art in Zero-Touch Network Management systems and debugging methods. Section III presents the proposed system architecture. Section IV describes the proposed holographic GUI. Section V presents the validation and performance results. Finally, Section VI concludes the paper.

11.3 Related Work

There has always been an interest in automating any network management task. Since the advent of virtualization and softwarization technologies, this particular area of research has gained momentum where researchers, projects, and standardization bodies have been able to make progress towards closed-loop automation of network and service management operations. This is the case of the H2020 SELFNET project [90], [91] that based the core of its investigation on addressing autonomic network management framework to achieve self-organizing capabilities in managing 5G network infrastructures. Researchers in [92], [93] show closed-loops of operational processes and tasks executed automatically to address particular use cases. More recently studies based in Zero-touch systems [94, 89] have paved the way for introducing a common architecture for a new Zero-touch network and Service Management paradigm.

Despite the numerous advances made in recent years in this area, the human being has been always interested in to supervise and to closely monitor decisions made by any autonomous systems. Analyzing network behaviour and its current status is an imperative feature for network administrators to confirm the correct functioning of all services running on top of the network architecture. The incoming 5G Networks impose high requirements with respect its flexible and dynamic topology [95], which are even pushed to the extreme in Zero-touch Systems [89], where Virtual Network Functions (VNFs) and/or network links may be instantiated or destroyed as part of an orchestrated plan to address any issue or improvement in the network without human intervention (and probably without even knowing it) [96, 97]. However, typical monitoring systems do not auto-discover devices or networks (being necessary to configure each device that needs to be monitored with a configuration file) and barely offer a WebApp where data can be viewed in an old-fashioned graphical web-based frontend. In [98] authors provide an open-source software for integrating Nagios [99] and OpenStack [100] to achieve an adaptive distributed monitoring architecture automatically deployed in the cloud infrastructure. Software-Defined Network (SDN) Controllers such as OpenDayLight [35] also present advanced monitoring capabilities including auto-discover functionalities, multi-tenant isolation and graphical interfaces. Skydive [12] and MidoNet

[36] are advanced open-source real-time network topology tools able to discover physical and overlay networks of both virtual machines and containers with multi-tenant support. However, none of the aforementioned solutions offers a complete answer where 5G mobility of the user equipment (UE) needs to be tracked, 5G VMs are dynamically migrated or specialized hardware such as radio equipment also needs to be monitored. Furthermore, none of the monitoring tools found in the state of the art has the ability to monitor any combination of the administrative domains (including the E2E) of a 5G network architecture.

Our contribution aims to present the first of the next generation monitoring tools that harness the benefits of future 5G networks to in turn provide them back high-quality, real-time and visually understandable information by providing an immersive human-machine interface.

11.4 Proposed Framework Architecture

Fig. 11.1 illustrates the core concept of the ZSM reference architecture produced and approved by the ETSI Zero touch network and Service Management Industry Specification Group (ZSM ISG) [101]. The ZSM architecture is divided into different areas representing the separation of multiple management domains (MDs) which are responsible for their own full-automation of operations shown in Fig. 11.1 as Monitoring, Analysis, Decision and Actuation. This architecture seeks of modularity, extensibility, scalability and resiliency as its main principles. The E2E MD is in charge of coordinate and orchestrate between the multiple MDs (and their services) belonging to different administrative entities, thus achieving and end-to-end management and reducing the overall system's complexity. Every MD, including the E2E, provides a set of ZSM service capabilities by management functions that expose and/or consume a set of service end-points. These services and consequently, its produced data, can be in turn used by any E2E service (e.g., intelligence services) to feed domain-level and/or cross-domain mechanisms. Throughout the cross-domain integration fabric (depicted in the middle of the figure) it is enabled an access to reach, if required, exposed cross-domain endpoints. It is worth noting that some services are only provided and consumed locally

inside the management domain (by using the intra-domain integration fabric) and do not provide any cross-domain service/data exposure.

Fig. 11.1 The ZSM architecture and the proposed holographic extension

The E2E automation and zero-touch management of network services and infrastructures rely on the ability of close the management loop. Fig. 11.1 illustrates Management Domains that are composed by the following service management functions: (1) The monitoring component in charge of collecting performance information about the managed resources of such domain; (2) The analytic component that is in charge of the autonomous detection

of alarms that need to be handled in the system; (3) The decision making component is in charge of the autonomous decision to handle and/or mitigate the alarms; (4) The actuator in charge of the enforcing of the decisions into the MD; And finally, (5) the topology inventory has all the information about devices, ports, flows, connections and other relevant metadata about the infrastructure of the MD.

Management Domains not only provide access to their ZSM services but are also capable to consume ZSM services provided by other MDs. Similarly, other consumers such as vertical applications can consume ZSM services exposed by the E2E service management domain and the intra management domains. In summary, the ZSM framework reference architecture offers cross-domain data services that can be consumed by: a) The E2E service management domain; b) Management intra-domains; c) Any other ZSM Framework consumer.

The ZSM framework reference architecture follows the current trend to move away from static management systems to more flexible sets of management services. This contribution leverages the ZSM framework reference architecture to provide a novel service. Fig. 11.1 depicts (top-right corner) an E2E service and its interfaces, which are described in the following section, to provide holographic network management capabilities.

11.5 Proposed Immersive Interface for ZTM

This section describes the proposed Immersive Interface for Zero-Touch Network and Service Management. This interface has been integrated in an Augmented Reality headset to provide full 3D immersive view of the autonomous management that is happening in the network (see Fig. 11.2). The interface provide a full spectator view where users can interact with their voice and hands to explore the topology. This exploration system provides a 3D logical representation where are rendered all the Physical Machines (PMs), Virtual Machines (VMs), Physical Switches, Software Switches (Open vSwitch¹ and Linux Bridges), Physical Routers, Remote Radio Heads (RRHs) and UE. This information is stored in the "Topology Inventory"

¹Open vSwitch is available at <http://www.openvswitch.org/>

of the ZSM architecture and discovered by the network probes installed in the different components of the architecture.

Fig. 11.2 Topology exploration system

Fig. 11.2 shows an example of visualization of a network topology. Every box in the figure represent a different type of device. This topology has two different levels in the Z axis. On the top, the Virtual Networks are rendered where all the VMs are allocated. In this case, it can be distinguish VMs with two colors. This means that there are two different tenants sharing the infrastructure and each color represent the owner of each one of them. The VMs are linked to a PM that host such VM in the bottom level. This bottom level represents the Physical Network. PMs are connected between them through different switches. In this topology, it can be seen four Core PMs placed in the centre of the network and 4 Edge PMs placed on the boundaries of the topology. All the PMs placed in the Core segment are also connected to other servers that give access to different services. Every PM in the Edge segment have two 5G RRHs connected that give access to UE devices to the network. Furthermore, it can be appreciated some warnings triangles on top of some devices. Those warnings represent alerts that have happened to something related to those devices. This view allow the administrator to explore the complete network and understand their interconnections. VM migrations are shown in real-time when happening.

Fig. 11.3 Topology metrics view

Moreover, the user can access the metrics for every single device and every single device port managed in the infrastructure. To get access to the available metrics of a concrete device the user can tap on the box that represent this device. This will open the perspective shown in Fig. 11.3. This figure shows the internal layout of a device. Each sphere rendered on the device represents an interface. If the user tap on them it will show the metrics available for such interface. The device of Fig. 11.3 has three physical interfaces. Inside of the device there are two software switches than can be also clicked. These software switches have more interfaces that follow the internal datapath of the device. The spheres on top of the device are the logical interfaces that provide connectivity to the VMs hosted in this PM. On top of the device there are different holographic buttons for every real-time metric available for this device. This information is provided by the monitoring architectural component of the ZSM architecture. Then, to visualize the metric the user just tap on it.

Fig. 11.4 shows what happen when the CPU Usage metric is selected. This action opens a graph board using the units provided by this metric. In this case is a percentage metric that varies through the time. The system start rendering the real-time values provided by the monitoring system.

Fig. 11.4 Topology CPU usage view

In addition, users can visualize events that are taking place in real-time for all the previous components cited. When the user clicks the warning on top of the device, the perspective shown in Fig. 11.5 appears. This perspective shows the list of events received for this device. The events are represented in three colors, red, yellow and green. Red is used for alerts that are automatically detected but are not automatically mitigated and thus require human intervention. These alerts are generated by the anomaly based analytics module of the ZSM framework. The yellow alert represents events that are automatically detected and the system knows how to solve them but requires of human confirmation to be automatically enforced. The steps to solve the alert are provided by the decision making module. Finally, green alerts are used when the framework components of detection, decision and mitigation have already applied a complete solution to mitigate the alert without human intervention. These alerts will not last indefinitely, so they will be removed after a certain period of time set by the user or when being seen/addressed. Notice that when the user is exploring the topology, only one colored alert is shown on top of the devices despite of the number of alerts associated to it. In this case, the color rendered will be the one belonging to the most critical alert (red > yellow > green).

Fig. 11.5 Topology alerts view

11.5.1 Implementation Details

The interface has been prototyped and implemented in Unity3D using C# for the scripting backend. The system supports both holographic headset: *Microsoft HoloLens 1st and 2nd Gen*. To make it possible for the gesture interactions with holograms, it adopted the *Mixed Reality Toolkit* version 2.1.0 provided by Microsoft. In order to communicate with all the components in the ZTM system, the system employed RabbitMq, which provides good scalability results and support for different platforms. Nonetheless, *HoloLens (1st Gen)* run over a x86 architecture, and for this reason *RabbitMq client* had to be adapted using the C client compiled for x86 and wrapped, making it compatible for *Universal Windows Platforms* over WinRT. All the messages exchanged followed a JSON format. *Newtonsoft.Json* was employed to serialize and deserialize these JSONs.

11.6 Empirical Validation and Performance Results

This section presents the validation and scalability tests conducted using the proposed interface.

11.6.1 Testbed Description

The execution of all the tests have been carried out using a realistic 5G infrastructure deployed in our premises. This infrastructure is composed of 20 PMs in the core of the network and four PMs in the edge; each one of these edge PMs has connected two RRHs and each one of those RRHs has connected eight UE devices. This infrastructure is shared by two tenants that have VM instances in every PM. The RRHs are Ettus USRP B210 SDR DUs. Each PM in the infrastructure is a high-performance laptop EUROCOM Sky X9E3, with Intel CPU i7 7700K 4.2GHz and 64GB RAM DDR4-2400. The UE devices in the infrastructure correspond to different IoT devices distributed along the campus. However, to test the scalability of the proposed framework, these UE devices have been extended using the emulation mode supported by the 5G Radio Access Network (RAN) and Core network stack. OpenAirInterface was employed as 5G stack and OpenStack was used for the management of the resources. OpenDayLight and OpenVSwitch were incorporated as a SDN control framework.

11.6.2 Interface Validation

To validate the proposed GUI, the screenshots shown in Fig. 11.2, Fig. 11.3, Fig. 11.4 and Fig. 11.5 have been taken as a demonstration of the functional validation of the system. These screenshots were taken in the Microsoft HoloLens 2 headset and they show the deployed architecture in our premises, providing evidence of the system running in real-time. The total time to render this topology in the interface took approximately 15 seconds from cold-start in Microsoft HoloLens 2 and after that, it yielded 25 frames per second (FPS) performance providing real-time immersive experience for the user.

11.6.3 Performance Results

To provide scalability results for the implemented interface, the UE devices connected to the network have been extended using the emulation mode. Thus, the total number of UE ranged

exponentially from 64 to 2048 (64, 126, 256, 1024 and 2048). These performance results were conducted using the *Microsoft HoloLens 2* headset.

Fig. 11.6 Time to render all the devices in the immersive GUI for every scenario

Fig. 11.6 shows the time that the GUI took to render all the devices in the topology since it received the first one until the last one was rendered. The graph shows similar results in the first three scenarios that correspond to topologies with 64, 128 and 256 UE devices in total. However, the three following ones (512, 1024, 2048) show an exponential trend. It took around 50 seconds for the scenario with 512 UE, around 2 minutes for the scenario with 1024 UE and less than 6 minutes for the scenario with 2048 UE. This exponential trend was due to the number of polygons drawn by the headset. The hardware is limited in this kind of devices since the rendering of 3D elements is an expensive task that requires GPU processing. These results indicate how much it took for the system to converge, allowing the user to start using it with a complete view of the network. However, it does not imply a scalability problem as indicated next.

Fig. 11.7 shows the FPS that the headset is able to generate while the complete process of rendering the largest topology analyzed in Fig. 11.6, which has a total of 2138 devices (including 2048 UE). The FPS were measured every 5 seconds. In the first 30 seconds

Fig. 11.7 Frames per second measured every 5 seconds while rendering a topology scenario containing 2138 devices

the interface started and stabilized at around 25 FPS (A). After that, the interface started receiving the elements from the topology. In the first 20 seconds after receiving the first element (B), the interface have already started drawing elements and suffered an exponential decreasing in FPS. The FPS continued decreasing slightly until 2 FPS (C). After 5 minutes drawing the entire topology, the interface was able to recover until approximately 25 FPS (D), which is beyond of the minimum frame rate the human requires to experiment sensation of visual continuity [102]. Thus, it will allow a human to navigate in real-time across the topology and understand what is happening in the system since now all the topology has been drawn with FPS still being around 25.

11.7 Conclusions

This paper presents a novel immersive holographic Human-Computer interface for Zero-Touch Network and Service Management systems. The GUI has been designed and implemented to be a debugging tool for network administrators and users in general, in order to provide an spectator view and allow them to understand the current state of the overall

network and the actions taken by the autonomous system. The ETSI ZSM framework has been extended to allow the integration with the proposed interface. The interface has been validated over a realistic 5G multi-tenant network testbed. Scalability results have been performed by ranging different sizes of network topologies. These results have determined that the scalability is limited by the hardware where the application is deployed. However, when measuring the FPS, relevant results have been obtained in the frame rate after drawing the complete topology (around 25 FPS) for a topology size of 2138 devices.

Future work will target at further improving scalability of the proposed system. To this end, it is planned to integrate the interface with holographic remote rendering, which would allow extracting the hosting to an external computer. This would enable access to powerful external resources and offload the holographic headset.

11.8 Acknowledgements

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Chapter 12

Topology Awareness for Smart 5G eMBB Network Slicing VNF Placement

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12.1 Abstract

This paper presents an architecture to gather non-traditional metrics from 5G multi-tenant infrastructure using information about the network topology to take smart decisions on where to optimal placement VNFs that are used to provide services to network slices. The metrics considered are spatial metrics, where information about the shape and size of the network topology is taken into consideration. The architecture has been prototypical validated showing how optimal decisions are taken in an eMBB high-dense scenario, with topologies up to 65538 mobile users geographically concentrated on the same location. Our prototype is able to deal with the calculation of such spatial metrics over the 5G multi-tenant network with 65538 mobile users within 20 seconds, which make it viable at operational phase.

12.2 Introduction

The imminent Fifth-Generation (5G) mobile networks are intrinsically linked to virtualisation and containerisation. This introduces significant costs reduction making usage of softwarisation and key enablers such as Software Defined Networks (SDN) or Network Functions Virtualisation (NFV). SDN pursue the separation of network control functions from network forwarding functions whereas NFV seeks the execution of network functions in virtualised environments. A large-scale 5G multi-tenant network will require a significant amount of different Virtual Network Functions (VNF) to provide support for all the tenants of the infrastructure. The efficient management and orchestration of such large-scale amount of VNFs represents a significant challenge to be addressed.

VNFs are network functions that can deliver services to network slices by using Service Function Chain (SFC), which is a set of ordered network functions providing specific features to the network flows that compose such network slice. The placement of such VNFs along any possible location in the infrastructure will have a significant impact in the efficient management and orchestration of resources to optimise the performance of the delivery of such network services. A wrong choice for the placement of a VNF could incur in extra

delays, packet losses, lack of scalability, possible resource shortages, etcetera, thus it is of critical importance to make an efficient decision on the allocation of such VNFs.

This is specially relevant in the context of 5G multi-tenant networks where the ambitious requirements imposed by the 5G use cases such as Enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB), Ultra-reliable Low Latency Communications (URLLC) and Massive Machine Type Communications (mMTC) will stress even more the importance of the optimal placement of VNFs.

There exists a number of research works focused on improving the placement of VNF. However, almost the vast majority of them only consider metrics and capabilities related to the state of the physical machines (PMs) and the requirements imposed by the VNFs to take decisions on their placement. Although these works represent a first step on taking informed decisions, they achieve results far to be optimal, mainly due to the fact that they completely ignores information about the shape and size of the network topology and the connectivity among the different physical and virtual VNFs that compose the 5G multi-tenant infrastructure.

The main aim of this contribution is the design and implementation of a novel architecture able to provide structural metrics that are used to achieve a smart VNF placement. To be specific, the main innovations achieved in this architecture are as follows:

1. New spatial metrics to allow metric-aware VNF placement optimisation
2. New topology awareness capabilities to allow end-to-end network slicing optimisation
3. Architecture compatible with multi-tenancy support for multi-operator operational environments

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. Section 12.3 introduces and compares different solutions in the state of the art about VNFs placement strategies. Section 12.4 introduces the proposed architecture to achieve topology awareness metrics. Section 12.5 defines the 5G-aware spatial metrics proposed to be used on VNF placement decisions. Then, section 12.6 describes the proposed VNF placement strategy using the metrics previously

introduced tailored for specific use cases. Afterwards, Section 12.8 presents the performance evaluation of the empirical results obtained. Finally, Section 12.9 concludes this paper.

12.3 Related Work

Key multi-tenant virtualisation technologies such as OpenStack [100] and Kubernetes [103] still making use of a random VNF placement strategy where clearly is impossible to take informed decisions.

Askari et al [104] presents a comprehensive analysis of different VNF placement strategies for Service Chain (SC) provisioning. They conclude that an efficient placement strategy can reduce the operational cost in terms of delay, QoE and economy of service provisioning up to 16% or 23%. This clearly emphasises the importance of taking an optimal decision.

Oechsner and Ripke [63] propose a VNF placement strategy integrated with OpenStack where the infrastructure is modeled as a tree where each node represents a computer which the associated metrics of delay and availability and where such metrics are used to take optimum decisions based on these metrics. Similarly, Alahmad and Agarwal [64] make use of metrics to evaluate both availability and reliability to take optimised VNF placement decisions. Agarwal et al [105] propose a placement strategy based on vertical business requirements, to insert the notion of final-user in the loop. Also, Jemaa et al [106] present strategies that enable QoS-aware VNF placement based on real-time performance metrics and QoS models.

All the previous research works do not consider scenarios where there are multiple geographically separated potential locations to place VNFs. This is, in fact, addressed by Benkacem et al [107] extending the coverage of the network infrastructure to include both edge and core network segments as possible candidate options for VNF placement, which in turn, are based on quality of experience (QoE) metrics.

Laghrissi et al [108] present a benchmark to determine the best algorithms for VNF placement and provide their own predictive placement strategy.

Unfortunately, none of the research works and reference software implementations analysed have considered the use of spatial metrics to inform the decision making process to allocate VNFs. None of them have also ever consider tailored scenarios where not only multi-tenant infrastructures are at operations but also where there are deployments of multiple 5G networks running on top of such tenants where the mobility of 5G users need to be considered across multiple antennas.

Pei et al [66] has gone a step forward making use of the topological information of geo-distributed datacenter to optimise two different use cases. The first case is to optimise the allocation of VNFs making use of the topological information and the service function chain associated to such VNFs. The second case is to enhance such placement by reducing the number of redundant VNF instances by allowing them to take combined workload. This is a solution closer to our approach since it take partially into consideration topological information. However, they only take a partial representation of the topology where there is not any 5G infrastructure elements, and not any user mobility across the infrastructure. Furthermore, their experiments have been tested only on a small scale (75 nodes) network topology, clearly need further optimisation. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first proposal that considers the topological information coming from different and heterogeneous data sources, including, physical infrastructure, virtual infrastructure, 5G mobile network infrastructure and 5G final-users in order to take VNF placement decisions based on the current shape and size of the network to make sure that such decisions will benefit to the majority of the users, which is a clear way to optimise resource allocation decisions.

12.4 Topology-awareness in 5G Multi-tenancy Networks

Fig 12.1 shows an overview of the proposed architecture to achieve a smart VNF placement strategy. The architecture consists on different software architectural components exchanging messages through a middle-ware communication message bus using a publication/subscription paradigm. All the subscribers of a given topic will receive the messages associated and the senders will publish those messages to react the interested parties.

Fig. 12.1 Architecture Overview of our Topology-awareness system in 5G Multi-tenancy Networks

The three bottom components in Fig 12.1 are responsible for gathering the topological information from the underline infrastructure, keeping such information up-to-date and reporting it every time there is a change in the topology (see *Topology Exchange*). These agents are described as follows:

Resource Inventory Agent (RIA) is a component deployed inside each physical and virtual machine of the 5G multi-tenant network. It is responsible for generating the topological information for all the devices, ports and connections between ports available inside of the machine. RIA is responsible for discovering the VMs and physical and virtual network interfaces as well as logical switches and interconnection between network interfaces.

Topology Inventory Manager (TIM) is a component deployed in the management plane that provides information not available inside the computers/devices, where RIA is deployed. This lack of availability could be for two different reasons. Firstly, RIA cannot be installed in closed hardware devices such as managed switches and routers and thus topological information needs to be collected from a centralised place. Secondly, there are some cases where information is stored in the management software and not distributed to computers. These are architectural decisions of the management stack used. Therefore, TIM will extract

the information by its integration with the management stack. As example, TIM will extract the tenant information about the networks through the management interfaces of OpenStack.

5G Mobile Agent (MA) is a component deployed in the control plane that provides information about the attachment of the 5G mobile users to the specific 5G distributed units and keeps tracking the user mobility across antennas. To achieve so, this component is directly integrated with the control plane of both 4G and 5G networks by retrieving such information from the 4G Mobility Management Element (MME) and 5G Session Management Function (SMF) / Access and Mobility Management Function (AMF). To be concrete, this integration has been performed by creating an ad-hoc API in the MME implementation of the Mosaic 5G project as described by [85]. Marco et al [86] provides a comprehensive explanation of this API.

The previously described architectural components report the topological information at periodic intervals to keep updated and in real-time the entire network topology discovered.

The key component of the proposed architecture is **VNF Spatial Metric Agent (vSMA)**. It is deployed in the management plane and computes in real-time 5G spatial metrics (explained in section 12.5), based on the topological information reported from the agents. The vSMA keeps the 5G topology updated in a graph structure and performs periodic calculation of the 5G spatial metrics by interrogating the graph in order to extract topology information about size and shape of the networks to make VNF placement optimal. The graph changes continuously according to the reports coming from the topology discovery agents. The framework computes continuously the metrics for each physical server capable of allocating VNFs.

These metrics are then received by the **VNF Scheduler** component of the framework to make advanced topology-aware decisions for 5G network VNF placement. The *VNF Scheduler* is in charge of deciding the VNF placements. In terms of prototypical validation, it is a new scheduling algorithm implemented over OpenStack. This component is also receiving the capabilities of the different options for placement. Thus, the *VNF Scheduler* aggregates information about the available resources (e.g. CPU availability) and combine this knowledge in order to provide the best decision to place the VNF requested.

Finally, the **Compute** components are responsible to enforce the VNF allocation in the associated physical machines. In terms of prototypical validation, this is the traditional OpenStack Nova service ¹.

12.5 5G Spatial Metrics

Spatial networks metrics rely on the structure of the networks, dynamically gathered from the agents in charge of topology discovery to calculate relevant information about the size and shape of the network to make smart decisions on VNF allocation. However, current state of the art is not yet capable of providing spatial network metrics tailored for 5G multi-tenant infrastructures where complex topologies with hundreds of thousands composed the network, including physical and virtual infrastructures and mobile users connected, showing a level of complexity and scalability that makes network graphs impracticable, specially when computing those metrics in real time and considering the whole 5G network topology.

VNF placement decisions require a complete overview of the network topologies to make valuable deployments, for instance, by deciding the allocation of a VNF in an appropriate MEC node depending on the number of connected users and their demands. Figure 12.2 represents graphically the abstraction layer of the graph used to represent a 5G network topology, where it can be identified several User Equipments (UEs) connected to two different 5G Distributed Units (DUs) which are used as radio access network to provide connectivity to the users towards the edge of the network. Two different EDGE computers allocated in two different geographical locations at the edge of the network. They represent physical servers. This two physical servers are connected to routers and switches towards the transport network to interconnect the CORE data center with the edges. The CORE network segment is represented by two physical servers. These 4 different physical servers are hosting a set of VNFs running different services. The naming convention is to make use of a "v" prefix to indicate that they are VNFs. This, vAUSF, vPCF, vSMF, vAMF, vUDM, are all the architectural components of the 5G network running in virtualised machines, the vCU nodes

¹OpenStack Compute (nova) is available at <https://docs.openstack.org/nova/>

represent virtualised Centralised Units, the vVNF node represents a virtualised VNF and vCDN nodes represent a virtualised Content Delivery Network service.

Fig. 12.2 5G Network Graph representation

A useful example and relevant spatial metric is the Closeness Centrality metric [45]. When applied over a 5G multi-tenant network it provides information associated to each node about how close a node is to all the other nodes of the network. Nodes are more central as they are closer to the majority of the other nodes in the graph. Equation 12.1 depicts the formulation of the metric implemented, where V represents the set of available physical servers where a VNF can be placed. Then for each of these servers $C(v)$ is defined as the Closeness Centrality metric for node v . N represents the set of all nodes available in the topology and V is a subset of N only composed by the physical machines. G is defined as the graph of the whole topology where all the nodes (N) are available and also the interconnections between them. Then, $SP_{GB}(v, n)$ is defined as the Shortest Path in the graph G , using bandwidth (B) as weights, between the node v whose metric is being calculated and the rest of the nodes in N . The distance function used on the calculation of the shortest path algorithm is achieved using a weighted graph. It allows the possibility to tailor the metric for specific use cases, for example, for bandwidth optimisation, delay optimisation, wider benefit optimisation, etcetera. The Shortest Path algorithm is based on *Dijkstra's algorithm*, which runs in time $O(m + n \log n)$. It should be noted that this algorithm has been tailored to

5G Multi-tenant Network Topology graphs and thus the metric is only calculated for those nodes that can allocate VNFs.

$$\forall v \in V, C(v) = \frac{1}{\sum_{n \in N} SP_{GB}(v, n)} \quad (12.1)$$

Note that Fig 12.2 has the values calculated over the graph shown in the figure using Eq 12.1 to allow the reader to understand how the algorithm is applied over a given topology. The metric considered is based on wide benefit optimisation, i.e. the metric will indicate the place that will benefit more nodes of the network. Thus, the reader can see how the top score is on the physical machine on EDGE-A where the vast majority of UEs is attached to the radio access network. The calculation of this metric has been implemented inside of the *VNF Spatial Metric Agent* previously described in Section 12.4. This agent keeps a graph model of the whole topology and computes periodically the algorithm to provide the score for every placement option and share it with the *VNF Scheduler*.

12.6 Smart VNF Placement Strategy

The *VNF Scheduler* is receiving at periodic intervals the available resources on all the physical machines of the infrastructure. It is also receiving at periodic interval the metric values of the 5G spatial metric previously described for all the physical machines of the infrastructure. Then, when a VNF placement request is received to the *VNF Scheduler*, the best location to perform the placement is done as follows. First, the subset of physical nodes is filtered according to the requirements for the VNF requested so that a subset of viable placement locations is considered. Then, such placement locations are ordered by the value of the 5G spatial metric and the most optimal location is then selected as a decision to enforce the placement. The most optimal is the one providing the maximum or the minimum value of the metric depending if we are facing a maximisation or a minimisation problem. By making use of the 5G spatial metric, the decision is considering the information of the whole network topology. The best location (that will be selected) is the location that is less used and closest to the majority of UEs. Our Smart VNF Placement Strategy consists on a solution that takes

into account the status of the network topology in real-time. This status in a graph format provide a score for every placement option to be consider.

12.7 eMBB Media Stadium Use Case

This section provides a concrete example for a specific use case to allow the reader to understand the application of the VNF placement strategies in-situ. The use case represents a smart city scenario similar to a large stadium, that consists on a network topology where there is a large amount of UEs connected to the same edge and all of them require an enhanced mobile broadband (eMBB). This is a use case that is being studied by telecommunication operators as a demanding 5G use case where there is a need to adapt the existing infrastructures for the incoming 5G networks deployment.

Fig. 12.2 shown a concrete disposition of the UEs connected to the network. The disposition of the nodes in the graph allow to represent the difference between the amount of UEs connected to each DUs, which are located in different edges in order to represent a high dense scenario and its difference with a low dense one. Obviously, the number of nodes is just example to illustrate the unbalance, and in practice we will have hundreds of thousands of devices. Scalability is addressed in further sections, and the purpose of the graph is to illustrate the effectiveness of the metric so that this distribution of the nodes represent a proportional realistic situation where EDGE-A is serving coverage to the stadium.

The whole procedure to provide a smart VNF placement start gathering metrics from the *Topology Exchange* where the distributed and centralised topology discovery components are reporting. When achieved the topology state shown in Fig. 12.2 the vSMA will have calculated the $C(v)$ metric for every VNF placement candidate. Then, a VNF request to place a vCDN cache to deal with the density of the studio is received, as a high number of users are demand video delivery. Then, the *VNF Scheduler* receives the request and using the best value of metrics to make the decision. In our case, 99 % associated to EDGE-A. As a result, the *VNF Scheduler* decides to place the vCDN tagged the most beneficial location for all the nodes of the network, i.e. EDGE-A.

12.8 Empirical Evaluation

The solution proposed has been implemented using OpenStack VNF placement and an integration of the new proposed scheduling algorithm to consider the metrics reported by our new architectural component *VNF Spatial Metric Agent*. This section describes scalability tests carried out to perform the empirical validation of the proposed architecture for large-scale 5G multi-tenant networks.

12.8.1 Testbed Description

All the empirical executions have been carried out in a Cyberserve XE5-308S v4 computer, with Dual E5-2660 v4 Intel Xeon, 14 Cores, 2.00GHz, 35M Cache, 105Watts with hyperthreading activated, 128GiB DIMM DDR4 Synchronous 2400 MHz, 1.6 TB Intel SSD PCIe, and Ubuntu 18.04.2 LTS. This computer runs the vSMA software component for the calculation of the spatial metrics. Our 5G infrastructure is composed by nine Cyberserve computers with the same specifications indicated. They run OpenStack Newton² where one computer is the cloud controller and the other eight are computes employed for a 5G mobile edge computing network. These computes have deployed inside the Mosaic 5G stack³. The infrastructure is deployed with Ethus USRP X310 as DU. All the switches of the infrastructure are Netgear GS724T at 1 Gbp Ethernet. In order to stress the scalability of the topology, the three different topology discovery components (RIA, TIM and MA) have been extended with an extra functionality that allows to emulate the reporting of large scale infrastructure even if the physical components are not available. This allows us to scale up from only 8 UEs available in our premises to the 65k nodes reported in this contribution. But, it is important to say that the behaviour of the component will be similar when the real users are present in the infrastructure since we are emulating them, and not any simulation is being taking place.

²OpenStack is available at <https://www.openstack.org/>

³Mosaic 5G is available at <http://mosaic-5g.io/>

12.8.2 vSMA Scalability Results

An scalability test has been conducted with the intention of show how the *VNF Spatial Metric Agent* dealing with large-scale topologies to provide metrics to the *VNF Scheduler*. Fig. 12.3 shows the time required (y-axis) by vSMA after receiving the topological information to calculate and report all the values of the metrics for all the possible VNF locations involved in the scenario. The implementation matches the architecture described in Fig 12.1. For all the experiments, the number of physical machines available in the CORE network segment has been fixed to 16 with their associated virtualised components for simplicity. The EDGE physical machines are used to deal with scalability, ranging from 1 to 256, all of them connected to a DU. DUs allows UEs to be connected. A fixed ratio of 256 UEs per DU have been fixed as an example of high dense scenario. Each scenario has 8 different tenants, requiring VNFs to deliver services for the network slices associated to such tenants. These description leads to scenarios ranging exponentially from a minimum of 256 UEs to a maximum of 65536 UEs which is a significant number of UEs to be covered by the stadium use case presented. Notice that these numbers are completely different from the sizes of the topology graphs that are being managed to support such scenarios. To be concrete, the total number of nodes for these two cases are, 2558 nodes for the smallest scenario and 537803 for the biggest one.

As expected, results show an exponential ascendant trend. However, it is very relevant to mention that the metric calculation take less than 1 seconds for up to 8192 UEs and for the largest scenarios with 65536 nodes, it take less than 20 secs which is significant result that allows to take decision on a very decent level of freshness for the metric values.

Fig. 12.4 shows a different perspective for the scalability of the proposed VNF placement strategy. This time the number of UEs is fixed to 65536 UEs, which is the maximum being considered in our experiments due to lack of resources in the data center to perform higher emulations and the ranging is now focused on the number of edge physical machines. The number of UEs connected is always the same for all the experiments and what changes is the ratio of UEs connected to each EDGE, according to the number of EDGES available in the scenario. Thus, the number of edge PMs has been ranged from 1 to 1024 which means

Fig. 12.3 Time required (y-axis) by vSMA to calculate the $C(v)$ for every placement option in a topology with 16 core PMs, a fixed number of 256 UEs per edge PM and ranging the number of edge PMs from 1 to 256. In the x-axis, it shows the total number of UEs in the topology.

that the number of UEs has been ranged from 65536 to 64 to keep the total. The rest of the topology is the same than the one used in the previous experiment.

Fig. 12.4 shows an almost constant trend and around 20 seconds (similar to the biggest scenario previous described) as the time required to calculate the 5G spatial metrics. It clearly shows how scalable the proposed architecture is despite of the number of edge nodes. These results make the 5G spatial metric usable and feasible and demonstrate how the VNF placement decision are optimised to the place where they are most effective for the final user. This placement will allow to provide a smart service in the context of the network slices of each of the tenants available in the infrastructure.

12.9 Conclusion

This paper has proposed a solution based on the usage of topological information which is collected in real-time to provide a topology-aware description of the 5G multi-tenant network. Such information is then used to create new spatial metrics at periodic intervals that allows the VNF Scheduler to take optimal placement strategies by making use of the topological information available. The architecture has been empirically validated based on

Fig. 12.4 Time required (y-axis) by vSMA to calculate the P_{score} for every placement option in a topology with 16 core PMs, ranging the number of edge PMs from 1 to 1024 and keeping a fixed number of 65536 UEs in total for the whole topology. In the x-axis, it shows the total number of edge PMs in the topology.

an OpenStack infrastructure and scalability tests carried out over a realistic 5G multi-tenant network show efficient metric calculation and VNF placement decision to make the system practical in operational phase. VNF placements are taking the same overhead as the original OpenStack scheduler while the time to provide the updated value of the metrics is around 20 seconds for a high dense eMBB scenarios with 65536 UEs, which clearly provides some useful insights of the practical aspects of the approach presented.

As future work, it is planned to improve the system to deal with other aspects that will enrich our existing abstraction of the network topologies, dealing with Lora IoT networks, Wi-Fi networks and other types of networks currently not being addressed in our research work.

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